

D2.3. Technical and Functional Requirements

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, obstructing blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom-free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring of DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science, and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator-free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI-driven DVT detection based on novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography, and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large-scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Task T2.3 and Deliverable D2.3 Description

DoA provides this description of the task T2.3: “The goal of this task is to identify the high-level technical and functional criteria required by the wearable system to effectively and personally monitor, detect, and prevent DVT. Also, this task involves the identification and reviewing of existing integration tools of extended reality, sensor, and motion recognition technologies, to derive the technical specifications for the integration requirements between the different software and hardware components of ThrombUS+. Focus groups and brainstorming sessions will be conducted with clinicians to include the medical perspective. Algorithm requirements will be defined for integration and processing of data stream generated by multisensory system for AI-based decision support, and also for interface with intelligent autonomous wearable. Technical requirements for maximal size, power consumption, durability of reliable sensor contact, unobtrusiveness, and requirements for wireless data communication channels will be defined. The technical academic partner KTU, with extensive experience in medical wearable sensors and sensor networks, will lead this task. All partners will participate to ensure that technical and functional requirements represent all views and are fully understood by the entire consortium. A report on the high-level technical and functional requirements for the wearable system to effectively and personally monitor, detect, and prevent DVT. Output of Task 2.3.”

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Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
APG	Air plethysmography
ASGP	Ambulatory strain gauge plethysmography
CHI	Identifier for ThrombUS+ module Central Hub & Intelligence
CUS	Compression ultrasound imaging
DBQ	Database query plan
DoA	Description of action
DOF	Degrees of freedom
DVI	Deep vein incompetence
DVO	Deep vein occlusion
DVT	Deep vein thrombosis
EIM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Electrical impedance module
EIP	Electrical impedance plethysmography
FV	Flow volume
ICC	Intraclass coefficient
ICU	Intensive care unit
IMU	Inertial measurement unit
IPCS	Intermittent pneumatic compression system
LAM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Limb Activity Module
LRM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Light Reflection Module
LRR	Light reflection rheography
MEMS	Microelectromechanical systems
NMES	Neuromuscular electrical stimulation
OF	Outflow
PE	Pulmonary embolism
PPG	Photo plethysmography
PPH	Postpartum haemorrhage
PV	Peak velocity
RUC	Reference use case
SGP	Strain-gauge plethysmography
SOTA	State-of-the-art
TAMEAN	Intensity-weighted mean frequency
TCA	Tissue compression actuator

Term	Definition
TENS	Transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation
TSA	Ultrasound transducer steering actuator
US	Ultrasound
USM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Ultrasound Module
VDUS	Venous duplex ultrasound
VFT	Venous function test
VOP	Venous occlusion plethysmography
VTE	Venous thromboembolism
WAM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Actuator Module
XGM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Extended Reality & Serious Games Module
XR	Extended reality

Executive Summary

Deliverable 2.3 outlines the technical and functional requirements for a wearable system to monitor, detect, and prevent deep vein thrombosis (DVT). This was achieved through analysing contractual obligations, patient-centric use cases, regulatory frameworks, clinical guidelines, and clinician consultations, while ensuring methodological and technical feasibility.

The analysis of over 190 literature sources revealed that a universal system integrating multiple measurement methods—compression duplex ultrasound, electrical impedance (EIP), and light reflection rheography (LRR)-based venous occlusion plethysmography—would be beneficial. These methods will share common modules, including a wearable tissue compression actuator (TCA) and a central hub (CHI) with software for medical specialists. An extended reality and serious game module (XGM) is also proposed for DVT prophylaxis.

Key innovations include operator-independent, compression ultrasound scanning for DVT detection, which would replace manual monitoring. This method's feasibility depends on vein visibility during scans, particularly in supine patients, with potential solutions involving automatic calf compression and Doppler ultrasound monitoring. Hydrogel disposable pads are suggested to address issues with drying ultrasound gel. In addition, EIP and LRR venous occlusion plethysmography will enable automated DVT screening while sharing the TCA across modalities. Investigational studies are needed to define optimal patient and sensor positioning. Exploring passive monitoring methods through mechanical or electrical stimulation may enhance venous flow.

DVT prophylaxis is also emphasized, with the potential to improve venous flow through mechanical and/or electrical stimulation. Integrating serious games into the ThrombUS+ platform could enhance both prevention and rehabilitation for immobilized patients.

The identified module-based requirements will inform the further development of the ThrombUS+ system, with detailed specifications to be outlined in Deliverable D6.1, "Product Design Specifications."

1. Introduction

1.1. Methodology

ThrombUS+ functional and technical requirements are directly based on and derived from the following:

- contractual obligations as stated in the Description of Action (DoA),
- patient-centric reference use cases and high-level technical and functional criteria definition as presented in deliverable D2.1,
- regulatory framework, security, safety, and ethics as described in Deliverable D.2.2,
- clinical and health guidelines and recommendations,
- focus groups and brainstorming sessions with clinicians to include the medical perspective,
- technical feasibility based on the state-of-the-art analysis.

The work on the deliverable proceeded according to the plan outlined below. The overall functionality of the system and its main components are identified in the DoA (Section 2.2). Brainstorming sessions with clinicians from the Lithuanian University of Health Sciences were held on February 6, 2024, and also with other partners during the consortium meeting in Kaunas, Lithuania, on May 14-15, 2024. Following this, the ThrombUS+ reference use cases¹ (ThrombUS+ Deliverable D2.1) and regulatory framework² (ThrombUS+ Deliverable D2.2) were analysed, target users were identified, and major user requirements were established.

A state-of-the-art (SOTA) analysis was conducted to determine the key technical characteristics and parameters of various system components, identify existing knowledge gaps, and assess the feasibility of implementing the use cases outlined in D2.1. The SOTA analysis, presented in Annex 3, led to the development of the ThrombUS+ system modules (Section 3.1) and the consolidation of functional (Section 3.2) and technical (Section 3.3) requirements.

User and system requirements for each module were described using the templates recommended by activities in the ongoing Task 9.1 “Regulatory compliance monitoring and mitigation” to ensure regulatory preparedness and conformity (Annex 1, Annex 2). These consolidated requirements will guide the design of the system architecture (D2.4) and the elicitation of product design specifications (D6.1).

To put in context the system under development, generic use cases of medical devices and systems were analysed and classified:

- **Screening** – checking for disease when there are no clinical indications, e.g., mammography, colonoscopy, blood and genetic tests, etc.
- **Continuous screening** – regular monitoring of patients for signs, symptoms, or changes that may indicate the development of a particular condition, e.g., heart arrhythmia screening using a smartwatch³, continuous screening for sleep apnoea using a sleeping mat⁴, etc.

¹ Segal, L., Puppo, F., & Folkvord, F. ThrombUS+ D2.1: Patient-centric cases and requirements definition (Version 1). Zenodo. 2024; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12554621>

² Prinz, T., Narten, Z., Wenner, H., Didaskalou, S., & Schlötelburg, C. ThrombUS+ D2.2: Regulatory framework, security, safety and ethics strategy and guidelines. (Version 1). Zenodo. 2024; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12726793>

³ Track your AFib History with Apple Watch. [Online]. Available: <https://support.apple.com/en-us/HT212214>

⁴ Sleep Analyzer [Online]. Available: <https://www.withings.com/lt/en/sleep-analyzer>

- **Diagnostic (detection) tests** – checking for disease when there are symptoms and the patient is in the need of a differential diagnosis, e.g., diagnosis of cardiac disease by using electrocardiograph⁵, sleep apnoea diagnosis by polysomnography or home test⁶, DVT diagnosis and thrombus identification by using ultrasound⁷, etc.
- **Monitoring** – ongoing observation of individuals who have already been diagnosed with a particular health condition, e.g., regular blood pressure measurements at home for hypertension monitoring, glucose monitoring⁸, etc. Monitoring can be classified into: (1) continuous, and (2) intermittent monitoring, which can be further divided into (a) periodic intermittent and (b) aperiodic intermittent monitoring.
- **Risk assessment** – the systematic assessment and tracking of factors that contribute to the likelihood of developing specific diseases or health conditions, e.g., Framingham Risk Score for Hard Coronary Heart Disease⁹, Caprini model¹⁰ and Wells scores for DVT, etc.
- **Prevention** – the actions and strategies aimed at reducing the incidence, prevalence, and impact of diseases, e.g., implantable cardioverter defibrillator for prevention of sudden cardiac death, intermittent sequential compression cuffs and exercises for prevention of DVT, etc.

To avoid confusion from now on, the project will adopt a single term – **monitoring** – to define the intended purpose and usage of the ThrombUS+ system.

2. Intended purpose, high-level functional and technical requirements

2.1. Intended purpose of the ThrombUS+ system

ThrombUS+ is an active wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, continuous (intermittent) monitoring in patients with increased risk for deep vein thrombosis (DVT), that is applied to the patient's lower limb. For this purpose, ThrombUS+ autonomously combines compression ultrasound imaging (CUS), electrical impedance plethysmography (EIP), and light reflection rheography (LRR) to assess blood clot formation and blood flow on the lower limbs.

Additionally, ThrombUS+ uses inertial measurement units (IMUs) to monitor patient's lower limb activity. Via an extended reality (XR) environment and serious gaming, patients are trained and motivated, respectively, to perform lower limb exercises for DVT prevention at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ is intended for application to adult patients in the clinical environment by healthcare professionals.

⁵ Monedero (2022). A novel ECG diagnostic system for the detection of 13 different diseases. Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2021.104536>

⁶ Automated diagnosis of Obstructive Sleep Apnoea. [Online]. Available from: <https://acurable.com/en/products/acupebble-SA100>

⁷ Kainz et al. Non-invasive diagnosis of deep vein thrombosis from ultrasound imaging with machine learning. npj Digit. Med. 4, 137 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-021-00503-7>

⁸ Continuous glucose monitoring (CGM). [Online]. Available: <https://www.dexcom.com/>

⁹ Framingham Risk Score for Hard Coronary Heart Disease. [Online]. Available from: <https://www.mdcalc.com/calc/38/framingham-risk-score-hard-coronary-heart-disease>

¹⁰ Caprini Score for Venous Thromboembolism (2005). [Online]. Available from: <https://www.mdcalc.com/calc/3970/caprini-score-venous-thromboembolism-2005>

2.2. ThrombUS+ system components

The overall ecosystem of ThrombUS+ is comprised of major components (Figure 1). Each component is analysed in detail against state-of-the-art (Section 0), and then user/functional and technical requirements are formulated (Section 3).

Figure 1. Component diagram of the ThrombUS+ system.

2.3. ThrombUS+ reference use cases (RUCs)

The project deliverable D2.1¹, “Patient-centric Cases and Requirements Definition”, identified 7 use cases for the ThrombUS+ system, referring to them as Reference Use Cases (RUCs). Below is a brief summary of each use case:

RUC #1 – Neurosurgery

- Prophylaxis determination: Continuous monitoring can help doctors decide whether patients need only mechanical prophylaxis or require pharmacological prophylaxis. This monitoring should begin as early as possible and continue for several days to effectively assess and mitigate the risk of DVT (Deep Vein Thrombosis) and pulmonary embolism (PE).
- Post-surgery monitoring: Monitoring is more beneficial post-surgery rather than during surgery. Although useful for scientific purposes, intraoperative monitoring adds limited value as thrombi take days to become dangerous. The device should be used intensively during the critical post-surgery period, particularly in the intensive care unit (ICU), to promptly start prophylaxis when necessary.
- Optimal timing for prophylaxis: This is especially important for neurosurgery patients, where starting prophylaxis at the right time can prevent complications. Unlike other surgeries, neurosurgery cannot begin prophylaxis pre-operation due to high bleeding risks.
- Design considerations: The design should account for the patient’s neurological status, which can often be predicted post-surgery.

- Suggested device: An intermittent compression stocking with integrated ultrasound scanning could provide mechanical prophylaxis while monitoring DVT. This would be especially beneficial for neurosurgery patients, reducing the need for anticoagulants and minimizing bleeding risks.
- Stocking advantages: A stocking design remains stable and provides consistent compression, unlike a bracelet or belt. It is particularly suitable for patients needing various positions or frequent movements.
- Mobility and adaptability: The device should be modular to adapt to different stages of recovery. While compression is crucial when patients are immobilized, their natural muscle movement provides compression as they regain mobility.
- Material considerations: Using appropriate fabrics can prevent skin irritation, making the device comfortable and practical for extended use.

RUC #2 – Lower limb orthopaedic surgery

- Current monitoring challenges: Routine monitoring for DVT is often not conducted due to cost and time constraints, leading to undetected and untreated cases. Experts estimate that around 10% of lower limb surgeries result in DVT.
- Continuous monitoring benefits: A device for continuous DVT monitoring could enhance early detection and treatment, addressing the gap in detecting asymptomatic cases. The device should ideally be used from one-hour post-operation, especially in the critical first three days for elective surgery patients and throughout prolonged immobile periods for trauma patients.
- Anticoagulant management: Continuous monitoring can help tailor anticoagulant doses, improving treatment by detecting early clot formation and allowing for timely dose adjustments.
- Treatment adherence: Continuous monitoring could also help detect non-adherence to anticoagulant regimens during the initial rehabilitation month, enabling doctors to intervene and improve compliance.
- Patient comfort and mobility: The device should be minimally invasive, lightweight, and flexible to avoid discomfort and aid in recovery. It should avoid compressing wounds or restricting air circulation.
- Design considerations: A suggested design is a belt-type wearable for the thighs, adaptable to different parts of the limb depending on wound location. Both legs should be monitored as immobility, a major DVT factor, affects both legs.
- Scanning frequency: Scans should occur at least every 12 hours, though more frequent checks are preferable for timely intervention.

RUC #3 - Cardiovascular surgery and risk

- Enhanced detection: Current ultrasound studies are not fully reliable for detecting DVT, particularly in asymptomatic cases. A device with greater sensitivity and frequency for continuous monitoring could significantly reduce dangerous complications, especially in high-risk patients (e.g., those in ICU, with elevated inflammation, or undergoing long immobilization).
- Automatic operation: An automatic device performing scans every 4 hours could be sufficient for high-risk patients, potentially reducing the need for frequent standard ultrasound scans and saving time for medical staff.
- Diagnostic efficiency: If the device matches or exceeds the sensitivity of standard ultrasounds while requiring less time and fewer human resources, it could streamline the diagnostic process and allow for routine or symptomatic patient scans, improving detection rates.
- Healthcare professional acceptability: The device should be self-sufficient, simple to fit, and not add significant time, risk, or complexity compared to current procedures. It should allow patients to sit or lie down without needing constant attention from medical staff.

- Patient comfort: The device should be comfortable, avoiding excessive pressure, skin irritation, or reactions that could cause discomfort. It should consider patient anxiety by being easy to use and minimally intrusive.
- Design considerations: A stocking-shaped design could be suitable, especially if it includes anti-embolism compression for high-risk patients who cannot be anticoagulated. The design should monitor both legs, as many surgeries are bilateral. However, it must avoid excessive pressure or irritation, especially for cardiovascular surgery patients with leg wounds or swelling and should not be used in cases where continuous compression is contraindicated (e.g., peripheral arterial disease or low arterial flow patients).

RUC #4 – Pregnancy and postpartum

- Continuous monitoring opportunities: For patients with sufficient suspicion or detection of VTE (venous thromboembolism), continuous DVT monitoring is beneficial. This applies to both hospitalized and self-treated patients, as continuous monitoring of blood clot formation is not feasible even in high-risk therapy units. This is especially crucial for conditions like postpartum haemorrhage (PPH), where thromboprophylaxis can't be used, increasing VTE risk.
- Early detection and resource utilization: Continuous scanning and alerting for DVT indicators allow earlier and more effective detection, optimizing clinical resources.
- Post-discharge monitoring: Continuous monitoring can be used preventively at home or during travel for moderate-risk cases, aiding in follow-up and understanding prophylactic self-treatment outcomes. It also helps clinicians understand VTE recurrence better.
- Current practices: Physical and non-pharmacological devices, such as graduated elastic compression stockings, are already welcomed in current practice to prevent VTE events. ThrombUS+ could be highly valued if it increases early detection rates and is accepted for use, potentially preventing maternal deaths and long-term health consequences for women.
- Key functionalities: The device should detect key signs like saturation, pulse rate, and respiratory rate, sending alarms to doctors upon detecting DVT-related anomalies. Constant monitoring and real-time alerts are essential for timely interventions.
- Simplicity and data storage: The device should be simple to use, deployable by nurses and patients, and capable of storing at least 24 hours of data for informed medical decisions upon receiving alarms.
- Design considerations: As 90% of cases occur on the left leg, the device could be designed as a stocking, strap, belt, or band, prioritizing patient comfort. Continuous compression, while not dangerous, can be uncomfortable or painful, affecting adherence, especially outside clinical settings.
- Material and comfort: The device should be light, breathable, and comfortable, considering pregnant women's tendency to overheat and general discomfort due to reduced mobility.
- Interoperability: Ensuring compatibility with other electronic devices, including smartphones, can make the device more user-friendly and acceptable to patients.

RUC #5 – Cancer and oncological treatment

- Early detection: Continuous monitoring can detect asymptomatic DVT, as no specific monitoring is currently performed, especially in low-monitoring settings.
- Outpatient management: It helps assess prophylactic treatment effectiveness after discharge, aiding in deciding when to adjust or stop treatment, improving patients' quality of life.
- Recurrence prevention: Beneficial even for patients who have responded well to treatment and regained mobility to prevent DVT recurrence.
- Leg device preference: Most DVT cases occur in the leg, making a leg device most appropriate, but adaptability to other body parts for monitoring different symptoms is beneficial.

- Sensitivity and comfort: Device sensitivity determines usage duration; it should be comfortable for near 24/7 wear, including during sleep, especially for cancer patients.
- Ease of use: The device must be user-friendly and non-intrusive, requiring minimal attention from patients, essential for long-term use, particularly for those undergoing multiple treatments.

RUC #6 – Obesity

- Customized design considerations: Designing ThrombUS+ devices must consider the patient's health status and weight, ensuring minimal disruption and maximum effectiveness. This co-creation approach with doctors and patients aims to optimize device usability.
- Benefits for obesity patients: Intermittent compression stockings integrated with ultrasound scanning offer mechanical prophylaxis without increasing bleeding risks. This design supports patients following lifestyle treatments to reduce weight and fat percentage, crucial for managing obesity-related risks like DVT.
- Adaptability and mobility: Stocking designs are preferred as they provide stable compression without slipping, crucial during immobilization periods post-surgery. However, they may hinder mobility during recovery stages where natural muscle compression suffices.
- Long-term use and follow-up: Patients with obesity may require prolonged device use, necessitating comfort, and materials that prevent skin irritation. ThrombUS+ usage could reduce the need for frequent Doppler ultrasound studies, cutting costs and streamlining follow-up procedures.
- Comfort and usability: Devices must be comfortable and easy to use, especially for obese patients dealing with fatigue, mobility challenges, and multiple treatments. Comfort ensures patient adherence, even during sleep, if continuous monitoring is required.
- Long-term wear: Since some patients may need to use the device for months or years, it must be non-intrusive and integrate seamlessly into daily life alongside other treatments.
- Body adaptability: While leg devices are typically suitable for DVT monitoring, flexibility to adapt to other body parts with varying coagulability should be considered. This adaptation ensures the device meets specific patient needs, discussed in collaboration with healthcare providers.

RUC #7 – Autoimmune diseases and genetic disorders

- Suitability for autoimmune diseases and genetic disorders: Intermittent compression stockings with integrated ultrasound scanning provide mechanical prophylaxis essential for these patients. They reduce the need for risky anticoagulant treatments and can alert doctors promptly if critical conditions arise.
- Flexibility and sensitivity: Devices must adapt to rapid health changes typical of autoimmune diseases, such as flare-ups in conditions like multiple sclerosis. Sensitivity and flexibility in device usage duration are crucial for patient comfort and adherence.
- Long-term wear and comfort: Considering the chronic nature of autoimmune diseases, devices must be comfortable for long-term use, accommodating patient fatigue and the need for multiple treatments and devices.
- Integration into daily life: Since patients may need to use the device for extended periods, ease of use and comfort are essential to ensure continuous adherence alongside other treatments and devices.

2.4. Target users

Although the ThrombUS+ system intended purpose is to be used by healthcare professionals in the clinical environment to enhance patients' treatment, the functional and technical requirements were designed based on the device's overall lifespan. Therefore, in the context of user and system requirements, the target users are:

- patients,
- medical specialists: doctor, physical therapist, nurse, medical technician,
- administrators: system administrator, maintenance engineers,
- researchers: medical researcher, biomedical engineer.

2.5. Main user requirements

The ThrombUS+ system must provide the following main user functionalities:

- Assist medical specialists with decision support for DVT diagnosis in the following RUCs:
 - neurosurgery,
 - lower limb orthopaedic surgery,
 - cardiovascular surgery and risk.
- Assist medical specialists in continuously monitoring patients for changes in DVT digital biomarkers that indicate an increased risk of DVT in the following RUCs:
 - pregnancy and postpartum,
 - cancer and oncological treatment,
 - obesity,
 - autoimmune diseases and genetic disorders.
- Assist patients with DVT prevention and prophylaxis in the following RUCs:
 - pregnancy and postpartum,
 - cancer and oncological treatment,
 - obesity,
 - autoimmune diseases and genetic disorders.
- Assist administrators in maintaining the system by recording system startup, operation, and error logs.
- Assist medical researchers and biomedical engineers in collecting raw medical data and signals for dataset acquisition.

3. Module-based analysis of requirements

The ThrombUS+ system has a modular structure defined by the complexity of DVT monitoring functions and the multimodality of data sources and technologies. The modular concept of hardware and software enhances the system's flexibility, scalability, and reusability, allowing for easy adaptation to user needs and use cases. At the same time, ThrombUS+ functions as a unified whole, communicating with the modules and integrating and aggregating module data in the Central Hub Intelligence. The technical requirements presented below are organized on a module-based level.

3.1. ThrombUS+ system modules

The conceptual structure of the modules in the ThrombUS+ system, along with their main internal relationships, is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Conceptual modules and their Interrelationships in the ThrombUS+ system.

A project-wide unique identification system will incorporate the project outcomes and all related technical information and documentation, including individual software and hardware components, use cases, user requirements, and functional and technical specifications. At this stage, preliminary identifiers are proposed for the various planned project outcomes at the major module level, as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Indicative unique identifiers of modules (the list will be updated during the project).

ThrombUS+ Modules	Identifier
Central Hub & Intelligence	CHI
Wearable Actuator Module	WAM
Ultrasound Module	USM
Electrical Impedance Module	EIM
Light Rheography Module	LRM
Limb Activity Module	LAM
Extended Reality & Serious Gaming Module	XGM

The ThrombUS+ modules, as integral parts of the system, each serve specific purposes, described below:

- The CHI consists of hardware (a laptop computer) and software (ThrombUS+ applications) used for controlling actuators, gathering data from sensors, processing data, implementing operator-controlled and independent DVT monitoring methods, patient guidance, and supporting decision-making.
- The WAM performs thigh tissue compression to implement: a) the Compression Duplex Ultrasonography (CDUS) method, b) automatic steering of the ultrasound transducer using a feedback mechanism, enabling operator-independent DVT monitoring, and c) the Venous Occlusion Plethysmography (VOP) method, using EIM and LRM modules.
- The USM performs intermittent measurements for operator-independent DVT monitoring, including: a) ultrasound imaging and online segmentation of deep veins in the thigh using the compression method,

b) detection of thrombus by tracking vein localization and dimensions during pressure application with the WAM, c) estimation of vein blood flow perturbations caused by distal DVT using Colour, Power, and Wave Doppler imaging, and d) ensuring a continuous data stream for decision support on DVT risk, thrombus detection, and characterization.

- The EIM is a hardware module used by CHI for the implementation of the VOP method together with WAM.
- The LRM is a hardware module used by CHI for the implementation of the VOP method together with the WAM or the tiptoe DVT test.
- The LAM is a hardware module used by CHI for the implementation of a serious game used in DVT prophylaxis, as well as for providing biofeedback on lower limb maneuvers during ultrasound-based monitoring.
- The XGM is a software module used for DVT risk estimation and prophylaxis.

3.2. User (functional) requirements

User (functional) requirements of the ThrombUS+ system describe the specific behaviours, actions, or functions a system must perform to meet the needs of its users. These requirements focus on what the system should do from the end user’s perspective, defining the capabilities and tasks it must fulfil. They are user-oriented, specifying what users expect the system to do. In addition, they are actionable, as they outline specific tasks the system must perform. The requirements are also measurable, ensuring clarity for testing and validation. Lastly, they are non-technical, emphasizing what the system should achieve without delving into how it should be implemented.

Four types of users were identified of the ThrombUS+ system: 1) Medical specialists (doctor, nurse, medical technician), 2) Patients, 3) Maintenance engineers, 4) Biomedical researchers. The list of main user functionalities of the ThrombUS+ system is provided in Table 2, Table 3, Table 4 and Table 5 below, for each user level.

Table 2. Functional requirements: medical specialist level.

ID	Description	Request (R) Wish (W)
FR_MS_01	The system must support user authentication.	R
FR_MS_02	Allow medical specialists to input and review patient-related data, such as demographics and anamnesis.	R
FR_MS_03	The system must support interactive real-time measurements by using compression ultrasound (B-scan and Doppler), LRR, EIM, and IMU sensors.	R
FR_MS_04	The system must support online monitoring and data analysis of measurement data automatically.	R
FR_MS_05	The system must support automatic alerts based on the DVT detection model.	R
FR_MS_06	The system must support offline measurements and visual analytics of the total recorded data—including risk factors, ultrasound images (B-scan and Doppler) and related parameters, light reflection rheography and electrical impedance signals and parameters, physical activity, and limb orientation data—in an interactive and semi-automatic way.	R
FR_MS_07	The system should have a database with lower limb exercises for DVT prevention and rehabilitation and allow medical specialists to prescribe the rehabilitation scheme.	R

FR_MS_08	The system must enable alternately performed operator-independent scanning of vein in two perpendicular planes.	R
FR_MS_09	The system of continuous ultrasonic monitoring must ensure minimal dimensions and ease of application	R
FR_MS_10	The possibility to use an ultrasound transducer for conventional scanning of peripheral veins must be ensured.	R
FR_MS_11	The resolution of ultrasound images must enable a detection of veins up to the depth of 12 cm.	R
FR_MS_12	The ultrasound monitoring must supply Doppler based data on possible deviations of the vein blood flow due to DVT.	R
FR_MS_13	The system must have a user interface adaptable for the ultrasound monitoring module for imaging, data presentation and control.	R

Table 3. Functional requirements: patient level.

ID	Description	Request (R) Wish (W)
FR_P_01	The system must support user authentication.	R
FR_P_02	Provide daily activity goals to prevent DVT through lower limb exercises.	R
FR_P_03	Display real-time updates on patient-specific DVT risk levels based on wearable sensor data.	R
FR_P_04	Alert patients to perform preventive actions (e.g., exercises) when their DVT risk increases.	R
FR_P_05	Offer a serious game to motivate patients to engage in preventive exercises.	R
FR_P_06	Offer an extended reality environment to guide patients on performing prescribed exercises correctly.	R
FR_P_07	Allow patients to enter their subjective symptoms and track any changes over time.	W

Table 4. Functional requirements: maintenance engineer level.

ID	Description	Request (R) Wish (W)
FR_ME_01	The system must support user authentication.	R
FR_ME_02	Automatically record system start-up, operation, and error logs.	R
FR_ME_03	Notify maintenance engineers of system errors or malfunctions through an alert system.	R
FR_ME_04	Provide real-time system health monitoring dashboards for all system components.	R
FR_ME_05	Log detailed diagnostic data for troubleshooting hardware modules.	W
FR_ME_06	Allow remote access to system logs for offsite diagnostics and troubleshooting.	W

Table 5. Functional requirements: biomedical research level.

ID	Description	Request (R) Wish (W)
FR_MR_01	The system must support user authentication.	R
FR_MR_02	Collect and store raw medical data from the wearable sensors (e.g., ultrasound, plethysmography).	R
FR_MR_03	Allow researchers to export anonymized datasets for scientific analysis.	R
FR_MR_04	Enable customized data collection settings for specific research protocols.	W
FR_MR_05	Offer AI-powered tools to identify patterns and anomalies in large datasets for DVT research.	W
FR_MR_06	Support the integration of external research tools for dataset analysis and processing.	W

Two software applications will be developed, one for medical specialist and one for the patient.

3.3. Technical requirements

Technical requirements are specific criteria that outline the capabilities, functions, characteristics, parameters, and standards the ThrombUS+ system must meet to fulfil its intended purpose.

The tables below present only the main technical requirements related to the system and its modules. Detailed design specifications will follow as a result of the forthcoming Task T6.1.

Table 6 outlines the key requirements for the CHI, designed to implement DVT monitoring and prophylaxis methods. The CHI will support two applications: the Medical Specialist App and the Patient App, both reliant on complex computations. Additionally, the CHI will power ultrasound imaging and actuators, necessitating the use of a modern laptop with advanced specifications as the central hub.

Table 6. Technical requirements: Central Hub & Intelligence module.

ID	Description	Request (R) Wish (W)
TR_CHI_01	Computer: Central hub must CPU – at least i5-13600K; GPU- at least Nvidia RTX 4060; RAM – at least 16GB; ROM – at least SDD 1TB; communication – Wi-Fi and BlueTooth; battery – at least 6 cells. Display– at least 17 in.	R
TR_CHI_02	Medical Specialist App: Central hub must be able to run an app for a medical specialist.	R
TR_CHI_03	Medical Specialist App: The app must support interactive real-time measurements by using compression ultrasound (B-scan and Doppler), LRR, EIM, and IMU sensors.	R
TR_CHI_04	Medical Specialist App: The application must support real-time monitoring and automated data analysis of measurement data, as well as provide automatic alerts based on the machine learning DVT detection model.	R
TR_CHI_05	Medical Specialist App: The application must support offline measurements and visual analytics of recorded data, including risk factors, ultrasound images (B-scan & Doppler) and related parameters, light reflection rheography and electrical impedance data, physical activity, and limb orientation data, in an interactive and semi-automatic manner.	R
TR_CHI_06	Patient App: The central hub must be capable of running the patient application.	R
TR_CHI_07	Patient App: The application must be capable of running a serious game for prophylaxis.	R

TR_CHI_08	Patient App: The application must be capable of presenting risk factors to the patient.	R
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Table 7 lists main requirements for the WAM, whose purpose is to perform thigh tissue compression for the implementation of (a) the compression duplex ultrasonography (CDUS) method, (b) steering the ultrasound transducer automatically using a feedback mechanism, thereby enabling operator-independent DVT monitoring, and (c) the venous occlusion plethysmography (VOP) method using EIM and LRM as sensors.

Table 7. Technical requirements: Wearable actuator module.

ID	Description	Request (R) Wish (W)
TR_WAM_01	Structure: The WAM must include (a) a C-shell type semirigid wearable textile for the integration of a detachable ultrasound transducer and air bladders, and (b) an electronic actuator controller. The shell and textile must be robust and skin-compatible to ensure durability and prevent irritation during prolonged use.	R
TR_WAM_02	Pressure Output Range: The actuator must generate sufficient force to compress the leg for implementation of CDUS and VOP methods without causing harm. Typical range of pressure 20-150 mmHg.	R
TR_WAM_03	Time Intervals: The actuator must be able to apply and release pressure at specific time intervals (ranging from minutes to several hours) for prolonged monitoring periods (lasting several days), depending on the application.	R
TR_WAM_04	Speed and Response Time for the CDUS method: The actuator must adapt to the CDUS requirements for compression and release speed. The inflation speed of the WAM should range from 3 to 6 mmHg per second, with a pump response time of less than 0.5 seconds.	R
TR_WAM_05	Angular Range of Transducer Steering: The actuator must be capable of adjusting the angle of US transducer by a minimum of 5 degrees in both directions, resulting in a total angular range of 10 degrees.	R
TR_WAM_06	Actuator Controller: The actuator controller must have the following sensors and inputs: 1) Two pressure sensors measuring pressure in two different bladders; 2) Feedback signal from Central HUB indicating the level of compression of the vein or other summarizing parameter such as the strain of tissue compression.	R
TR_WAM_07	Noise Level: Operational noise shall not exceed 40 dB to ensure patient comfort during prolonged use.	R
TR_WAM_08	Safety Features: The actuator must include overpressure protection to prevent excessive pressure that could lead to injury and emergency stop to end the operation immediately in case of malfunction. The safety threshold pressure setting is 180 mmHg.	R
TR_WAM_09	Power Supply: The power supply must ensure a stable voltage of 5V and a current of at least 450 mA. It is anticipated that the actuator will be powered via a USB-C cable from the Central Hub.	R
TR_WAM_10	Durability and Lifetime: The actuator is a reusable device and must withstand several thousand cycles of operation. Materials used in the actuator that come into direct or indirect contact with the body must meet biocompatibility standards (e.g., ISO 10993) to avoid adverse reactions. The device should withstand multiple sterilization cycles without compromising functionality or material integrity.	R
TR_WAM_11	Maintenance: The actuator must provide critical information (e.g., error codes about the status of piezo pumps) about its status for logging in to the Central Hub's log files.	R

TR_WAM_12	Usage for Research: The actuator controller must have an option to provide pressure levels from each cuff for recording and exporting raw data and signal files by the Central Hub.	R
TR_WAM_13	Reusability: WAM must be reusable, enabling washing and disinfection of it's parts.	R

Table 8 lists the main requirements for the Ultrasound Module, whose purpose is to implement the compression duplex ultrasonography (CDUS) method for DVT monitoring.

Table 8. Technical requirements: Ultrasound module

ID	Description	Request (R) Wish (W)
TR_USM_01	Transducer: The linear multi-element ultrasonic transducer for automated vein scanning must have at least 128 elements and have a central frequency in the range of 5 to 7 MHz.	R
TR_USM_02	A composite multielement ultrasonic transducer, enabling scanning of veins in two perpendicular planes (e.g. T or Row-Column (RC) type) must ensure scanning depth up to 12 cm.	R
TR_USM_03	The casing of the transducer must be small and suitable for integration into the WAM and removal from it.	R
TR_USM_04	The casing of the transducer should allow an attachment of a handle for manual B-scan operation.	W
TR_USM_05	Beamformer: The beamformer must ensure B-steer scanning with linear transducer having up to 128 elements.	R
TR_USM_06	The beamformer must support linear scanning with RC transducer having 96 elements and phased/sectorial scanning with 32 elements	R
TR_USM_07	The beamformer must provide adjustable focusing during transmission in 8 zones and dynamic focusing during reception.	R
TR_USM_08	The beamformer must support imaging modes including B-steer for linear probes, Color Doppler, Power Doppler, Pulse Wave Doppler, and duplex in two perpendicular scanning planes (with respect of the vein direction)	R
TR_USM_09	The beamformer must be connected to the Central Intelligence Hub via a USB-A or USB-C connector for both power supply and data transmission.	R
TR_USM_10	Data formats: The data format at the output of the beamformer for B-scan, Colour Doppler, and Pulse Wave Doppler modes must be an 8-bit image.	R
TR_USM_11	Beamformed RF data access through an SDK library must be ensured for parametrization of ultrasound signals.	W
TR_USM_12	The data format at the output of the beamformer for RF data must be 16 bits sampled at a rate of no less than 40 MHz.	W
TR_USM_13	Detection and registration: Online detection of a vein and the adjacent artery in the B-scan image, along with the segmentation of the vein's cross-section, must be ensured including provision of real-time data on the vein's position in the scanning plane for the operator-less feedback control of the transducer's position.	R
TR_USM_14	Online tracking of vein dimensions and the level of vein closure during the application of controllable pressure must be conducted using the results of online segmentation.	R

TR_USM_15	Online registration of Colour and Wave/Spectral Doppler data stream must be enabled for automatic calculation of blood flow parameters.	R
TR_USM_16	Ultrasound scanning plane parallel to the vein direction must be maintained by online control of transducer position ensuring operator-less Wave Doppler data registration.	R
TR_USM_17	The USM beamformer must provide a consolidated stream of controllable scanning parameters, images, clips and signals to CHI by USB connection.	R
TR_USM_18	Parameters and characterization: Quantitative parameters must be available from the wave/spectral Doppler signal, such as vein flow pulsatility, respiratory phase parameters, and the reaction of flow changes due to possible distal augmentation.	R
TR_USM_19	A detected thrombus must be characterized using ultrasound parameters such as echogenicity, strain elastography under applied pressure, to evaluate the thrombus's status and age—whether it is new or chronic.	W
TR_USM_20	Thrombus characterization using strain elastography with RF data obtained from beamformer must be ensured.	W
TR_USM_21	Safety and Security: Ultrasonic Monitoring module must be safe, and performance is as intended. This includes ensuring that it does not compromise patient safety or health, and that it has an acceptable risk/benefit profile.	R
TR_USM_22	The Ultrasonic Monitoring Module must comply with the safety requirements and safety indices on potential thermal and mechanical hazards associated with ultrasound usage described in IEC 60601 standard.	R
TR_USM_23	Ultrasound transducers used for continuous monitoring should be suitable for cuffs with different sizes and be detachable from the cuff.	R

Table 9 lists the main requirements for the EIM which will perform impedance plethysmography measurements during venous occlusion intervention and during other, experimental interventions such as deep respiration, and provide the output impedance signal to the Central Hub of the ThrombUS+ system.

Table 9. Technical requirements: Electrical impedance module.

ID	Description	Request (R) Wish (W)
TR_EIM_01	Electrode Configuration: A tetrapolar electrode configuration, where the two outer electrodes are used for current injection, and the two inner electrodes for voltage measurement, must be used. This configuration is preferred over the bipolar configuration as it minimizes confounding factors, particularly the effects of skin-electrode impedance.	R
TR_EIM_02	Electrode Materials: Washable electroconductive textiles must be used for all electrodes.	R
TR_EIM_03	Excitation Frequency: One or more excitation frequencies in the frequency band of 10 – 500 kHz. At least one of the measurement frequencies shall be in the frequency band between 50 kHz.	R
TR_EIM_04	Excitation Current: The injected AC current must be in the range 0.1-3mA.	R
TR_EIM_05	Impedance Measurement Range: The measurement range of at least 0.1 – 400 Ohm, with measurement resolution of at least 0.1 Ohm and noise level of 0.1 Ohm rms maximum.	R
TR_EIM_06	Data Processing: The device must be able to send raw data, along with EIM-extracted parameters, to CHI.	R

TR_EIM_07	Communication: Wi-Fi and Bluetooth (available in HW).	R
TR_EIM_08	Power Supply: A rechargeable battery for at least 2 days of intermittent monitoring.	R
TR_EIM_09	Calibration: Regular automatic internal calibration is recommended.	W
TR_EIM_10	Accuracy: The system should be accurate to within 1-2% to detect small physiological changes reliably.	R
TR_EIM_11	Compliance and Safety: The device should comply with relevant medical standards, IEC 60601, for electrical medical devices and must be designed to prevent interference with other medical equipment and ensure it operates in noisy environments without degradation in performance.	R

Table 10 lists the main requirements for the LRM, which is used to implement DVT monitoring (via the VOP method) and DVT prophylaxis (via prescribed and monitored limb movements).

Table 10. Technical requirements: Light rheography module.

ID	Description	Request (R) Wish (W)
TR_LRM_01	Data Rate: The minimum sampling rate for LRR data is 100Hz.	R
TR_LRM_02	Wavelength: The LRM module must have two light-emitting diodes (LEDs): 660 nm (red light) and 880 nm (infrared light).	R
TR_LRM_03	Wavelength: Two additional wavelengths are recommended for LRR/PPG signal acquisition: green (530 nm) and blue (460 nm). These wavelengths are more suitable for extracting additional physiological parameters such as heart rate, breathing, and pulse wave velocity, which may be useful in AI-based DVT prediction.	
TR_LRM_04	Data Processing: The LRR data processing is performed in the CHI by the LRM SDK.	R
TR_LRM_05	Output: The LRR sensor provides raw and filtered data, along with extracted features, to a machine learning-based DVT monitoring algorithm.	R
TR_LRM_06	Communication: Wi-Fi	R
TR_LRM_07	Power Supply: A rechargeable battery for at least 2 days of intermittent monitoring.	R
TR_LRM_08	Attachment: LRM modules must be attachable to lower extremity segments using comfortable Velcro straps.	R
TR_LRM_09	Compliance and Safety: The device should comply with relevant medical standards, IEC 60601, for electrical medical devices and must be designed to prevent interference with other medical equipment and ensure it operates in noisy environments without degradation in performance.	R

Table 11 lists the main requirements for the LAM, which will use IMUs to monitor patients' lower limb activity and drive the XGM.

Table 11. Technical requirements: Limb activity module.

ID	Description	Request (R) Wish (W)
TR_LAM_01	Data Rate: The minimum sampling rate for leg activity and orientation in space data is 50 Hz.	R

TR_LAM_02	Measurement Range: The accelerometer measurement range is ± 2 to ± 16 g (3 axes); the acceptable gyroscope range is ± 250 to ± 2000 deg/s (3 axes); the acceptable magnetometer range is ± 4900 μ T (axes).	R
TR_LAM_03	The Number of IMU Sensors: The minimum quantity is three—one for each leg segment (foot, calf, and thigh).	R
TR_LAM_04	Additional IMU Sensors: An additional sensor can be placed on the torso to monitor body orientation. More sensors may be used for redundancy, data quality enhancement, or, if required, for AI-based orientation estimation.	W
TR_LAM_05	Data Processing: The IMU data processing must be performed locally in the IMU sensor by the motion processing unit to decrease the load on the microcontroller of the LRRRA.	R
TR_LAM_06	Output: The capability to transmit calculated 3D orientation data for each limb segment (in degrees, radians, or quaternions), as well as raw sensor data (in m/s^2 , deg/s, and μ T).	R
TR_LAM_07	Power Supply: A rechargeable battery for at least 2 days of intermittent monitoring.	R
TR_LAM_08	Attachment: LAM modules must be attachable to lower extremity segments using comfortable Velcro straps.	R

Table 12 lists the main requirements for the Extended Reality and Serious Game, which are intended for implementation in the Patient App.

Table 12. Technical requirements: Extended reality & serious game module.

ID	Description	Request (R) Wish (W)
TR_XGM_01	The XGM has a database containing lower limb exercises and poses which are recommended for: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. DVT prevention/ rehabilitation 2. rehabilitation after orthopedic surgery 3. US, EIP and LRR examination 4. [Optional] rehabilitation of patients defined in the ThrombUS+ Use Cases deliverable (D2.1) 	R
TR_XGM_02	The system has a private database per patient (as a personal health record segment) that stores exercise prescriptions, personalized exercises, recordings of lower-limb activity, patient progress calculated data, and XR/SG state data	R
TR_XGM_03	The system has an interface for recording exercises: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start/ stop recording option, 2. accept/decline recording option, 3. meta data input (name of exercises, description, photo, keywords, can be used in the serious game, etc.) 	R
TR_XGM_04	The system has an interface to be used by physiotherapists to prescribe rehabilitation schemes, such as: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. browse/search, preview and select exercises, 2. set the sequence of exercises 3. for each exercise: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. number of repetitions b. number of sets 	R

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> c. record a demonstration of exercise on patient (set the goal for exercise - personalization of the exercise) d. visualize lower limb in real time during demonstration 4. set the number of scheme repetition per day 5. set the duration for the whole scheme 6. set multiple schemes for the whole rehabilitation program (calendar) 7. to set prohibited exercises 	
TR_XGM_05	The system has an interface to select from the prescribed exercises and the ability to: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. visualize in 3D each exercise 2. visualize in 3D the current lower limb pose (real-time) 3. visualize in 3D an overlap / comparison of real-time activity and the recorded exercise 4. provide guidance on how to perform each exercise 5. notify the patient if prohibited exercise is detected 	R
TR_XGM_06	The XGM is controlled (starts/stops/pause) on demand of the central intelligence application	R
TR_XGM_07	The XGM captures all data that are related to exercises and application metadata when application runs for future activity visualization and reporting	R
TR_XGM_08	The XGM has an interface to: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. display reports including visual elements on patient's progress (including activity during gaming) 2. to export stored/recorded data 	R
TR_XGM_09	The XGM has at least 3 different story lines	R
TR_XGM_10	The game adapts the level of difficulty based on the prescription scheme (e.g. number of repetitions, sets, duration, etc.) and the patient's progress	R
TR_XGM_11	Each story line accepts as input at least 5 exercises (i.e., as HCI commands)	R
TR_XGM_12	Game engagement is supported for each one of the 3 lower limb segments for at least one exercise and at least one story line	R
TR_XGM_13	Game engagement is supported for patients in the lying, sitting and standing position	R

4. Summary and Conclusions

- The goal of Deliverable 2.3 has been to identify the high-level technical and functional requirements for the wearable system to effectively and personally monitor, detect, and prevent DVT. Other objectives included specifying the intended purpose, target users, and ThrombUS+ system modules.
- The objective was achieved by analysing the contractual obligations stated in the DoA, patient-centric reference use cases presented in Deliverable D2.1, the regulatory framework described in Deliverable D2.2, clinical and health guidelines and recommendations, and by organizing meetings and dedicated brainstorming session with clinicians to incorporate the medical perspective, as well as assessing methodological and technical feasibility based on state-of-the-art analysis.
- More than 190 literature sources were analysed to identify knowledge gaps and propose potential solutions with implications for technical and functional requirements. It was concluded that DVT monitoring would benefit from a universal system merging several measurement methods: compression duplex ultrasound, and electrical impedance- (EIP) and light reflection rheography-based (LRR) venous occlusion plethysmography. These methods will share common modules, such as a wearable actuator

(WAM) and a central hub (CHI) with software for use by medical specialists. An extended reality and serious game module (XGM) for DVT prophylaxis is also envisioned and analysed. This module will share the same central hub used for monitoring and will be implemented in the software for the patient.

- A significant innovation, if successful, will be the implementation of operator-independent, compression ultrasound-based scanning for the detection and characterization of DVT. The functional and technical requirements are formulated to mimic the gold standard method for DVT diagnosis described in the DVT Diagnosis Guidelines, replacing a sonographer with automatic intermittent monitoring. However, the feasibility of this method strongly relies on the visibility of the vein in B-scans during compression dynamics when the patient is in a supine position. In this position, peripheral veins may collapse and become invisible in B-scans. To mitigate this issue, venous blood flow augmentation can be achieved through automatic calf compression, with monitoring of peak blood velocity increases using Doppler ultrasound. Another issue with ultrasound-based monitoring is the drying of ultrasound gel. Hydrogel disposable pads may provide a viable solution to this problem.
- Venous occlusion plethysmography using two modalities electrical impedance and light reflection rheography will supplement the ultrasound method with possibility for automated intermittent screening of DVT. Major technical requirements to both EIM and LRM modules formulated. The same wearable tissue compression actuator will be shared with ultrasound modality. Investigational studies and data collection are necessary to define the optimal patient and sensor positioning during various tests for DVT detection. In addition, a passive, operator-independent DVT monitoring method using venous blood flow modulation at the calf through either mechanical or electrical stimulation could be investigated.
- A significant attention to DVT prophylaxis was given. A combination of mechanical and electrical stimulation methods, synchronized with physiological processes like breathing and exergames, may enhance venous flow. Most studies assessed venous flow using Doppler ultrasound parameters such as ejected blood volume and peak velocity. While duplex ultrasonography is the standard, critical venous flow thresholds for reducing thromboembolism risk are unknown. No solutions for operator-independent ultrasonography in prolonged monitoring exist. Few studies have explored serious games for DVT prophylaxis but integrating them into the ThrombUS+ system could enhance its value by supporting thrombosis prevention and rehabilitation through tailored activity plans for immobilized patients.
- The identified module-based functional and technical requirements reflect the capabilities, functions, characteristics, and parameters of each module. A more detailed, module-level specification of the ThrombUS+ system will be developed in Deliverable D6.1, “Product Design Specifications”.

ANNEX 1 | ThrombUS+ User Requirements

Version 1, Date: 30 October 2024

Unique Identifier	User Requirements	User or Stakeholder	Ref.-No.	Change Index	Date	Request (R) Wish (W)	Source	Evaluation Method
Central Hub and Intelligence (CHI)								
UR_PRO1_CHI_01_01	To set up application settings and manage accounts for Medical Specialists and physical therapists (operators)	System Admin	CHI_01	1	2024-10-30	R	Security Management	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PRO1_CHI_02_01	To initialize the device for a patient (including patient identification details and medical history)	Medical Expert	CHI_02	1	2024-10-30	R	Security Management	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PRO1_CHI_03_01	To prescribe ultrasound (including parameters such as cuff pressure level), impedance, light plethysmography examinations and physical therapy	Medical Expert	CHI_03	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with Medical Expert	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PRO1_CHI_04_01	To fill in patient health records related to DVT risk factors	Medical Expert, Patient	CHI_04	1	2024-10-30	R	ThrombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PRO1_CHI_05_01	To visualize personalized DVT risk estimation	Patient	CHI_05	1	2024-10-30	R	ThrombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PRO1_CHI_06_01	To notify patient regarding upcoming examinations (including position recommendations), prevention and rehabilitation goals.	Patient	CHI_06	1	2024-10-30	R	ThrombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PRO1_CHI_07_01	To visualize Ultrasound current examination progress and results (including correct position in XR)	Patient	CHI_07	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with Medical Expert	Usability evaluation / Verification

Unique Identifier	User Requirements	User or Stakeholder	Ref.-No.	Change Index	Date	Request (R) Wish (W)	Source	Evaluation Method
UR_PR01_CHI_08_01	To visualize Electrical Impedance Plethysmography current examination progress and results (including correct position in XR)	Patient	CHI_08	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with Medical Expert	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_CHI_09_01	To visualize Light Reflection Rheography current examination progress and results (including correct position in XR)	Patient	CHI_09	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with Medical Expert	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_CHI_10_01	To allow emergency stop of examinations in case of abnormality	Patient	CHI_10	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with Medical Expert	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_CHI_11_01	To allow access to physical therapy exercises and rehabilitation games (XGM)	Patient	CHI_11	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with Medical Expert	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_CHI_12_01	To display the current status examinations (EIP, LRR, US) based on prescription and physical therapies	Patient	CHI_12	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with Medical Expert	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_CHI_13_01	To display results and reports of examinations	Patient	CHI_13	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with Medical Expert	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_CHI_14_01	To access own medical data and wearable activity data (e.g., from ultrasound, plethysmography, IMU sensors).	Patient	CHI_14	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with Medical Expert	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_CHI_15_01	To monitor patient status, activity, reports and risk estimation	Medical Expert	CHI_15	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with Medical Expert	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_CHI_16_01	To notify medical expert about patient condition and application alarms	Medical Expert	CHI_16	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with Medical Expert	Usability evaluation / Verification

Unique Identifier	User Requirements	User or Stakeholder	Ref.-No.	Change Index	Date	Request (R) Wish (W)	Source	Evaluation Method
UR_PR01_CHI_17_01	To perform manual initialization of examinations (ultrasound, plethysmography etc)	Medical Expert	CHI_17	1	2024-10-30	W	Interview with Medical Expert	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_CHI_18_01	To export examination results, reports and any patient related data	Medical Expert	CHI_18	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with Medical Expert	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_CHI_19_01	To allow Medical Specialists view recorded medical data offline, including detailed analytics of their health metrics.	Medical Expert	CHI_19	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with Medical Expert	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_CHI_20_01	To allow Medical Specialists access to anonymized patient data for scientific research and analysis.	Medical Expert	CHI_20	1	2024-10-30	W	Regulations	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_CHI_21_01	To provide Medical Specialists the ability to customize data collection settings to match specific research protocols.	Medical Expert	CHI_21	1	2024-10-30	W	Interview with Medical Expert	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_CHI_22_01	To enable interoperability of patient data with certified HIS	Health Provider	CHI_22	1	2024-10-30	W	HL7 Standard	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_CHI_23_01	ThrombUS+ modules communicate with CHI either with a wire or wireless via provided appropriate programming interfaces	System Admin	CHI_23	1	2024-10-30	W	ThrombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
Wearable Actuator Module (WAM)								
UR_PR01_WAM_01_01	To perform compression of the ultrasound transducer to achieve vein compression	Medical Specialists	WAM_01	1	2024-10-30	R	ThrombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_WAM_02_01	To adjust the angle of the ultrasound transducer	Medical Specialists	WAM_02	1	2024-10-30	R	ThrombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification

Unique Identifier	User Requirements	User or Stakeholder	Ref.-No.	Change Index	Date	Request (R) Wish (W)	Source	Evaluation Method
UR_PR01_WAM_03_01	To measure the current pressure for all bladders	Medical Specialists	WAM_03	1	2024-10-30	R	ThrombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_WAM_04_01	To ensure patients comfort with respect to noise	Patient	WAM_04	1	2024-10-30	R	State of the art analysis	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_WAM_05_01	To ensure protection against over-pressure that could lead to injury	Patient	WAM_05	1	2024-10-30	R	State of the art analysis	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_WAM_06_01	To sufficiently powered	Medical Specialists	WAM_06	1	2024-10-30	R	ThrombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_WAM_07_01	To operate robustly over prolonged time periods	Patient	WAM_07	1	2024-10-30	R	ThrombUS+ DoA IEC 60601 standard	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_WAM_08_01	To be re-used by other patients	Patient	WAM_08	1	2024-10-30	R	ThrombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_WAM_09_01	To be washable	Patient	WAM_09	1	2024-10-30	R	ThrombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_WAM_10_01	To be adjustable with respect to thigh circumference	Patient	WAM_10	1	2024-10-30	R	ThrombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_WAM_11_01	To be biocompatible ensuring no adverse reaction during prolonged wear	Patient	WAM_11	1	2024-10-30	R	ISO 10993 IEC 60601	Usability evaluation / Verification

Unique Identifier	User Requirements	User or Stakeholder	Ref.-No.	Change Index	Date	Request (R) Wish (W)	Source	Evaluation Method
UR_PR01_WAM_12_01	To log critical information	System Admin	WAM_12	1	2024-10-30	R	ThrombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_WAM_13_01	To record and export raw data	Researchers	WAM_13	1	2024-10-30	R	ThrombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
Ultrasound Module (USM)								
UR_PR01_USM_01_01	To image with sufficient quality veins and arteries in within the lower limb to perform DVT diagnosis	Medical Specialists	USM_01	1	2024-10-30	R	ThombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_USM_02_01	To have different imaging modes in two perpendicular planes and depth of 8cm to support DVT diagnosis	Medical Specialists	USM_02	1	2024-10-30	R	State of the art analysis	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_USM_03_01	The bulk and CMUT type ultrasound probes should be suitable both for manual and operator-less scanning	Medical Specialists/ Researchers	USM_03	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with medical doctors	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_USM_04_01	To identify and segment in real-time veins and arteries within the imaging plane	Medical Specialists	USM_04	1	2024-10-30	R	ThombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_USM_05_01	The ultrasound probe should be able to be integrated in to the WAM	Medical Specialists	USM_05	1	2024-10-30	R	ThombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_USM_06_01	To support quantitative estimation of venous flow and thrombi	Medical Specialists	USM_06	1	2024-10-30	W	State of the art analysis	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_USM_07_01	To be biocompatible ensuring no adverse reaction during prolonged wear	Patients	USM_07	1	2024-10-30	R	ISO 10993 IEC 60601	Usability evaluation / Verification

Unique Identifier	User Requirements	User or Stakeholder	Ref.-No.	Change Index	Date	Request (R) Wish (W)	Source	Evaluation Method
Electrical Impedance Module (EIM)								
UR_PR01_EIM_01_01	To provide sufficient bioimpedance signal quality and resolution to discriminate physiological from pathological condition	Medical Specialists	EIM_01	1	2024-10-30	R	ThombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_EIM_02_01	To support automatic calibration of EIM module	Medical Specialists	EIM_02	1	2024-10-30	W	State of the art analysis	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_EIM_03_01	To be biocompatible ensuring no adverse reaction during prolonged wear	Patients	EIM_03	1	2024-10-30	R	ISO 10993 IEC 60601	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_EIM_04_01	Electrodes should have reliable contact with the skin and be reusable.	Patients	EIM_04	1	2024-10-30	R	State of the art analysis	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_EIM_05_01	To permit easy wearing procedure	Patients / Medical Specialists / Physical Therapist	EIM_05	1	2024-10-30	W	ThombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
Light Rheography Module (LRM)								
UR_PR01_LRM_01_01	To provide sufficient light rheography signal quality and resolution to discriminate physiological from pathological condition	Medical Specialists	LRM_01	1	2024-10-30	W	ThombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_LRM_02_01	Sensors should be reusable	Patients	LRM_02	1	2024-10-30	W	ThombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_LRM_03_01	To be biocompatible ensuring no adverse reaction during prolonged wear	Patients	LRM_03	1	2024-10-30	W	ISO 10993 IEC 60601	Usability evaluation / Verification

Unique Identifier	User Requirements	User or Stakeholder	Ref.-No.	Change Index	Date	Request (R) Wish (W)	Source	Evaluation Method
UR_PR01_LRM_04_01	To permit easy wearing procedure	Patients / Medical Specialists / Physical Therapist	LRM_04	1	2024-10-30	W	ThombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
Limb Activity Module (LAM)								
UR_PR01_LAM_01_01	To provide sufficient online position and orientation signal quality with high resolution for monitoring the activity of each lower limb segment	Medical Specialists/ Patients	LAM_01	1	2024-10-30	R	ThombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_LAM_02_01	Sensors should be reusable	Patients	LAM_02	1	2024-10-30	R	ThombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_LAM_03_01	To be biocompatible and ensuring no adverse reaction during prolonged wear	Patients	LAM_03	1	2024-10-30	R	ISO 10993 IEC 60601	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_LAM_04_01	To permit easy wearing procedure	Patient / Medical Expert / Physical Therapist	LAM_04	1	2024-10-30	W	ThombUS+ DoA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_LAM_05_01	To support automatic calibration of LAM module	Medical Specialists	LAM_05	1	2024-10-30	W	State of the art analysis	Usability evaluation / Verification
Extended Reality & Serious Gaming Module (XGM)								
UR_PR01_XGM_01_01	To contain a collection of predefined exercises dedicated to DVT prevention.	Physical therapist	XGM_01	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification

Unique Identifier	User Requirements	User or Stakeholder	Ref.-No.	Change Index	Date	Request (R) Wish (W)	Source	Evaluation Method
UR_PR01_XGM_02_01	To contain a collection of predefined exercises dedicated to rehabilitation after orthopedic surgery.	Physical therapist	XGM_02	1	2024-10-30	W	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_03_01	To contain the correct pose for the ultrasound imaging	ThrombUS+ device	XGM_03	1	2024-10-30	W	Diagnostic guidelines	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_04_01	To contain the correct pose for the Electrical Impedance Plethysmography	ThrombUS+ device	XGM_04	1	2024-10-30	R	Diagnostic guidelines	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_05_01	To contain the feet exercise (tip-toe-test) for the Light Reflection Rheography	ThrombUS+ device	XGM_05	1	2024-10-30	R	Diagnostic guidelines	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_06_01	To update the database with new predefined exercises	Researcher/ System Admin / Physical therapist	XGM_06	1	2024-10-30	R	ThrombUS+ use cases	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_07_01	To set which exercises prescribed to be performed by the patient	Physical therapist	XGM_07	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_08_01	To personalize the predefined exercises on patient's needs, abilities and condition via live demonstration on the patient	Physical therapist	XGM_08	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_09_01	To set which movements are NOT allowed to be performed by the patient	Physical therapist	XGM_09	1	2024-10-30	W	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_10_01	To set the prescription: number of exercises, repetitions and number of repeats per day.	Physical therapist	XGM_10	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification

Unique Identifier	User Requirements	User or Stakeholder	Ref.-No.	Change Index	Date	Request (R) Wish (W)	Source	Evaluation Method
UR_PR01_XGM_11_01	To demonstrate exercises / movements / poses as performed by a 3D avatar (visual articulations)	Physical therapist / Patient	XGM_11	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_12_01	To visualize patient lower limb movement in real-time as performed by a 3D avatar (visual articulations)	Physical therapist / Patient	XGM_12	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_13_01	To provide a visual comparison of real-time activity and the predefined/ recorded exercises	Physical therapist / Patient	XGM_13	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_14_01	To provide visual guidance on how to perform the allowed exercises	Patient	XGM_14	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_15_01	To provide audio guidance on how to perform the allowed exercises	Patient	XGM_15	1	2024-10-30	W	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_16_01	To record lower-limb activity	Physical therapist	XGM_16	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_17_01	To visualize the recorded lower-limb activity	Physical therapist	XGM_17	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_18_01	To notify patient when not allowed movements are detected	Patient	XGM_18	1	2024-10-30	W	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_19_01	To prompt patients to perform the exercises/ movements	Patient	XGM_19	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification

Unique Identifier	User Requirements	User or Stakeholder	Ref.-No.	Change Index	Date	Request (R) Wish (W)	Source	Evaluation Method
UR_PR01_XGM_20_01	To generate detailed reports including visual elements on patient's performance	Physical therapist / Patient	XGM_20	1	2024-10-30	W	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_21_01	To export recorded data	Researcher / System Admin	XGM_21	1	2024-10-30	R	ThrombUS+ DOA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_22_01	Game should align with exercises prescribed by the physical therapist	Patient	XGM_22	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_23_01	To have multiple game story lines	Patient	XGM_23	1	2024-10-30	R	ThrombUS+ DOA	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_24_01	Game should incentivize patients to complete exercises correctly	Patient	XGM_24	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_25_01	Game should adapt based on patients improvement	Patient	XGM_25	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification
UR_PR01_XGM_26_01	Game should adapt based on physiotherapists prescription	Patient	XGM_26	1	2024-10-30	R	Interview with physical therapist	Usability evaluation / Verification

ANNEX 2 | ThrombUS+ System Requirements

Version 2, Date: 12 November 2025

Unique Identifier	System Requirement	Ref No.	Change Index	Date	Ref. to User Requirement	Acceptance Criteria (including Test Procedure, as applicable)
Central Hub and Intelligence (CHI)						
SR_PRO1_CHI_01_01	The CHI provides an interface for administrators to set up application settings, manage accounts for medical specialists and define operator roles.	CHI_01	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_01_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_CHI_02_01	The CHI has a local database that stores patient medical data (as a personal health record segment), wearable activity data and system settings	CHI_02	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_01_01 UR_PRO1_CHI_14_01 UR_PRO1_CHI_19_01	Passed software test: database functionality (data integrity, completeness, etc.)
SR_PRO1_CHI_03_01	The CHI provides an interface to initialize the device for a new patient, including patient identification details and medical history.	CHI_03	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_02_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_CHI_04_01	The CHI has an interface for medical experts to prescribe ultrasound, impedance plethysmography, light reflection rheography examinations, and physical therapy, including relevant examination parameters (e.g., cuff pressure level, schedule).	CHI_04	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_03_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_CHI_05_01	The CHI has a default mechanism for automatic initialization for each prescribed examination (e.g., ultrasound, plethysmography) within the thrombus project scope	CHI_05	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_03_01	Passed software test: application functionality
SR_PRO1_CHI_06_01	The CHI utilizes a background service which orchestrates the whole prescribed examination	CHI_06	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_01_01 UR_PRO1_CHI_03_01	Passed software test: application functionality

Unique Identifier	System Requirement	Ref No.	Change Index	Date	Ref. to User Requirement	Acceptance Criteria (including Test Procedure, as applicable)
	and rehabilitation process (XGM), records and stores the raw data via provided SDKs from each wearable component (USM, LRM, EIM, WAM, LAM).					
SR_PRO1_CHI_07_01	The CHI has an interface to enter patient health records related to DVT risk factors	CHI_07	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_04_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_CHI_08_01	The CHI provides patients with a visualization of their personalized DVT risk estimation based on current patient condition.	CHI_08	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_05_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_CHI_09_01	The CHI has notification alerts for patients' upcoming examinations (including position recommendations when necessary) and physical activity goals (prevention and rehabilitation exercises)	CHI_09	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_06_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_CHI_10_01	The CHI has an interface to visualize the current examination progress and results of ultrasound, EIP, and LRR examinations for the patient, including correct positioning in the XR environment.	CHI_10	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_07_01 UR_PRO1_CHI_08_01 UR_PRO1_CHI_09_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_CHI_11_01	The CHI provides an emergency stop function to immediately halt any ongoing examination in case of detected abnormalities or patient distress.	CHI_11	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_10_01 UR_PRO1_WAM_05_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_CHI_12_01	The CHI provides the ability to start/pause/stop the rehabilitation/prevention app (XGM)	CHI_12	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_11_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users

Unique Identifier	System Requirement	Ref No.	Change Index	Date	Ref. to User Requirement	Acceptance Criteria (including Test Procedure, as applicable)
SR_PRO1_CHI_13_01	The CHI allows patients to view the current status of their prescribed examinations (e.g., EIP, LRR, ultrasound) and track physical therapy activities.	CHI_13	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_12_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_CHI_14_01	The CHI has an interface to visualize historical data of examinations and other data (including reports) to provide medical experts with immediate insights.	CHI_14	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_13_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_CHI_15_01	The CHI provides a monitoring dashboard for medical experts to view patient status, activity logs, examination results, reports, and risk estimations.	CHI_15	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_15_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_CHI_16_01	The CHI creates application alarms and alerts related to patient conditions, providing notifications to medical experts in case of abnormality.	CHI_16	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_16_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_CHI_17_01	The CHI has a method for manual initialization for each examination (e.g., ultrasound, plethysmography) within the thrombus project scope	CHI_17	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_17_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_CHI_18_01	The CHI has an interface which supports manual ultrasound examination (B-Scan)	CHI_18	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_03_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_CHI_19_01	The CHI has an interface to export examination results, reports, and patient-related data in a standardized format.	CHI_19	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_18_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users

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SR_PRO1_CHI_20_01	The CHI allows researchers to export anonymized datasets for scientific research and analysis purposes.	CHI_20	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_20_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_CHI_21_01	The CHI enables customized data collection settings to align with specific research protocols defined by medical researchers.	CHI_21	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_21_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_CHI_22_01	The CHI enables the interoperability of patient data with certified Health Information Systems (HIS) to facilitate seamless information sharing with healthcare providers.	CHI_22	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_22_01	Passed software test: application functionality
Wearable Actuator Module (WAM)						
SR_PRO1_WAM_01_01	The WAM has: 1) a C-shell type semirigid wearable textile for the integration of a detachable ultrasound transducer and air bladders, 2) an electronic actuator controller	WAM_01	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_WAM_01_01	Passed functionality test: the WAM integrates a wearable textile, a detachable US transducer, and an electronic controller.
SR_PRO1_WAM_02_01	The WAM generates sufficient force to compress the leg for the implementation of CDUS and VOP methods without causing harm. Typical range of pressure 20-150 mmHg.	WAM_02	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_WAM_01_01	Passed performance test: verification of pressure range is acceptable within $\pm 5\%$.
SR_PRO1_WAM_03_01	The WAM applies and releases pressure at specific time intervals (ranging from 15 minutes to 4 hours in steps of 15 minutes) for prolonged monitoring periods (lasting several days).	WAM_03	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_WAM_01_01	Passed functionality test: the WAM is able to apply and release pressure at set time intervals.
SR_PRO1_WAM_04_01	The WAM adapts to CDUS requirements for compression speed. The inflation speed of the	WAM_04	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_WAM_01_01	Passed performance test: verification of inflation speed and a

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	WAM ranges from 3 to 6 mmHg per second, with a pump response time of less than 0.5 seconds.					pump response time is acceptable within $\pm 5\%$.
SR_PRO1_WAM_05_01	The WAM is capable of adjusting the angle of US transducer by a minimum of 5 degrees in both directions, resulting in a total angular range of 10 degrees.	WAM_05	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_WAM_02_01	Passed performance test: verification of the total angular range of US transducer adjustment is acceptable within $\pm 5\%$.
SR_PRO1_WAM_06_01	The WAM controller has the following sensors and inputs: 1) two pressure sensors measuring pressure in two different bladders, 2) feedback signal from a central hub indicating the level of compression of the vein or other summarizing parameter such as the strain of tissue compression.	WAM_06	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_WAM_01_01 UR_PRO1_WAM_03_01	Passed functionality test: the WAM controller accepts two types of input data: pressure in the bladders and a feedback signal from the CHI about the level of tissue/vein compression.
SR_PRO1_WAM_07_01	Operational noise of the WAM does not exceed 40 dB to ensure patient comfort during prolonged use.	WAM_07	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_WAM_04_01	Passed performance test: the noise created by the working WAM is less than 40 dB.
SR_PRO1_WAM_08_01	The WAM includes: 1) overpressure protection to prevent excessive pressure that could lead to injury, 2) emergency stop to end the operation immediately in case of malfunction. The safety threshold pressure setting is 180 mmHg.	WAM_08	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_WAM_05_01	Passed functionality test: the WAM controller stops compressing at the set overpressure threshold and also stops operation in case of any malfunction.
SR_PRO1_WAM_09_01	The WAM is powered via a USB-C cable from the central hub & intelligence module ensuring: 1) stable voltage of 5V 2) current of at least 450mA	WAM_09	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_WAM_06_01	Passed functionality test: the WAM controller accepts power via a USB-C cable from the CHI.

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SR_PRO1_WAM_10_01	The WAM withstands at least 2 thousands cycles of operation.	WAM_10	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_WAM_07_01	Passed performance test: the WAM is able to withstand at least 2,000 compression release cycles.
SR_PRO1_WAM_11_01	The WAM withstands at least 20 washing cycles without compromising functionality or material integrity.	WAM_11	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_WAM_08_01	Passed performance test: the WAM is able to withstand at least 20 washing cycles.
SR_PRO1_WAM_12_01	The WAM controller is detachable allowing the textile to be washed and be reused.	WAM_12	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_WAM_08_01 UR_PRO1_WAM_09_01 UR_PRO1_WAM_10_01	Passed usability test: the WAM controller can be detached for washing the textile.
SR_PRO1_WAM_13_01	The materials of the WAM which come into direct contact with the body meets biocompatibility standards to avoid adverse reactions.	WAM_13	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_WAM_11_01	Passed safety test: the WAM controller and US transducer fit into the biocompatible wearable textile.
SR_PRO1_WAM_14_01	The WAM controller complies with the safety indices on potential thermal and mechanical hazards as described in IEC 60601-1 standard.	WAM_14	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_WAM_11_01	Passed performance and safety tests: all standard requirements are fulfilled.
SR_PRO1_WAM_15_01	The WAM controller provides critical information about its status for logging in to the CHI log files (e.g., error codes about the status of piezo pumps).	WAM_15	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_WAM_12_01 UR_PRO1_WAM_13_01	Passed functionality test: the WAM controller provides critical information about its status in the log files kept in the CHI.
SR_PRO1_WAM_16_01	The WAM system provides an SDK for data processing and programming interfaces.	WAM_16	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_23_01	Passed functionality and compatibility tests: the SDK fulfills the requirements for command execution, data communication, processing, and programming functionality.

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Ultrasound Module (USM)						
SR_PRO1_USM_01_01	The USM has a linear multi-element ultrasonic transducer for automated vein scanning which has: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 128 elements of conventional technology, and 96 CMUT technology (extendable on demand); 2) central frequency in the range of 4 to 7 MHz. 	USM_01	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_01_01 UR_PRO1_USM_03_01 UR_PRO1_USM_04_01	1) Validation of elements number according to specification and ensured by the design; 2) Passed acoustic control with pulse-echo method. Central frequency averaged on all the elements of the array.
SR_PRO1_USM_02_01	The USM has a composite multielement ultrasonic transducers bulk and CMUT based: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) enabling scanning of veins in two perpendicular planes (e.g. T or Row-Column (RC) type) 2) ensuring scanning depth not less than 8 cm. 	USM_02	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_01_01 UR_PRO1_USM_03_01 UR_PRO1_USM_04_01	Testing of imaging capabilities by using certified ultrasound phantoms and in pilot in-vivo experiments.
SR_PRO1_USM_03_01	The casing of the transducer is suitable for integration into a smart wearable actuator (WAM) and removal from it.	USM_03	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_03_01 UR_PRO1_USM_05_01 UR_PRO1_USM_07_01	Passed usability test including drawings review of USM casing and WAM
SR_PRO1_USM_04_01	The casing of the transducer allows an attachment of a handle for manual B-scan operation.	USM_04	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_03_01 UR_PRO1_USM_03_01 UR_PRO1_USM_05_01	Passed usability test.
SR_PRO1_USM_05_01	The USM beamformer must ensure B-steer scanning with linear probes having up to 96 elements	USM_05	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_01_01 UR_PRO1_USM_02_01 UR_PRO1_USM_04_01	Passed usability test against specification, verifying acquired ultrasound data and capability to steer and number of scanning beams.
SR_PRO1_USM_06_01	The USM has a beamformer which supports: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) linear scanning with 96 elements, 2) phased/sectorial scanning with 32 elements for the RCA transducer. 	USM_06	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_01_01 UR_PRO1_USM_02_01 UR_PRO1_USM_04_01	Passed test of imaging capabilities by using certified ultrasound phantoms and pilot in-vivo experiments.

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SR_PRO1_USM_07_01	The USM has a beamformer which provides: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) adjustable focusing during transmission in 8 zones, 2) dynamic focusing during reception. 	USM_07	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_01_01 UR_PRO1_USM_04_01	Ability to focus verified by using phantoms and dedicated software.
SR_PRO1_USM_08_01	The USM has a beamformer which supports imaging modes including: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) B-steer for linear probes, 2) Color Doppler, 3) Power Doppler, 4) Pulse Wave Doppler, 5) Duplex in two perpendicular scanning planes (with respect of the vein direction). 	USM_08	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_01_01 UR_PRO1_USM_02_01 UR_PRO1_USM_04_01	Passed imaging capabilities test using certified ultrasound phantoms and pilot in-vivo experiments.
SR_PRO1_USM_09_01	The USM has a beamformer which is connected to the central intelligence hub via a USB-A or USB-C connector for both: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) power supply, 2) data transmission. 	USM_09	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_01_01 UR_PRO1_CHI_23_01	Passed usability test - if implemented by the design.
SR_PRO1_USM_10_01	The USM has a beamformer which outputs an 8-bit image for the: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) B-scan mode, 2) Color Doppler mode, 3) Pulse Wave Doppler mode. 	USM_10	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_02_01	Veified data recorded during in the initial pre-clinical tests.
SR_PRO1_USM_11_01	The beamformed RF signal and data access through an SDK library must be ensured for parametrization of ultrasound signals	USM_11	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_01_01 UR_PRO1_USM_02_01	Passed test of RF signal and imaging data availability for analysis and recording.
SR_PRO1_USM_12_01	The USM has beamformer which outputs RF data of: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 16-bits, 	USM_12	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_01_01 UR_PRO1_USM_02_01	Passed verification of sampling parameters of RF data obtained

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	2) sampled at a rate of no less than 40 MHz.					from known depth scan using calibrated phantoms.
SR_PRO1_USM_13_01	The USM provides real-time: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) detection of a vein and the adjacent artery, 2) segmentation of detected vein's cross-section, 3) vein's position in the scanning plane for the operator-less feedback control of the transducer's position during B-scan mode. 	USM_13	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_02_01 UR_PRO1_USM_04_01 UR_PRO1_USM_05_01	Passed software test: application functionality. Passed usability test: segmentation of detected vein
SR_PRO1_USM_14_01	The USM provides and stores real-time measurements for the segmented vein's: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) dimensions 2) level of compression (closure). 	USM_14	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_02_01 UR_PRO1_USM_04_01 UR_PRO1_USM_05_01	Passed verification of vein closure during compression by pilot in-vivo trial
SR_PRO1_USM_15_01	The USM provides online registration of color and wave/spectral Doppler data stream enabling evaluation of blood flow parameters.	USM_15	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_01_01 UR_PRO1_USM_02_01 UR_PRO1_USM_06_01	Passed functionality test: availability of Doppler data Passed software test: performance of algorithm for blood flow evaluation
SR_PRO1_USM_16_01	The USM has the ability for online control of the transducer's orientation during ultrasound scanning to maintain the imaging plane parallel to the vein's direction, ensuring operator-independent wave-Doppler data registration.	USM_16	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_01_01 UR_PRO1_USM_02_01 UR_PRO1_USM_04_01	Passed usability test verifying the control of the scanning plane position enabling the imaging of vein
SR_PRO1_USM_17_01	The USM beamformer must provide a consolidated stream of controllable scanning parameters, images, clips and signals to CHI by USB connection.	USM_17	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_01_01 UR_PRO1_USM_02_01 UR_PRO1_CHI_07_01	Passed usability test:
SR_PRO1_USM_18_01	[Optional] USM will provide quantitative data from wave/spectral Doppler signal, such as:	USM_18	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_06_01	(Optional, dependent on necessary research results) Passed

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	1) vein flow pulsatility, 2) respiratory phasicity, 3) vein flow changes (e.g. due to compression on distal limb).					functionality test of principal ability to obtain vein flow data with sufficient signal to noise ratio and subsequent evaluation of quantitative flow data.
SR_PRO1_USM_19_01	[Optional] The USM characterizes a detected thrombus (new or chronic) by its: 1) echogenicity, 2) strain elastography under applied pressure, 3) strain elastography with RF data.	USM_19	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_06_01	(Optional, dependent on necessary research results) Passed usability test on phantoms and pilot in-vivo trials
SR_PRO1_USM_20_01	The USM complies with IEC 60601 standard "Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of ultrasonic medical diagnostic and monitoring equipment" including the safety indices on potential thermal and mechanical hazards associated with the wearable ultrasound usage.	USM_20	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_USM_07_01	Passed compliance test for safety and essential performance
SR_PRO1_USM_21_01	The USM provides an SDK for raw ultrasound RF signal and data processing and programming interfaces.	USM_21	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_23_01	Passed functionality and compatibility tests: The SDK fulfills the requirements for command execution, data communication, processing, and programming functionality.
Electrical Impedance Module (EIM)						
SR_PRO1_EIM_1_01	The EIM contains of a tetrapolar electrode where: 1) the two outer electrodes are used for current injection, and 2) the two inner electrodes for voltage measurement.	EIM_1	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_EIM_01_01	Passed functionality test: the tetrapolar electrode system is available for accurate bioimpedance measurements

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SR_PRO1_EIM_2_01	The EIM uses excitation frequencies in the frequency band of 10-500kHz with at least 5kHz discrete resolution.	EIM_2	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_EIM_01_01	Passed performance test: Excitation validation with oscilloscope, $\pm 3\%$ acceptable.
SR_PRO1_EIM_3_01	The EIM injects AC current in the range of 0.1-3.0mA	EIM_3	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_EIM_01_01	Passed performance and safety tests: verification with reference resistors, $\pm 5\%$ acceptable.
SR_PRO1_EIM_4_01	The EIM supports measurements in the range of 0.1-400 Ohm.	EIM_4	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_EIM_01_01	Passed performance test: verification with test circuit, $\pm 5\%$ acceptable.
SR_PRO1_EIM_5_01	The EIM supports measurements with a resolution of at least 0.1 Ohm and a noise level of 0.1 Ohm RMS (root mean squared) maximum.	EIM_5	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_EIM_01_01	Passed performance test: noise level verification via test circuit.
SR_PRO1_EIM_6_01	The EIM measurements are accurate to within 1-2% to detect small physiological changes reliably.	EIM_6	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_EIM_01_01	Passed performance test: verified with tissue modeling electronic circuit.
SR_PRO1_EIM_7_01	The EIM can transmit raw data and EIP-extracted parameters to the CHI module via the defined communication protocol specified in D6.1 "Specifications", over WiFi. Bluetooth is available in the hardware.	EIM_7	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_EIM_01_01 UR_PRO1_CHI_23_01	Passed functionality and compatibility tests: The EIM can communicate with the CHI and transmit data via WiFi.
SR_PRO1_EIM_8_01	The EIM uses a rechargeable battery for at least 2 days of intermittent monitoring with 5 VOP measurements done each day.	EIM_8	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_23_01 UR_PRO1_EIM_02_01	Passed performance test: verification via current consumption measurement and simulated use. Accepted value at minimum 5 VOP measurement in 2 days.
SR_PRO1_EIM_9_01	[Optional] The EIM supports automatic internal calibration.	EIM_9	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_EIM_02_01	Passed functionality test: self-calibration is performed

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						before each intermittent measurement.
SR_PRO1_EIM_10_01	The EIM complies with the IEC 60601-1 electrical medical standards.	EIM_10	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_EIM_03_01	Passed performance and safety tests: all standard requirements are fulfilled.
SR_PRO1_EIM_11_01	The EIM does not interfere with other medical equipment and ensures its reliable operation in noisy environments without degradation in performance.	EIM_11	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_EIM_03_01	Passed performance test: all standard requirements are fulfilled.
SR_PRO1_EIM_12_01	Electrodes of the EIM are made of washable electroconductive textiles.	EIM_12	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_EIM_04_01	Passed performance test: washing electroconductive textiles does not change EIM performance characteristics.
SR_PRO1_EIM_13_01	Electrodes of the EIM have adjustable circumference.	EIM_13	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_EIM_04_01	Passed usability test: evaluation by users.
SR_PRO1_EIM_14_01	The EIM provides an SDK for data processing and programming interfaces, specified in D6.1 'Specifications'.	EIM_14	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_23_01	Passed functionality and compatibility tests: The SDK fulfills the requirements for command execution, data communication, processing, and programming functionality.
SR_PRO1_EIM_15_01	The EIM is integrated into a biocompatible wearable with the LRM and the LAM	EIM_15	1	2024-10-31	UR_PRO1_EIM_03_01 UR_PRO1_EIM_04_01 UR_PRO1_EIM_05_01	Passed safety tests: the EIM fits into the biocompatible wearable.

Light Rheography Module (LRM)

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SR_PRO1_LRM_01_01	The LRM has sampling rate not less than 100Hz.	LRM_01	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_LRM_01_01	Passed performance test: the sampling rate is equal to 100Hz.
SR_PRO1_LRM_02_01	The LRM has a two-wavelength (red and infrared) light reflection rheography sensor.	LRM_02	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_LRM_01_01	Passed performance test: the LRM sensor has two-wavelength (red and infrared) LEDs.
SR_PRO1_LRM_03_01	The LRM can transmit raw data and extracted parameters to the CHI module via the defined communication protocol specified in D6.1 "Specifications" over WiFi. Bluetooth is available in the hardware.	LRM_03	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_LRM_01_01 UR_PRO1_CHI_23_01	Passed functionality and compatibility tests: The LRM can communicate with the CHI and transmit data via WiFi.
SR_PRO1_LRM_04_01	The LRM is integrated into a biocompatible and washable wearable with the EIP and the LAM.	LRM_04	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_LRM_02_01 UR_PRO1_LRM_03_01 UR_PRO1_LRM_04_01	Passed safety tests: the LRM fits into the biocompatible wearable.
SR_PRO1_LRM_05_01	The LRM uses a rechargeable battery for at least 2 days of intermittent monitoring.	LRM_05	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_23_01 UR_PRO1_LRM_02_01	Passed performance test: verified through current consumption measurement and simulated use. The accepted value is a minimum of 2 days of intermittent measurements.
SR_PRO1_LRM_06_01	The LRM complies with the safety indices on potential thermal and mechanical hazards as described in IEC 60601-1 standard.	LRM_06	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_LRM_03_01	Passed performance and safety tests: all standard requirements are fulfilled.
SR_PRO1_LRM_07_01	The LRM provides an SDK for data processing and programming interfaces, specified in D6.1 'Specifications'.	LRM_07	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_23_01	Passed functionality and compatibility tests: The SDK fulfills the requirements for command execution, data communication, processing, and programming functionality.

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Limb Activity Module (LAM)						
SR_PRO1_LAM_01_01	The LAM module integrates inertial measurement unit (IMU) and optionally photoplethysmography (PPG) sensors.	LAM_01	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_LAM_01_01	Passed functionality test: the LAM module integrates IMU and PPG sensors.
SR_PRO1_LAM_02_01	The LAM has a minimum sampling rate of 50Hz for activity and orientation measurements	LAM_02	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_LAM_01_01	Passed performance test: the sampling rate is equal to 100Hz.
SR_PRO1_LAM_03_01	The LAM measurements are in the range of: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) accelerometer (3 axes): ± 2 to ± 16 g, 2) gyroscope (3 axes): ± 250 to ± 2000 deg/s, 3) magnetometer (3 axes): ± 4900 μT 	LAM_03	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_LAM_01_01	Passed performance test: Validation against a reference (electromagnetic orientation and position measuring device) is acceptable within $\pm 3\%$.
SR_PRO1_LAM_04_01	The LAM consists of a minimum of three IMU sensors per leg, with one sensors per leg segment: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) foot, 2) calf, 3) thigh. 	LAM_04	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_LAM_01_01	Passed functionality test: The LAM module integrates at least three IMU sensors per leg and one sensor per leg segment.
SR_PRO1_LAM_05_01	[Optional] The LAM contains an extra IMU sensor placed on torso.	LAM_05	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_LAM_01_01	Passed functionality test: the LAM module integrates an additional IMU torso sensor for zero calibration.
SR_PRO1_LAM_06_01	[Optional] The LAM contains extra IMU sensors for redudancy and data quality enhancement.	LAM_06	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_LAM_01_01	Passed functionality test: the LAM module integrates an additional IMU sensor for data quality enhancement.
SR_PRO1_LAM_07_01	For each connected IMU sensor the LAM outputs: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 3D orientation data (in degrees, radians, quaternions), 	LAM_07	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_LAM_01_01	Passed functionality test: for each connected IMU sensor, the LAM outputs and CHI receives

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	2) raw sensors data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) 3-axes acceleration (m/s²) b) 3-axes angular velocity (deg/s) c) 3-axes magnetic flux (μT) 					3D orientation data and raw sensor data.
SR_PRO1_LAM_08_01	The LAM communicates with the CHI via WiFi	LAM_08	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_23_01	Passed functionality test: the settings, commands and data are successfully communicated to and from the LAM to the CHI via WiFi.
SR_PRO1_LAM_09_01	LAM uses a rechargeable battery for at least 2 days of intermittent monitoring	LAM_09	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_LAM_02_01	Passed performance test: verified through current consumption measurement and simulated use. The accepted value is a minimum of 2 days of intermittent measurements.
SR_PRO1_LAM_10_01	The LAM complies with the safety indices on potential thermal and mechanical hazards as described in the IEC 60601-1 standard.	LAM_10	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_LAM_03_01	Passed performance and safety tests: all standard requirements are fulfilled.
SR_PRO1_LAM_11_01	The LAM provides an SDK for data processing and programming interfaces.	LAM_11	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_CHI_23_01	Passed functionality and compatibility tests: the SDK fulfills the requirements for command execution, data communication, processing, and programming functionality.
SR_PRO1_LAM_12_01	The LAM is integrated into a biocompatible and washable wearable with the EIP and the LRM.	LAM_12	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_LAM_02_01 UR_PRO1_LAM_03_01 UR_PRO1_LAM_04_01	Passed safety tests: the LAM fits into the biocompatible wearable.

Extended Reality & Serious Gaming Module (XGM)

Unique Identifier	System Requirement	Ref No.	Change Index	Date	Ref. to User Requirement	Acceptance Criteria (including Test Procedure, as applicable)
SR_PRO1_XGM_01_01	<p>The XGM has a database containing lower limb exercises (at least 50) and poses which are recommended for:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) DVT prevention/ rehabilitation, 2) rehabilitation after orthopedic surgery, 3) US, EIM and LRM examination, 4) [Optional] rehabilitation of patients defined in the ThrombUS+ Use Cases (D2.1). <p>Each exercise is represented by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) IMU data 2) [Optional] video 3) metadata (name of exercise, description, textual guidance, indication (ICD11), photo, keywords, can be used in the serious game, etc.). 	XGM_01	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_XGM_01_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_02_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_03_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_04_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_05_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_06_01	Passed software test: database functionality (data integrity, completeness, etc.)
SR_PRO1_XGM_02_01	<p>The XGM has a private database per patient (as a personal health record segment) that stores exercise prescriptions, personalized exercises, recordings of lower-limb activity, patient progress calculated data, and XR/SG state data.</p>	XGM_02	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_XGM_07_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_08_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_09_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_10_01	Passed software test: database functionality (accessibility, data integrity, completeness, etc.)
SR_PRO1_XGM_03_01	<p>The XGM has an interface for recording exercises:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) start/ stop recording option, 2) accept/decline recording option, 3) meta data input (name of exercises, description, photo, keywords, can be used in the serious game, etc.) 	XGM_03	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_XGM_01_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_02_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_03_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_04_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_05_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_06_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_16_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_XGM_04_01	<p>The XGM has an interface to be used by the physiotherapists to prescribe rehabilitation schemes, such as:</p>	XGM_04	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_XGM_07_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_08_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_09_01	Passed software test: application functionality,

Unique Identifier	System Requirement	Ref No.	Change Index	Date	Ref. to User Requirement	Acceptance Criteria (including Test Procedure, as applicable)
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) browse/search, preview and select exercises, 2) set the sequence of exercises, 3) for each exercise: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) number of repetitions, b) number of sets, c) record a demonstration of exercise on patient (set the goal for exercise - personalization of the exercise), 4) visualize lower limb in real time during demonstration, 5) set the number of scheme repetition per day, 6) set the duration for the whole scheme, 7) set multiple schemes for the whole rehabilitation program (calendar), 8) to set prohibited exercises. 				UR_PR01_XGM_10_01 UR_PR01_XGM_11_01 UR_PR01_XGM_12_01 UR_PR01_XGM_13_01	Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PR01_XGM_05_01	The XGM has an interface to select from the prescribed exercises and the ability to: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) visualize in 3D each exercise, 2) visualize in 3D the current lower limb pose (real-time), 3) visualize in 3D an overlap / comparison of real-time activity and the recorded exercise, 4) provide guidance on how to perform each exercise, 5) notify the patient if prohibited exercise is detected. 	XGM_05	1	2024-10-30	UR_PR01_XGM_11_01 UR_PR01_XGM_12_01 UR_PR01_XGM_13_01 UR_PR01_XGM_14_01 UR_PR01_XGM_15_01 UR_PR01_XGM_16_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PR01_XGM_06_01	The XGM is controlled (starts/stops/pause) on demand by the central intelligence application	XGM_06	1	2024-10-30	UR_PR01_XGM_18_01 UR_PR01_XGM_19_01	Passed software test: start/stop/pause EXG system

Unique Identifier	System Requirement	Ref No.	Change Index	Date	Ref. to User Requirement	Acceptance Criteria (including Test Procedure, as applicable)
						through the central intelligence application
SR_PRO1_XGM_07_01	The XGM captures all data that are related to exercises and application metadata when application runs for future activity visualization and reporting.	XGM_07	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_XGM_16_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_17_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_18_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_19_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_20_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_21_01	Passed software test: service functionality
SR_PRO1_XGM_08_01	The XGM has an interface to: 1) display reports including visual elements on patient's progress (including activity during gaming), 2) to export stored/recorded data.	XGM_08	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_XGM_20_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_21_01	Passed software test: application functionality, Passed usability test: application interface evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_XGM_09_01	The XGM has at least 3 different story lines.	XGM_09	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_XGM_23_01	Passed software test: game functionality, Passed usability test: game evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_XGM_10_01	The game adapts the level of difficulty based on the prescription scheme (e.g. number of repetitions, sets, duration, etc.) and the patient's progress.	XGM_10	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_XGM_22_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_24_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_25_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_26_01	Passed software test: game functionality
SR_PRO1_XGM_11_01	Each story line accepts as input at least 5 exercises (i.e., as HCI commands).	XGM_11	1	2024-10-30	UR_PRO1_XGM_22_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_26_01	Passed software test: game functionality, Passed usability test: game evaluation by users
SR_PRO1_XGM_12_01	Game engagement is supported for each one of the 3 lower limb segments for at least one exercise and at least one story line	XGM_12	1	2025-11-12	UR_PRO1_XGM_22_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_26_01	Passed software test: game functionality, Passed usability test: game evaluation by users

Unique Identifier	System Requirement	Ref No.	Change Index	Date	Ref. to User Requirement	Acceptance Criteria (including Test Procedure, as applicable)
SR_PRO1_XGM_13_01	Game engagement is supported for patients in the lying, sitting and standing position	XGM_13	1	2025-11-12	UR_PRO1_XGM_22_01 UR_PRO1_XGM_26_01	Passed software test: game functionality, Passed usability test: game evaluation by users

ANNEX 3 | State-of-the-art analysis and existing gaps implying requirements

1. Risk assessment scores

Factors that promote the formation of blood clots within the veins can be categorized into those that promote venous stasis, those that enhance blood hypercoagulability, and those that cause endothelial injury. This trio of factors is collectively known as “Virchow’s triad”¹¹.

Risk factors for DVT can be either acquired or inherited. Acquired risk factors contribute to the development of DVT, with more than 50% of patients diagnosed with DVT presenting with one or more acquired risk factors. These include, but are not limited to, surgeries, trauma, cancer, pregnancy, cardiovascular and autoimmune diseases, immobilization, and previous thromboembolic events. On the other hand, while several inherited risk factors have been identified, the Factor V Leiden mutation and the prothrombin gene mutation account for more than 50% of all inherited thrombophilic disorders¹¹.

Over the past decades, several scoring systems have been developed and evaluated to stratify DVT-related risks. These systems rely on the patient’s medical history, clinical evaluation, symptoms, and laboratory tests. They are used in clinical practice to assist medical personnel in prescribing personalized anticoagulation prophylaxis for patients at high risk of DVT. Some of the main DVT risk assessment scores are reviewed below:

- **Caprini Risk Assessment Model**¹² is one of the most widely used DVT risk assessment tools. It evaluates various risk factors such as age, surgery type, personal history of DVT, and comorbidities like cancer and heart failure. Points are assigned to each risk factor, and the total score determines the patient’s risk level.
- **Wells Score** is commonly used to assess the probability of DVT in patients with symptoms suggestive of DVT, such as leg swelling and pain. It considers factors such as clinical signs and symptoms, previous DVT or pulmonary embolism (PE), recent surgery, immobilization, and the likelihood of alternative diagnoses being less than DVT. To safely rule out DVT, the D-dimer test should complement the Well’s score algorithm¹³.
- **Primary Care Rule** is a rule to estimate DVT risk in mainly by primary care physicians. It requires patients’ history information, such as active cancer or previous documented DVT, physical examination, and a D-dimer test¹⁴.
- **Padua Prediction Score**¹⁵ assesses the risk of venous thromboembolism (VTE), which includes both DVT and pulmonary embolism (PE). It considers various risk factors such as cancer, recent surgery, heart or respiratory failure, previous VTE, and age.

¹¹ Bagot et al. Virchow and his triad: a question of attribution. *Br J Haematol.* 2008 Oct;143(2):180-90. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2141.2008.07323.x> Epub 2008 Sep 6. PMID: 18783400.

¹² Cronin et al. Completion of the Updated Caprini Risk Assessment Model (2013 Version). *Clinical and applied thrombosis/hemostasis: official journal of the International Academy of Clinical and Applied Thrombosis/Hemostasis* vol. 25 (2019): 1076029619838052. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1076029619838052>

¹³ Wells et al. Evaluation of D-dimer in the diagnosis of suspected deep-vein thrombosis. *The New England journal of medicine* vol. 349,13 (2003): 1227-35. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa023153>

¹⁴ Oudega et al. Ruling out deep venous thrombosis in primary care. A simple diagnostic algorithm including D-dimer testing. *Thrombosis and haemostasis* vol. 94,1 (2005): 200-5. <https://doi.org/10.1160/TH04-12-0829>

¹⁵ Barbar et al. A risk assessment model for the identification of hospitalized medical patients at risk for venous thromboembolism: the Padua Prediction Score. *Journal of thrombosis and haemostasis: JTH* vol. 8,11 (2010): 2450-7. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1538-7836.2010.04044.x>

- **Geneva Score**¹⁶ is similar to the Wells Score and is used to assess the pretest probability of DVT in symptomatic patients. It considers factors such as clinical signs and symptoms, history of previous DVT or PE, and other possible diagnoses.
- **Hereditary Thrombophilia Risk Score**¹⁷ assesses the risk of DVT based on genetic factors predisposing individuals to thrombophilia, such as deficiencies in antithrombin, protein C, or protein S, or the presence of the factor V Leiden mutation or the prothrombin gene mutation.

A recent study¹⁸ concluded that the four risk assessment scores, Original Geneva, Simplified Geneva, Padua, and IMPROVE¹⁹, have limited overall accuracy and prognostic performance, raising questions about their clinical usefulness. Obtained sensitivity of 90-day VTE prediction ranged from 39.3% to 82.1% and specificity from 34.3% to 70.4%.

1.1. Summary of knowledge gaps and potential solutions with implications for requirements

- Most DVT risk assessment scores require a specialist’s subjective estimation of the likelihood of an alternative diagnosis. These scores rely on the patient’s medical history, clinical evaluation, symptoms, and laboratory tests. DVT can be safely excluded only in patients who are clinically assessed as “unlikely” to have DVT and simultaneously have a negative D-dimer test. In such cases, ultrasonography can be omitted.
- Most DVT risk assessment scores do not consider medical device-based quantitative measurements.
- Automating the estimation of DVT risk assessment scores would be beneficial for medical specialists and motivated patients alike.

2. Prophylaxis methods

There are several DVT prophylaxis methods after surgical operations: anticoagulants (blood thinners), graduated compression (passive) stockings, active leg exercises, intermittent pneumatic compression, neuromuscular electrical stimulation, and exoskeletons for performing passive leg exercises.

Active leg exercises increase blood flow and cause stagnant blood to be pumped out of veins. Immobility is one of the leading causes of thrombus formation. In scenarios where a patient can be physically active, it is necessary to perform exercises regularly. For example, long flights are a risk, which can be mitigated by periodically walking or performing a calf-pump manoeuvre (raising the foot). Physical activity can be a safe and beneficial part of the recovery process for patients with DVT. For those with acute DVT, early walking exercise is generally safe and may help reduce acute symptoms. However, strenuous activities like running or jumping should be avoided. In patients with a history of DVT, exercise training, such as walking, cycling, or

¹⁶ Nendaz et al. Multicentre validation of the Geneva Risk Score for hospitalised medical patients at risk of venous thromboembolism. *Explicit Assessment of Thromboembolic Risk and Prophylaxis for Medical Patients in Switzerland (ESTIMATE)*. *Thrombosis and haemostasis* vol. 111,3 (2014): 531-8. <https://doi.org/10.1160/TH13-05-0427>

¹⁷ Klarin et al. Genome-wide association analysis of venous thromboembolism identifies new risk loci and genetic overlap with arterial vascular disease. *Nature genetics* vol. 51,11 (2019): 1574-1579. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-019-0519-3>

¹⁸ Häfliger et al. Risk Assessment Models for Venous Thromboembolism in Medical Inpatients. *JAMA network open* vol. 7,5 e249980. 1 May. 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2024.9980>

¹⁹ Spyropoulos et al. Predictive and associative models to identify hospitalized medical patients at risk for VTE. *Chest* vol. 140,3 (2011): 706-714. <https://doi.org/10.1378/chest.10-1944>

swimming, can improve muscle strength and pump function in the legs, potentially preventing or improving post-thrombotic syndrome²⁰.

2.1. Intermittent pneumatic compression

Intermittent pneumatic compression (IPC) devices, substitute the effects of physical activity in immobile patients²¹. When physical activity is not possible, blood tends to stagnate in the veins. Regularly compressing the limb causes the blood to exit and prevents clot formation. The typical compression protocol for Novamedix AV Impulse System Model 6000 (Covidien, Mansfield, MA, USA) for delivering compression pulses is defined as 130 mmHg for 1s every 20s over extended periods.

2.2. Neuromuscular electrical stimulation

Neuromuscular electrical stimulation (NMES) is a promising avenue for DVT prophylaxis during surgery²² and post-surgery applications. The comparison of the IPC device with NMES showed that NMES was better than IPC due to its ability to increase ejected volume significantly, peak venous velocity, and intensity-weighted mean frequency (TAMEAN). NMES produces physiological muscle contractions similar to those during normal walking, leading to a more complete emptying of venous compartments than IPC. NMES is silent, portable, and lacks usability issues, making it more convenient and user-friendly for patients than IPC²³. The study²⁴ found that electrical stimulation devices could emulate the blood flow characteristics of intermittent pneumatic compression in both healthy and stroke participants if the intensity of electrical stimulation was sufficient. Patient and nurse satisfaction with the electrical stimulation devices was positive, with the Geko™ device receiving the highest satisfaction scores. The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence recommended the adoption of the Geko™ for use in people with a high risk of VTE and when other mechanical/pharmacological methods of prophylaxis are impractical or contraindicated in selected patients within the National Health Service in England²⁵. The Geko™ device is a small, disposable, self-adhesive band containing two electrodes and a stimulator with an integral battery that provides approximately 24 hours of operation before replacing the whole unit. It is applied to the lower leg on the skin, overlying the common peroneal nerve (Figure 3a). It pulses a current of 27 mA at a frequency of 1 Hz, which results in a single ankle dorsiflexor muscle twitch every second. Pulse width can be varied between 7 settings (70, 100, 140, 200, 280, 400, and 560 ms) and is adjusted to produce a slight visible movement of the foot. A similar device, Orthopaedic Microstim 2V2 (Figure 3b), consists of a stimulator box and two leads connected to two multiple-use self-adhesive electrodes placed over the common peroneal nerve. Current intensity, pulse width, and frequency can be varied.

²⁰ Kahn SR. et al. Physical activity in patients with deep venous thrombosis: a systematic review. *Thrombosis research* vol. 122,6 (2008): 763-73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.thromres.2007.10.011>

²¹ Kamm R. A study of external pneumatic compression for the prevention of deep venous thrombosis, Ph.D. dissertation, Dept. Mech. Eng, Massachusetts Inst. Technol, Cambridge, MA, USA, 1977.

²² Faghri et al. Electrical stimulation-induced contraction to reduce blood stasis during arthroplasty. *IEEE Trans Rehabil Eng.* 1997;5(1):62-69. <https://doi.org/10.1109/86.559350>

²³ Broderick et al. Comparative lower limb hemodynamics using neuromuscular electrical stimulation (NMES) versus intermittent pneumatic compression (IPC). *Physiol Meas.* 2014;35(9):1849-1859. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0967-3334/35/9/1849>

²⁴ Badger et al. Electrical stimulation devices for the prevention of venous thromboembolism: Preliminary studies of physiological efficacy and user satisfaction. *Journal of rehabilitation and assistive technologies engineering* vol. 5 2055668318800218. 25 Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1177/2055668318800218>

²⁵ Summers et al. The geko™ electro-stimulation device for venous thromboembolism prophylaxis: a NICE medical technology guidance. *Applied health economics and health policy* vol. 13,2 (2015): 135-47. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40258-014-0139-0>

Figure 3. Neuromuscular electro stimulation devices: Geko™ (a), and Orthopaedic Microstim 2V2™ (b).

Another study²⁶ compared NMES with transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS) of the soleus muscle for activation of venous flow. Flow volume (FV in mL/min) and peak velocity (PV in cm/s) from the popliteal vein were recorded via Doppler ultrasound. The improvements in FV were statistically higher with TENS than with NMES, but there was no statistical difference in PV. Thus, TENS obtained a higher flow volume increase from baseline than NMES, but it requires higher stimulation voltages potentially leading to lesser compliance. The habituation effects of week-long stimulation using NMES were investigated²⁷ with the results showing significantly increased ejected venous blood volume and peak velocity. This led to doubling previously reported values. These findings suggest that extended NMES protocols may offer greater hemodynamic benefits for preventing venous stasis than shorter sessions.

2.3. Exoskeletons and soft robotics

Exoskeletons and soft robotics were used for performing passive leg exercises. Soft robotic sock (Figure 4a) was developed to provide robotic assistance in ankle dorsiflexion and plantarflexion of stroke patients who are at high risk of developing deep vein thrombosis²⁸. The actuators extend and contract when infused and deflated from pressurized air. The following study²⁹ compared the venous flow profile of the superficial femoral vein between patients using a soft robotic sock device and those using a conventional IPC device. The conventional device significantly increased venous velocity and volumetric flow during use. The soft robotic sock device increased venous velocity at 10 minutes but showed a decrease at 30 minutes compared to baseline. While the soft robotic sock device demonstrated early effectiveness in enhancing blood flow, it did not sustain this improvement over time.

McKibbin's muscles³⁰ were employed to develop a device (Figure 4b) capable of accomplishing passive ankle exercises including dorsiflexion, plantarflexion, abduction, and adduction for DVT prevention. The device was

²⁶ Senin-Camargo et al. Effects on venous flow of transcutaneous electrical stimulation, neuromuscular stimulation, and sham stimulation on soleus muscle: A randomized crossover study in healthy subjects. *Medicine* vol. 101,35 (2022): e30121. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000030121>

²⁷ Corley et al. Hemodynamic effects of habituation to a week-long program of neuromuscular electrical stimulation. *Medical engineering & physics* vol. 34,4 (2012): 459-65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.medengphy.2011.08.005>

²⁸ Low et al. Effect of a Soft Robotic Sock Device on Lower Extremity Rehabilitation Following Stroke: A Preliminary Clinical Study With Focus on Deep Vein Thrombosis Prevention. *IEEE Journal of Translational Engineering in Health and Medicine* vol. 7 4100106. 22 Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JTEHM.2019.2894753>

²⁹ Low et al. Effect of a Soft Robotic Sock Device on Lower Extremity Rehabilitation Following Stroke: A Preliminary Clinical Study With Focus on Deep Vein Thrombosis Prevention. *IEEE journal of translational engineering in health and medicine* vol. 7 4100106. 22 Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JTEHM.2019.2894753>

³⁰ Chang et al. Design of a Wearable Deep Vein Thrombosis Prevention Device Using Thin McKibben Muscles, 2018 18th International Conference on Mechatronics - Mechatronika (ME), Brno, Czech Republic, 2018, pp. 1-6.

evaluated by evaluating the peripheral blood flow rate measured by a laser Doppler flowmeter (RBF-101, RBF-P101, Pioneer). The average peripheral blood flow rate at the large toe increased from 15.55 ± 2.05 mL/min before ankle exercises to 40.65 ± 5.05 mL/min after. The peripheral blood flow rate at the large toe varies with probe position, making it less reliable for evaluating DVT prevention. Instead, measuring flow rate and velocity in the deep veins of the lower limbs would be more accurate. A more comprehensive assessment, including blood velocity in the large saphenous vein before and after ankle exercises, should be pursued.

Figure 4. Soft robotic sock²⁹ (a), McKibben muscles for performing passive ankle exercises³⁰ (b).

To increase the effectiveness of the compression device, some researchers proposed to combine ankle movement and calf compression³¹. In this case, the device (Figure 5) simulates natural venous return mechanisms, enhancing blood flow and potentially reducing thrombosis-related complications. Experimental results on a healthy volunteer demonstrated a significant improvement in blood flow rate when compared to the ankle at rest, particularly when ankle movement and calf compression were synchronized (209% increase).

Figure 5. Prophylaxis device (left), and measurements of blood flow velocity (right)³¹.

³¹ Vinay et al. Design of a Device for Lower Limb Prophylaxis and Exercise. IEEE journal of translational engineering in health and medicine, 9, 2100107,(2020). <https://doi.org/10.1109/JTEHM.2020.3037018>

2.4. Physiology-guided stimulation

It was hypothesized that the effectiveness of the compression device could be further improved by adaptively synchronizing the prophylaxis device with the heart rate³² or respiration rate³¹. In the first case (Figure 6), a significant increase in blood velocity (56%) was found when the stimulation duration reached 56% of the beat-to-beat interval.

Figure 6. Schematic representation of the heart rate adaptive prophylaxis device (left), duplex ultrasonography, with a ratio of stimulation duration to beat-to-beat interval of 56% (right)³².

Breathing affects venous return^{33,34} by increasing venous blood velocity during inhalation; therefore, it could be used for the adaptation of stimulation. Adaptation to respiration rate is more medically accepted for device activation due to the decreased stimulation frequency and reduced discomfort for patients.

2.5. Exercises

Another method of DVT prophylaxis after surgery involves patients performing prescribed exercises according to given instructions. In the study³⁵, patients were asked to perform an ankle movement sequence consisting of 20° dorsal flexion, 30° varus, 40° plantar flexion, and 30° valgus flexion at a frequency of 30 times per minute, with 8-minute cycles, 1 cycle every 30 minutes, and 20 cycles each day (for 2 weeks post-operation: 7 cycles in the morning, 7 in the afternoon, and 6 in the evening). The control group (not performing exercises) had a significantly higher overall incidence of DVT (8 with asymptomatic DVT, n=97) compared to the case group (1 with asymptomatic DVT, n=96). On the 11th and 14th days of the experiment, the case group showed significantly higher maximum venous outflow and maximum venous capacity than the control group. Regarding the preferred frequency of flexion, the study³⁶ showed no difference in effects between the traditional approach of 3 cycles/min (holding flexion for 10 seconds) and 30 cycles/min. However, the patients expressed that performing flexion at a frequency of 30 cycles/min is more comfortable and causes less limb fatigue.

³² Weyer et al. RheoStim: Development of an Adaptive Multi-Sensor to Prevent Venous Stasis. *Sensors*. 2016; 16(4):428. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s16040428>

³³ Kwon et al. Effects of ankle exercise combined with deep breathing on blood flow velocity in the femoral vein. *Aust J Physiother*. 2003;49(4):253-258. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0004-9514\(14\)60141-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0004-9514(14)60141-0)

³⁴ Zsenák et al. Effect of active and passive techniques used in thromboembolic prophylaxis on venous flow velocity in the post-procedure period. *Frontiers in physiology* vol. 15 1323840. 27 Mar. 2024, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2024.1323840>

³⁵ Li et al. Active Ankle Movements Prevent Formation of Lower-Extremity Deep Venous Thrombosis After Orthopedic Surgery. *Medical science monitor: international medical journal of experimental and clinical research* vol. 22 3169-76. 7 Sep. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.12659/msm.896911>

³⁶ Li et al. Which Frequency of Ankle Pump Exercise Should Be Chosen for the Prophylaxis of Deep Vein Thrombosis? *INQUIRY: The Journal of Health Care Organization, Provision, and Financing*. 2022;59. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00469580221105989>

2.6. Serious games

The risk of thrombosis is greatly increased in patients who are immobilized and bedridden. In such cases, physiotherapists prescribe clinical exercises to reduce the risk of thrombosis, together with anticoagulant treatment. Depending on the patient status and comorbidities, these exercises may be combined with other rehabilitation regimes.

Game-based exercises (exergames) could be used to increase patient compliance with ankle and foot exercise-based DVT prevention³⁷. By aligning the game mechanics with the clinical exercises prescribed by the physiotherapist, the serious game incentivizes patients to perform the essential physiotherapy exercises for DVT. These game elements reinforce motivation through achievements and rewards, transforming the rehabilitation process into an interactive journey of achievement. The justification for the use of extended reality lies in its potential to go beyond traditional exercise methods. Through interactive experiences, patients can grasp the mechanics of movement more intuitively and strengthen the link between movement and thrombosis prevention.

The study³⁸ utilized a wireless foot physical activity sensor (LEGSys; BioSensics LLC, Watertown, Mass) to navigate a computer cursor on a screen and control the game. After the game finished, the investigators measured each patient's mean flow volume, peak flow velocity, mean flow velocity, and the cross-sectional area of the right femoral vein using ultrasound. They found enhanced blood flow in the femoral vein, with mean flow volume, mean flow velocity, and peak systolic velocity increasing by around 50% above baseline. Less forceful but more consistent contractions were found to be the most effective in improving venous blood flow.

Serious games have started to yield important results in healthcare and especially in physical rehabilitation where motivation and frequent patient compliance is crucial for the success of a therapeutic plan. These games exploit gamification approaches to transform the boring physiotherapy exercises into engaging activities, where entertainment and therapeutic aims are hand in hand. Here, we review the serious games already based on rehabilitation and therapy, offering technological and clinical solutions in the field.

Each game is designed with a particular rehabilitation or therapy need in mind: to be played with stroke or brain-injury patients, with surgery patients, with patients suffering from neurological conditions, even with elderly patients who just need some mobility rehab. Many of those games are played on PCs or mobile phones, and several games are even coupled with Microsoft's Kinect or VR for more immersive play. Most frequently, these games feature a potent combo of high-tech sensing technologies, such as motion tracking, VR, AI and wearable sensors and moreover with exoskeletons. The input methods, however, are varied: the motion sensors and wearable devices are common entrant technologies alongside the neural sensors, but standard PC/mobile controls can be deployed, too.

In the following, we will present representative games that relate to rehabilitation.

- **MIRA**³⁹: This is a physical rehabilitation platform designed for elderly patients and individuals recovering from strokes or surgeries. Adapting to patient movements through its advanced motion sensors, it uses artificial intelligence algorithms to follow users through the specified movements and ensure good execution of their prescribed exercises. Using cutting-edge gamification techniques, MIRA replaces traditional at-home physiotherapy exercises with interactive gamified products, thereby addressing the common problem that leads patients to readily skip their home workout sessions, providing both

³⁷ Shimizu et al. A novel exercise device for venous thromboembolism prophylaxis improves venous flow in bed versus ankle movement exercises in healthy volunteers. *Journal of orthopaedic surgery (Hong Kong)* vol. 25,3 (2017): 2309499017739477. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2309499017739477>

³⁸ Rahemi et al. Pilot study evaluating the efficacy of exergaming for the prevention of deep venous thrombosis. *Journal of vascular surgery. Venous and lymphatic disorders* vol. 6,2 (2018): 146-153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvsv.2017.08.019>

³⁹ MIRA Rehab. [Online]. Available: <https://www.fitness-gaming.com/profiles/company/mira-rehab.html>

individualized immediate feedback adjusted to the patient’s performance and generating automatically gathered data to allow remote monitoring of progress by healthcare professionals. Example screenshot is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. An indicative image of a user interacting with MIRA Rehabilitation Platform⁴⁰.

- **Jintronix**⁴¹: is a motion-based rehabilitation platform for stroke survivors and post-surgery patients. It tracks movement-usually through Microsoft Kinect-and guides the patient on how to make their movements better while doing exercises for physical therapy. The mission of Jintronix is to make rehabilitation more accessible, easy, and gamified to increase adherence with home-based exercises and to allow therapists to track improvements over time. An example screenshot is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. An indicative image of a user interacting with Jintronix⁴² user interface.

- **Kinapsys**⁴³: is a 3D motion-tracking rehabilitation system designed for patients with motor impairments. It is a personalized treatment plan that leads patients through exercises using a PC-based platform. It gives therapists real-time feedback with comprehensive tracking to track recovery and modify treatment

⁴⁰ MIRA Rehabilitation Platform Lets Patients Play Their Way to Recovery. [Online]. Available: <https://www.fitness-gaming.com/news/health-and-rehab/mira-rehabilitation-platform-lets-patients-play-their-way-to-recovery.html>

⁴¹ Jintronix. [Online]. Available: <https://jintronix.com/>

⁴² Jintronix. [Online]. Available: <https://hcfinc.com/rehabilitation/specialized-services/jintronix/>

⁴³ Kinapsys. [Online]. Available: <https://www.medicare Relief Center.com/content/kinapsys-0>

strategies. Embedded game elements keep users engaged and compliant with prescribed therapy routines. Example screenshot is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. An indicative image showing a user interacting with Kinapsys⁴³ software and some indicative images of the virtual environment options.

- **MindMaze⁴⁴**: is a different neuro-rehabilitation game that focuses on stroke patients. It uses VR and neural sensors to immerse users in virtual environments, activating brain plasticity and recovering motor functions. The aim was to expose patients to real-life tasks through the platform to regain control over their movements and cognitive abilities. Its scope is more significant than traditional therapy because it uses extended reality tuned with AI for faster rehabilitation. Figure 10 shows an example screenshot.

Figure 10. An indicative image showing a user interacting with MindMaze⁴⁵.

- **Neofect Smart Balance⁴⁶**: focuses on patients' balance rehabilitation after a stroke or a neurological condition. This platform is equipped with wearable sensors and AI, following the movements of patients in tracking exercises accurately challenging leg lifts and ankle rotations. Its gamification and real-time feedback increase patient motivation and adherence to a therapy plan. Example screenshot is shown in Figure 11.

⁴⁴ Mindmaze. [Online]. Available: <https://mindmaze.com/>

⁴⁵ Mindmaze. [Online]. Available: <https://mindmaze.com/digital-therapies-for-neurorehabilitation/>

⁴⁶ Smart Balance. [Online]. Available: <https://www.neofect.com/us/smart-balance>

Figure 11. An indicative image of a user interacting with Neofect Smart Balance⁴⁶.

- **Virtual Rehab**⁴⁷: is an innovative neurorehabilitation platform that combines motion sensors with Kinect in a very interactive way. Virtual Rehab targets patients diagnosed with Parkinson's, multiple sclerosis, or stroke and transforms physical therapy exercises into appealing tasks a patient will have to go through either at home or in the clinic. It also provides real-time feedback while allowing professionals to monitor their condition remotely. Example screenshot is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. An indicative image of a user interacting with the Virtual Rehab⁴⁸ platform.

- **FysioGaming**⁴⁹: offers to patients undergoing physical therapy personalized, gamified rehabilitation exercises of. It converts conventional routines of therapy into entertaining games that encourage patients to be more proactive in treatment. It applies the use of motion sensors in monitoring exercise

⁴⁷ Virtual Reality in Healthcare: a New Solution for Rehabilitation? [Online]. Available from: <https://program-ace.com/blog/virtual-reality-in-healthcare-a-new-solution-for-rehabilitation/>

⁴⁸ Virtual Reality Rehabilitation System. [Online]. Available: <https://sanraffaele.it/en/technology/virtual-reality-rehabilitation-system/>

⁴⁹ FysioGaming Expands Rehabilitation Options with Kinect Games. [Online]. Available from: <https://images.app.goo.gl/YfLMhkdWXapHNvqJ9>

performance and provides data to therapists for recovery progress monitoring and adjustment of the course of therapy when necessary. Example screenshot is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13 An indicative image showing a virtual scene within the FysioGaming⁴⁹ platform.

- **Playwork⁵⁰**: offers physical therapy exercises designed for rehabilitation through motion-tracking technology. By using Kinect sensors, it creates interactive sessions where patients can engage in exercises tailored to their needs. The work plays mode targets generally physical therapy, including also exercises for the elderly or those recovering from injuries, helping them regain mobility through fun, game-based therapy. Example screenshot is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14 An image showing a user performing physical exercises using the Playwork⁵¹. Data are streamed and visualized in a portable display.

- **SWORD Phoenix⁵²**: is an online platform focused on post-surgery rehabilitation, utilizing AI and movement sensors in wearables to lead patients through their exercises that have been prescribed by a physiotherapist. Emphasizing remote care, this platform enables patients to recover in the comfort of their home and receive real-time feedback from both users and healthcare professionals. Example screenshot is shown in Figure 15.

⁵⁰ Smart PLAYBALL by PLAYWORK: The revolutionary Therapy Ball. [Online]. Available: <https://www.playwork.me/playball>

⁵¹ Introducing the Pilates 25.5"/65cm Smart PLAYBALL: Revolutionizing Recovery and Exercise. [Online]. Available: <https://www.playwork.me/post/introducing-the-pilates-25-5-65cm-smart-playball-revolutionizing-recovery-and-exercise>

⁵² Sword Health Introduces Phoenix, the First AI Care Specialist and Raises \$130 Million in a Mix of Primary and Secondary Sale, Increasing Valuation to \$3 Billion. [Online]. Available: <https://swordhealth.com/newsroom/introducing-phoenix>

Figure 15. An indicative image of the SWORD Phoenix⁵² software, showing a user interacting with the platform.

- **Keeogo⁵³**: is a powered walking exoskeleton that assists individuals with mobility problems by helping the weakening muscles of one’s legs through a supporting device that enhances the movement of its wearer. Keeogo, in particular, is an indication in the rehabilitation of patients with impaired gait and mobility because it could have them return to ambulation in a shorter period and with less physiological stress for the patient. An example screenshot is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Image of the Keeogo⁵³ exoskeleton system.

Real-time feedback is another feature of all these games, enabling the user and healthcare professional to monitor the progress instantaneously. Most of the games are single player, though some have options for playing as multiplayer to further social or competitive aspects in treatment. All collect active user data for rehabilitation progress tracking and may be used in research or further customization of treatment. Most current serious games in health, focused on rehabilitation and physical therapy, are compared in Table 13.

⁵³ SMART Powered Knee Orthosis. [Online]. Available: <https://b-temia.com/keeogo/>

Table 13. Comparison among available serious games.

Game Title	Goal	Target Audience	Platform	Technology Used	Input Method	Real-time Feedback	No of players	Data Collection	Year
MIRA	Physical Therapy	Elderly Patients	PC	Motion Sensors, AI	Motion Sensors	Yes	Single	Yes	2014
Jintronix	Rehabilitation Post-Surgery	Stroke, Post-Surgery	PC, Kinect	Motion Tracking, AI	Motion Sensors	Yes	Single, Multi	Yes	2012
Kinapsys	Physical Rehabilitation	Patients with Motor Issues	PC	3D Motion Tracking	Motion Sensors	Yes	Single	Yes	2013
MindMaze	Stroke Rehabilitation	Stroke Patients	VR	VR, AI, Neural Sensors	Neural Sensors, VR	Yes	Single	Yes	2017
Neofect Smart Balance	Balance Training for Rehab	Stroke, Neurological Patients	PC, Mobile	Wearable Sensors, AI	Sensors	Yes	Single	Yes	2019
VirtualRehab	Neurological Rehabilitation	Stroke, Parkinson's Patients	PC, Kinect	Motion Sensors	Kinect Motion Sensors	Yes	Single, Multi	Yes	2012
FysioGaming	Rehabilitation Exercises	Physical Therapy Patients	PC, Mobile	Game-based Rehab	Motion Sensors	Yes	Single	Yes	2011
Playwork	Physical Therapy and Exercise	Patients and Elderly	PC, Kinect	Motion Tracking	Kinect Motion Sensors	Yes	Single	Yes	2015
SWORD Phoenix	Physical Therapy	Patients Recovering from Surgery	Mobile	AI, Digital Therapy	Sensors, Mobile Device	Yes	Single	Yes	2015
Keeogo (B-TEMIA)	Exoskeleton Technology	People with Mobility Issues	Wearable	Exoskeleton Technology	Wearable Exoskeleton	Yes	Single	Yes	2016

The research on sensor-based visualization tools for rehabilitation has focused on different types of technology or methodology, these include wearable sensors (e.g., Inertial Measurement Units, IMUs), Electromyography (EMG) signal captured by biometric sensors active electrodes available as T-Shirts, accelerometers data measuring wheelchair kinematics etc., optical systems such as Kinect from Microsoft or depth cameras and multisensor fusions systems. These tools are essential in providing snapshot views of the patient at a time of immediate concern for yield better outputs to clinicians, patients alike. These programs are developed to enhance the effectiveness of physical therapy exercises, educate patients and encourage compliance in addition to support personalized treatment plans.

2.7. Extended reality

The review of wearable sensors applied in healthcare with a specific focus on rehabilitation was given by Pantelopoulos & Bourbakis⁵⁴. In this paper, the authors detail which information can be obtained from patient movement data (e.g., accelerometers, gyroscopes, EMG sensors) in real-time to correct incorrect

⁵⁴ Pantelopoulos A, Bourbakis N. A survey on wearable biosensor systems for health monitoring. Annu Int Conf IEEE Eng Med Biol Soc. 2008;2008:4887-90. doi: 10.1109/IEMBS.2008.4650309. PMID: 19163812.

exercise performances. Beshara et al.⁵⁵ utilized motion sensors such as IMUs and the Microsoft Kinect for capturing patient movements, with the data being visualized to aid in modifying cises based on their performance.

Porciuncula and colleagues⁵⁶ proposed a multi-wearable sensor system measure with user-specific data modalities, such as IMUs and EMG for continuous monitoring of body motion patterns to assist both the therapists remotely track the rehabilitation progress and adapt therapy according to patient needs. Cuesta-Vargas et al.⁵⁷ explained the role of inertial sensors as a tool to monitor the human kinematics behaviour in rehabilitation, showing that the visualization of instantaneous data acquired by Inertial Sensors can help patients even in real-time to improve posture and range of motion.

Li et al.⁵⁸ developed an IMU-enabled tracking and display system for patient posture, that can provide real-time corrective feedback to ensure proper alignment during exercise. Da Gama et al.⁵⁹ used Microsoft Kinect, an optical depth sensor for monitoring patients' movement without the need to use any additional hardware on patient's body and giving the feedback in real time of their joining angles and body performance. Similarly, Liao et al.⁶⁰ performed the evaluation of rehabilitation systems in real time using depth sensors, such as Kinect and Intel RealSense sensing technologies for tracking and visualization of movements in different therapies, mainly aiming at physical therapy after ischemic stroke.

The effectiveness of electromyographic biofeedback in rehabilitation was studied using EMG sensors that can monitor muscle activity further providing feedback on patterns of muscle activation essential for neuromuscular rehabilitation⁶¹. Patel et al.⁶² provided an overview of wearable EMG sensors and results in the field, including post-stroke recovery and help with sports injuries—from muscle engagement in crutches after ultrasounds to compare rehabilitation techniques using EMG visualization to adjust therapy plans.

To analyse the movement of patients during physical rehabilitation, fusion of multiple sensors was tried for example inertial, optical and EMG sensors to achieve a higher accuracy and consistency in getting deeper insight into patient movements⁶³. Moreover, implants how to extract complex movements using wearable sensors, such as IMUs, EMG and accelerometers combined along a well-defined way of the spine and over

⁵⁵ Beshara P, Anderson DB, Pelletier M, Walsh WR. The Reliability of the Microsoft Kinect and Ambulatory Sensor-Based Motion Tracking Devices to Measure Shoulder Range-of-Motion: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Sensors (Basel)*. 2021 Dec 8;21(24):8186. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21248186>

⁵⁶ Porciuncula F, Roto AV, Kumar D, Davis I, Roy S, Walsh CJ, Awad LN. Wearable Movement Sensors for Rehabilitation: A Focused Review of Technological and Clinical Advances. *PM R*. 2018 Sep;10(9 Suppl 2):S220-S232. doi: 10.1016/j.pmrj.2018.06.013. Erratum in: *PM R*. 2018 Dec;10(12):1437. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmrj.2018.12.002>

⁵⁷ Cuesta-Vargas AI, Galán-Mercant A, Williams JM. The use of inertial sensors system for human motion analysis. *Phys Ther Rev*. 2010 Dec;15(6):462-473. <https://doi.org/10.1179/1743288X11Y.0000000006>

⁵⁸ Li R, Peterson N, Walter HJ, Rath R, Curry C, Stoffregen TA. Real-time visual feedback about postural activity increases postural instability and visually induced motion sickness. *Gait Posture*. 2018 Sep;65:251-255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2018.08.005>

⁵⁹ Da Gama A, Fallavollita P, Teichrieb V, Navab N. Motor Rehabilitation Using Kinect: A Systematic Review. *Games Health J*. 2015 Apr;4(2):123-35. <https://doi.org/10.1089/g4h.2014.0047>

⁶⁰ Liao Y, Vakanski A, Xian M, Paul D, Baker R. A review of computational approaches for evaluation of rehabilitation exercises. *Comput Biol Med*. 2020 Apr;119:103687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combiomed.2020.103687>

⁶¹ Mackay EJ, Robey NJ, Suprak DN, Buddhadev HH, San Juan JG. The effect of EMG biofeedback training on muscle activation in an impingement population. *J Electromyogr Kinesiol*. 2023 Jun;70:102772. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jelekin.2023.102772>

⁶² Patel S, Park H, Bonato P, Chan L, Rodgers M. A review of wearable sensors and systems with application in rehabilitation. *J Neuroeng Rehabil*. 2012 Apr 20;9:21. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1743-0003-9-21>

⁶³ Gravina R, Alinia P, Ghasemzadeh H, & Fortino G. Multi-sensor fusion in body sensor networks: State-of-the-art and research challenges. *Information Fusion*, 2017; 35, 1339-1351. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2016.09.005>

specific joints on the skin which can be fused for monitoring and visualizing them in order to support by physicians or patients to assess the quality of movement and eventually the effectiveness of exercise.

Lastly, Adans-Dester et al.⁶⁴ 2020 [64] concentrated on importing data collected from wearable sensors to visualization tools to give instant feedback of movement patterns, muscle activation and joint angles for the subjects, while they are performing rehabilitation exercises so that they could be well-appraised by regarding their postures and movements as incorrect. This expansive work elucidates the importance of sensor based-visualization in contemporaneous rehabilitation and has fuelled a new generation of patient-centred, live-feedback point-of-care approaches to optimize outcomes.

Sensor-based technologies in the last few years, revolutionized rehabilitation as advanced tools for monitoring analysing and visualizing patient movement in real-time were introduced. These inventions have become key support in the road of recovery itself, helping to gain importance for the therapy performance and deliver some clarifications needed for both physiotherapists as well as patients. Wearable sensors, like IMUs, EMG and accelerometers are becoming extremely popular to track body movements, muscle activity and biomechanics. Meanwhile, optical systems such as the Microsoft Kinect and depth cameras have made movement analysis a reality in non-invasive settings which is important for detailed kinematic analysis without need for wearables.

Multisensor systems have also made it even more accurate and reliable in the capturing of different motor patterns thanks to this fusion between different sensors, which allows for adding and improving the quality of movement tracking introduced. There are some real-time visualization tools that use raw sensor data streams to provide intuitive, interactive feedback for patients and therapists so they can keep tabs on progress and modulate therapy as needed. Beyond increasing the effectiveness of rehabilitation, these tools also increase patient motivation by providing patients with immediate performance feedback and allow opportunities for customized therapy. These sensor-based visualization tools are transforming rehabilitation from postural correction to gait analysis and neuromuscular recovery in an innovative way for dynamic, data-driven solutions that improve patient outcomes. Here we can see the most relevant platforms that are currently used in the healthcare industry.

Figure 17. Indicative images of the Motek Medical – CAREN⁶⁵, with a user interacting with the platform.

- **Motek Medical - CAREN (Computer Assisted Rehabilitation Environment)**⁶⁵: The CAREN (Cardiovascular Aquatic Rehabilitation & Exercise Networks) is a next-generation rehabilitation platform, which combines

⁶⁴ Adans-Dester C, Hankov N, O'Brien A, Vergara-Diaz G, Black-Schaffer R, Zafonte R, Dy J, Lee SI, Bonato P. Enabling precision rehabilitation interventions using wearable sensors and machine learning to track motor recovery. NPJ Digit Med. 2020 Sep 21;3:121. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-020-00328-w>

⁶⁵ The World's Most Advanced Biomechanics Lab. Study all aspects of balance and locomotion. [Online]. Available: <https://www.motekmedical.com/solution/caren/>

advanced technology for motion captures and force plates, along with visualization — all built into an immersive real-time rehabilitation environment (Figure 17). The system uses 3D motion capture to track patient movements and provide real-time visual feedback through visual environments displayed on a screen (to which the patient wears active glasses) or VR. The system works best for the patients who are recovering from neurological conditions, orthopedic injuries or balance related disorders.

- **Rehabkit⁶⁶**: A Kinect sensor with screen displayed movement patterns of the subject during certain rehab exercises in real-time, while a traditional computer-based program was available for other general functions. It is meant to help patients with conditions like stroke, orthopedic injuries and neuromuscular disorders rehabilitate by prompting them through predefined room-based exercises.
- **MIT's Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence Laboratory⁶⁷**: MIT's "MuscleRehab" system combines electrical impedance tomography and motion tracking to visualize muscle engagement and movement during unsupervised physical rehab (Figure 18). This tool enables users to track deep muscle engagement in real time, helping improve exercise accuracy and quality. Designed by MIT's CSAIL and Massachusetts General Hospital, it has potential applications in home rehabilitation for patients with mobility limitations and could be expanded for broader muscle groups and radiotherapy applications. This innovation aims to aid effective at-home rehab and enhance monitoring outside of clinical settings.

Figure 18. Indicative image of a user wearing the MuscleRehab⁶⁷ system, and the corresponding tracking of muscle activity.

- **Zeno Track (ProtoKinetics)⁶⁸**: Zeno Track is a gait analysis and rehabilitation platform combining pressure sensitive walkways with motion sensors to visualize patient movements (Figure 19). During walking exercises, it records more sophisticated data on the patient's foot pressure, gait symmetry and balance and displays this information in an easy-to-understand format for use by healthcare professionals to analyse modifications to their treatment pathways.

⁶⁶ Evolv Rehabkit. [Online]. Available: <https://evolvrehab.com/evolvrehab/rehabkit/>

⁶⁷ MIT system "sees" the inner structure of the body during physical rehab [Online]. Available: <https://news.mit.edu/2022/mit-system-sees-inner-structure-body-during-physical-rehab-1011>

⁶⁸ The Zeno™ Walkway Gait Analysis System. [Online]. Available: <https://protokinetics.com/zeno-walkway/>

Figure 19. An indicative image of a user walking over the Zeno Track (ProtoKinetics)⁶⁹.

- **Rehabitic⁷⁰**: Rehabitic is a platform that uses inertial measurement units (IMUs) and wearable sensors to capture movement data and visualize the patient's range of motion and posture (Figure 20). It is designed for patients undergoing rehabilitation after surgery or injury, providing both patients and therapists with real-time feedback on exercise performance.

Figure 20. An indicative image from the Rehabitic⁷¹ platform.

- **KineQuantum⁷²**: KineQuantum is a sensor and data processing software solution that uses wearable technology for movement monitoring in patients performing rehabilitation exercises (Figure 21). The system includes accelerometers and gyroscopes to measure range of motion during joint angle and movement patterns; this individual movement data can help therapists develop systematic rehabilitation programs that are more effective.

⁶⁹ Exercise. [Online]. Available: <https://protokinetics.com/>

⁷⁰ Rehabitic. [Online]. Available: https://www.imim.es/media/upload/arxius/oferta%20tecnologica/REHABITICwebIMIM_EN.pdf

⁷¹ BLOG DE REHABILITACIÓN QUE MIRA AL FUTURO. [Online]. Available: <http://www.rehabilitacionblog.com/2010/07/rehabitic-un-proyecto-de-telefonica.html>

⁷² KineQuantum. Virtual Reality for physiotherapists. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kinequantum.com/en>

Figure 21. An image of the portable KineQuantum⁷³sensor.

- **Hinge Health⁷⁴:** Hinge Health is a sensor-based digital platform that provides musculoskeletal rehabilitation supported by guided mobile apps, which guide the patient through personalized exercise programs. Real-time motion tracking is thus enabled, along with visual feedback on movement quality to allow patients to correctly perform exercises without injury (Figure 22).

Figure 22. An indicative image of a user interacting with Hinge Health⁷⁵. User's current pose is visualized in a display device along with exercise-related metrics.

2.8. Summary of knowledge gaps and potential solutions with implications for requirements

- Pharmacological prophylaxis methods, though considered the gold standard, carry the highest risks, while mechanical or electrical methods, which are generally safer, still need to undergo large-scale randomized clinical trials to assess the efficacy and risks associated with each technique.
- A combination of different mechanical and/or electrical stimulation methods synchronized with physiological processes (e.g., breathing) and combined with exergames could potentially increase the efficiency of venous flow.
- The majority of analysed studies evaluated changes in venous flow using Doppler ultrasound parameters such as ejected venous blood volume and peak velocity.
- Although duplex ultrasonography is the standard technique for measuring venous flow, the critical or clinically meaningful lower limb venous flow parameters and their thresholds necessary to reduce the risk of thromboembolism are unknown.

⁷³ Boost your practice with KineQuantum Liberty. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kinequantum.com/en/outil-kinequantum-liberte>

⁷⁴ Your digital clinic for joint and muscle care. [Online]. Available: <https://www.hingehealth.com/>

⁷⁵ Hinge Health raises \$300M Series D at \$3B valuation. [Online]. Available: <https://www.hingehealth.com/resources/press-releases/hinge-health-raises-series-d/>

- There are no proposed solutions for operator-independent ultrasonography in venous flow monitoring during prolonged prophylaxis and monitoring procedures.
- Few attempts in the literature have explored the use of serious games for DVT prophylaxis. Integrating such games into the DVT monitoring platform could offer immersive, game-like activity plans tailored to (partially) immobilized patients, based on physiotherapeutic prescriptions. This approach would significantly enhance the value of the ThrombUS+ system, supporting DVT prevention and rehabilitation.

3. DVT monitoring and diagnostic methods and technologies

3.1. B-scan and Doppler Ultrasound

Venous ultrasound is the standard imaging test for patients suspected of having acute deep venous thrombosis (DVT), which prevails in the lower extremities. Scalable ultrasound protocols, together with follow-up and recurrent DVT management guides, are recommended by radiologists⁷⁶, including applications in emergency⁷⁷, trauma^{78,79} and monitoring of asymptomatic intensive care patients⁸⁰. Depending on the situation, protocols recommend different investigation modalities – from applying compression ultrasonography (CUS) in two regions to extensive and full leg investigation, including complete Doppler ultrasound. A bedside ultrasound examination - a point-of-care ultrasound (POCUS)- has been increasingly used for DVT evaluation, mainly in urgent and critical care settings, ambulatory clinics, and the medical wards⁸¹. Duplex ultrasound offers an additional possibility to image a venous blood flow, thus enhancing DVT detection reliability⁸². Systematic reviews of main ultrasonography strategies - single limited, serial limited, and whole-leg CUS - have shown that all three strategies are comparable in performance. Also, a comparative analysis of 2⁸³ CUS POCUS techniques showed excellent performance for diagnosing. Those results indicate the high potential of local CUS in detecting DVT. Ultrasound is also an effective tool for characterizing

⁷⁶ Needleman et al. Ultrasound for Lower Extremity Deep Venous Thrombosis. *Circulation*, vol. 137, no. 14, pp. 1505–1515, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.117.030687>

⁷⁷ Di Vilio et al. Incremental Value of Compression Ultrasound Sonography in the Emergency Department. *World Journal of Critical Care Medicine* 10, no. 5 (9 September 2021): 194–203, <https://doi.org/10.5492/wjccm.v10.i5.194>

⁷⁸ Abdulaziz et al. Ultrasound Surveillance for Deep Venous Thrombosis and Subsequent Venous Thromboembolism in Adults with Trauma: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Medicine* 102, no. 43 (27 October 2023): e35625, <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000035625>

⁷⁹ Abdulaziz et al., Ultrasound Surveillance for Deep Venous Thrombosis and Subsequent Venous Thromboembolism in Adults with Trauma: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Medicine* 102, no. 43 (27 October 2023): e35625, <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000035625>

⁸⁰ Giordano et al., Ultrasound Screening for Asymptomatic Deep Vein Thrombosis in Critically Ill Patients: A Pilot Trial. *Internal and Emergency Medicine* 17, no. 8 (2022): 2269–77, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11739-022-03085-8>

⁸¹ POCUS Spotlight: Lower Extremity DVT Scanning, ASRA Pain Medicine, accessed 29 May 2024. Available: <https://www.asra.com/news-publications/asra-newsletter/newsletter-item/asra-news/2023/05/13/pocus-spotlight-lower-extremity-dvt-scanning>

⁸² Zygmunt et al Duplex Ultrasound Technical Considerations for Lower Extremity Venous Disease. *Endovascular Today* (Bryn Mawr Communications), accessed 29 May 2024, <https://evtoday.com/articles/2020-mar/duplex-ultrasound-technical-considerations-for-lower-extremity-venous-disease>

⁸³ Kraaijpoel et al. Diagnostic Accuracy of Three Ultrasonography Strategies for Deep Vein Thrombosis of the Lower Extremity: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *PLOS ONE* 15, no. 2 (11 February 2020): e0228788, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0228788>

thrombus age (acute or chronic) and structure by echogenicity and elasticity parameters⁸⁴. During ultrasound investigation of DVT, some physical impact to the extremity under investigation is used – a pressure for venous deformation, a cuff for temporal occlusion of venous blood flow, and an augmentation of venous flow by short pressure pulses applied distally. A combination of ultrasound technologies – B-scan, Duplex, Doppler spectrum, elastography - with testing maneuvers: Valsalva, changing leg position, vein pressure by the transducer, by the cuff, or distally by finger creates additional methods for DVT detection used⁸⁵.

Ultrasound measurements for lower limb venous flow assessment: vessel diameter, volume flow, time-averaged mean velocity (TAMV), the time-averaged maximum velocity, and peak velocity in the vein over three periods in cm/s. Volume flow (ml/min) is the product of the TAMV and the cross-sectional area of the blood vessel. TAMV (cm/s) is the weighted mean velocity during each time interval³² averaged out over the trace as an estimate of true mean velocity. Peak velocity (cm/s) is the maximum velocity reached during the trace⁸⁶.

Emerging solutions in machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) additionally enhance the performance of DVT detection by ultrasound⁸⁷. First results are obtained in the automatic detection and segmentation of blood vessels in B-scan images⁸⁸, prediction of DVT using comprehensive clinical data⁸⁹. An example of emerging pilot solutions on wearable vascular ultrasound is a carotid Doppler patch used for heart stroke volume⁹⁰ quite effective for arterial blood flow, but similar monitoring for slow venous flow still is highly problematic.

The development flexibility of sonography equipment is ensured through the collaboration of three partners: the imaging beamformer producer (TELEMED) and two producers of imaging transducers (VERMON and FRAUNHOFER). The development of middleware accessories integrating the independent data channels is strengthened by experts from two technical universities. The groups from KTU University and TAU are experts in biomedical engineering. The three independent data channels from planned clinical trials on venous outflow provide synergistic possibilities and highlight the strengths of potential practical methods, while research methods, though too sophisticated for direct application, will support the practical methods for clinical implementation.

The current US technique is manually operated by the sonographer, using subjective and subtle maneuvers with the imaging transducer and performing venous outflow augmentation, and analyzing speed-time

⁸⁴ Berthomier et al. Deep Venous Thrombus Characterization: Ultrasonography, Elastography and Scattering Operator. *Advances in Science, Technology and Engineering Systems Journal* 2 (1 April 2017): 48–59, <https://doi.org/10.25046/aj020308>

⁸⁵ Meha et al. Diagnosis of Deep Vein Thrombosis of the Lower Extremity: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Test Accuracy. *Blood Advances* 4, no. 7 (30 March 2020): 1250–64, <https://doi.org/10.1182/bloodadvances.2019000960>

⁸⁶ Badger et al. Electrical stimulation devices for the prevention of venous thromboembolism: Preliminary studies of physiological efficacy and user satisfaction. *Journal of rehabilitation and assistive technologies engineering* vol. 5 2055668318800218. 25 Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1177/2055668318800218>

⁸⁷ Kainz et al. Non-Invasive Diagnosis of Deep Vein Thrombosis from Ultrasound with Machine Learning. (medRxiv, 27 January 2021), <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.01.23.21249964>

⁸⁸ Hernanda et al. Semantic Segmentation of Venous on Deep Vein Thrombosis (DVT) Case Using UNet-ResNet. In *2022 10th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology (ICoICT)* (2022 10th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology (ICoICT), Bandung, Indonesia: IEEE, 2022), 105–9, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICoICT55009.2022.9914835>

⁸⁹ Hou et al. The Use of Machine Learning Techniques to Predict Deep Vein Thrombosis in Rehabilitation Inpatients. *Clinical and Applied Thrombosis/Hemostasis* 29 (26 June 2023): 10760296231179438, <https://doi.org/10.1177/10760296231179438>

⁹⁰ Kenny et al. Diagnostic Characteristics of 11 Formulae for Calculating Corrected Flow Time as Measured by a Wearable Doppler Patch. *Intensive Care Medicine Experimental*, 2020, 11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40635-020-00339-7>

waveforms by eye. This non-automated approach is one of the weaknesses of current sonography tools. Routine sonography transducers are still manually operated and produced in a standard design, which is a technological limitation. Commercial sonography equipment is limited for non-routine applications, especially when implementing additional data channels to characterize blood flow.

The possibility of an on-body mounted imaging transducer is strengthened by the project's partnership with two producers of imaging transducers. A dedicated design for the on-body mounting of the transducers can be developed. Corresponding imaging beamforming equipment is also flexibly adapted for more automated data acquisition of venous structures in the thigh. If imaging data alone is insufficient to represent the vein structure with adequate quality, an additional functionality to quantify venous blood flow can be implemented. The optional feature for assessing blood outflow is ultrasonic Doppler functionality. The research openness of the imaging algorithms favours synchronized data analysis of augmentation and outflow trends during venous outflow monitoring.

3.1.1. Summary of knowledge gaps and potential solutions with implications for requirements

- Insufficient quality and informativity of ultrasound images used for detection, diagnostic, and monitoring purposes. This is caused by the problems of placement and orientation of ultrasound scanning planes regarding veins. Several scanning planes (preferably orthogonal, along, and perpendicular to the vein) are needed for the increased reliability of DVT detection. This implies a new configuration of several ultrasound transducer arrays and beamformers working simultaneously.
- The need for assistance means for US image stabilization and tracking of veins under investigation. Online detection of veins in the diversity of patients, stabilization of images, and obtaining proper Doppler signals is still a big problem, which requires ML-based tracking and segmentation solutions, together with integrated controllable pressure on the vein for thrombus detection.
- Lack of solutions for long-term continuous and/or intermittent monitoring and monitoring of DVT risk. This requires a dedicated scalable solution integrating wearable lower extremity straps (socks), configurable ultrasonic transducers, inflatable cuffs for venous occlusion, and controllable micro cuffs for scanning plane stabilization.
- The need for new data processing algorithms and user interfaces integrating all data for risk warning and care decisions. Based on signal and image processing algorithms and ML models interfaces adaptable for physicians, nurses, and care providers to be built. It should contain processed and integrated signal and image data from US images and other sensors presented in a condensed ergonomic way.

3.2. Venous occlusion plethysmography

Venous occlusion plethysmography (VOP) is a non-invasive test capable of measuring blood volume changes in the limb of the human body. Multiple variations of VOP tests are available for detecting limb blood volume variations, including strain-gauge plethysmography (SGP), air plethysmography (APG), and electrical impedance plethysmography (EIP). Typical tracings of different VOP measurement techniques are presented in Figure 23.

The VOP test requires a subject to be in a supine position with the legs elevated to around 25-45 degrees to allow venous emptying. A cuff placed on the thigh is pressurized up to 80 mmHg to restrict further venous blood outflow because of the arterial inflow. The blood volume in the calf starts rising and after certain amount reaches a plateau where the blood volume is no longer rising due to the maximum venous capacity. After reaching the plateau, the thigh cuff is released rapidly, and the blood outflow curve is registered. In cases of obstructive vein disease (e.g., deep vein thrombosis), venous outflow is initially slowed, resulting in

a reduction of venous capacity⁹¹. According to Varaki et al.⁹², plethysmographic methods allow the extraction of hemodynamic parameters⁹² of the limbs, such as: venous filling index, ejection fraction, residual volume fraction, and multiple venous blood outflow parameters.

Figure 23. Typical VOP signal tracings by three different plethysmography techniques⁹³.

3.2.1. Strain-gauge plethysmography (SGP)

The SPG method is based on mercury-or gallium-filled flexible tubes surrounding the limb acting as a strain-gauge^{91,92}. Variations in strain-gauge length caused by changes in the limb volume result in changes in the electrical resistance. When combined, various parameters derived from the SGP measurements have an overall sensitivity of 96% to determine venous pathology, without the ability to distinguish between specific disorders, thus leaving it with a diagnostic uncertainty⁹². Moreover, the SGP method is sensitive to temperature and has a chemical hazard, the latter can be reduced when using indium gallium strain gauges⁹². The ideal gauge length is calculated by taking 90% of the limb's circumference, with a 10% stretch when applied⁹¹, this can pose limitations for routine screening due to individual differences.

Another variation of strain-gauge plethysmography - ambulatory strain gauge plethysmography (ASGP) is used to measure calf volume changes in the upright position⁹⁴. Strain gauges are applied to both ankles above the malleolus to avoid artifacts related to calf muscle contraction. According to A. N. Nicolaides the ASGP testing is done in the following way: the usual test exercise includes 20 knee bends at a specific rate of 30 per minute, after which the patient is asked to stand completely still until the full volume return is reached. This return usually lasts between 1-2 minutes for a normal person. This allows the calculation of venous refilling time (RT) and expelled volume (EV). The test is followed by the application of a below-knee compression cuff that is 2.5 cm wide and inflated to a pressure of 70 mmHg. This normalizes the venous return time in patients with isolated superficial venous reflux. Reference values for normal controls are RT of 42 to 96 seconds and EV of 0.7 to 3.1 mL/100 mL. In summary, ASGP measures the performance of the venous muscle pump by assessing venous reflux and expelled volume. While it can help distinguish between superficial and deep venous insufficiency, it does not provide detailed information about the location or

⁹¹ Neumann H.A.M., & Maessen-Visch, M. B. (1999). Plethysmography. *Current problems in dermatology*, 27, 114–123. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000060635>

⁹² Varaki et al. (2018). Peripheral vascular disease assessment in the lower limb: a review of current and emerging non-invasive diagnostic methods. *Biomedical engineering online*, 17(1), 61. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12938-018-0494-4>

⁹³ Anderson F.A. Impedance plethysmography in the diagnosis of arterial and venous disease. *Ann Biomed Eng* 12, 79–102 (1984). <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02410293>

⁹⁴ Nicolaides A. N. Investigation of Chronic Venous Insufficiency. *Circulation*, vol. 102, no. 20, pp. e126–e163, 2000. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.cir.102.20.e126>

extent of reflux or obstruction within the venous system. Duplex scanning with colour flow imaging is necessary for accurate localization and assessment⁹⁴.

3.2.2. Air plethysmography (APG)

The APG relies on an air-filled chamber that encloses the lower limb, and air displacement is used to measure blood volume changes⁹². Venous hypertension arises from impaired venous return, typically caused by one or a combination of factors including venous reflux, obstruction, and inadequate calf muscle pump function. Air plethysmography can measure each of these three components, enhancing the understanding of venous pathophysiology⁹⁴. APG is performed with a 5-liter air chamber encompassing the leg from the ankle to the knee, which is then connected to the pressure sensor reading changes. The pressure change is calibrated with 100 ml of air⁹⁵. According to A. N. Nicolaidis the air-plethysmograph consists of a 35cm-long tubular air chamber made from polyurethane, which surrounds the whole leg and is inflated to a 6mmHg pressure. For venous outflow (obstruction) testing not only an air chamber but also a tourniquet (10-12cm wide) is placed on the thigh as proximally as possible and is inflated to 80 mmHg (Figure 24)⁹⁴. Rapid deflation of the tourniquet allows the recording of a venous outflow signal. According to A. N. Nicolaidis, the outflow fraction at 1 second represents the venous outflow as a percentage of the total venous volume. This measurement is repeated after occluding the long saphenous vein at the knee. Clinically, an outflow fraction at 1 second greater than 38% suggests no significant functional obstruction, a range of 30% to 38% indicates moderate obstruction and values below 28% suggest severe obstruction⁹⁴. In another study by N. Labropoulos et al., APG was found to be 95% sensitive, 95% specific, and 95% accurate in detecting proximal (thigh) DVT. However, the method was found to be 45% sensitive, 95% specific, and 81% accurate for distal (calf) DVT⁹⁶. DVT was confirmed by venography or other gold standard procedures. Despite relatively good results these methods are not widely used and accepted. One of the key factors preventing adoption could be the cumbersome nature of the method and its application while also being operator dependent.

Figure 24. Typical experimental setup of APG test. Outflow fraction (OF) (median and 90% range) without and with occlusion of superficial veins (s) in limbs of 50 normal volunteers (N), 157 limbs with primary varicose veins, 70 limbs with deep venous incompetence (DVI), and 68 limbs with venographic evidence of deep venous occlusion (DVO)⁹⁴.

3.2.3. Electrical Impedance Plethysmography (EIP)

Impedance is an electrical parameter that describes how much an electrical circuit impedes (opposes) alternating current (AC), and it is calculated according to Ohm's law $U = V/I$. In the measurement of human impedance over the skin, the typical measurement setup involves a tetrapolar electrode setup, where two electrodes supply current and two other electrodes detect voltage. The four-electrode circuit will allow the effects of electrode-skin contact to be negligible due to minimal amount of current flowing into the voltage

⁹⁵ Dezotti et al. The clinical importance of air plethysmography in the assessment of chronic venous disease. *J Vasc Bras.* 2016 Oct-Dec;15(4):287-292. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1677-5449.002116>

⁹⁶ Labropoulos et al. Air Plethysmography in the Detection of Suspected Acute Deep Vein Thrombosis. *Phlebology.* 1995;10(1):28-31. <https://doi:10.1177/026835559501000107>

detection circuit. In EIP, the electrical current is both high frequency and low amplitude such that it is imperceptible to humans, and therefore, the method is completely non-invasive and safe.

Different materials have different impedance values according to their capability to conduct current, and blood is a good electrical conductor due to a high amount of ions⁹⁷. EIP measurement is typically used for the measurement of blood flow or volume through arteries. When blood flows through the arterial system and blood volumes increases, into a limb for example, the conductivity increases, and impedance gets lower. As blood leaves the measurement area, the reverse happens. The main impedance changes in a limb during a period of no activity are due to flow of blood because no other large changes in tissue happen that would affect electrical conductivity. Therefore, the impedance measurement in such a setting accurately reflects blood volume change in the limb, $\Delta Z \propto \Delta V$. This relation of impedance value to blood volume is used by venous occlusion plethysmography (VOP) to measure the amount of blood the venous system can hold (venous capacity) as well as the drainage (venous outflow). Both are limited and affected by thrombi occlusion.

3.2.4. Approach and extracted parameters.

The impedance measurement for VOP is based on a similar approach to the other plethysmographic methods. The legs are first raised to drain the venous system. A cuff is inflated to stop the flow of venous, but not arterial blood flow. This causes filling of the venous system in the lower legs, which decreases impedance due to increased conductivity from blood pooling. The cuff is released after set amount of time or when blood pooling saturates, and the outflow is computed together with the capacity. The function of blood outflow to stored blood (venous capacity) is plotted graphically and the diagnosis is based on a determinant line or an index value that is determined experimentally from a population with those two parameters. It is, therefore, an index-based diagnosis.

The two parameters measured from the VOP impedance signal are:

1. Venous capacity (this is the inflow of blood after cuff inflation. It is the difference in impedance value after emptying the veins and the value where impedance is lowest due to inflation of the cuff),
2. Venous outflow at 2 s and 3 s (this is the outflow of blood shortly after the cuff deflation. It is the difference in impedance from the lowest impedance value before deflation to the value 2 or 3 seconds after deflation).

The units for the two values are typically arbitrary impedance units. With assumptions about leg geometry and electrical model⁹⁸, they are also sometimes given as the normalized volume change of the amount of blood to the amount of surrounding tissue (ml/100ml or %) and outflow is sometimes reported as speed (%/min). However, as correct use of these units would require measuring the limb as well as knowledge of the haematocrit of blood, the arbitrary unit is used in most literature. Some systems may have population indices they use to convert the impedance units to volume units by assuming the anatomical dimensions of the measurand.

Although the explained two values are the basis of DVT diagnosis in majority of the EIP VOP literature, some other parameters are also considered. These include flow resistance, outflow time constant, venous tone, arterial inflow, base impedance and others that are derived from the signal. More hemodynamical parameters are available if also the arterial pulse signal is analysed.

⁹⁷ Miklavčič et al. Electric Properties of Tissues. in *Wiley Encyclopedia of Biomedical Engineering*, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2006. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780471740360.ebs0403>

⁹⁸ Jindal et al. Corrected formula for estimating peripheral blood flow by impedance plethysmography. *Med. Biol. Eng. Comput.*, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 625–631, Nov. 1994, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02524237>

The changes in venous capacity and venous outflow in DVT are due to large acute thrombi in popliteal, femoral or iliac veins that obstruct normal pressure/volume relationship in the venous system⁹⁹. This causes especially the outflow to be much slower but also for the capacity to be dampened. Bilateral testing is especially revealing but thrombi can also occlude both legs at the same time though probability of this to happen is low.

The main advantage of the impedance method is the low cost¹⁰⁰ and non-invasiveness as well as its simplicity. It was widely reported in the literature beginning in the 1970s¹⁰¹ to the 1990s¹⁰² but generally replaced by other methods such as compression ultrasound.

3.2.5. EIP implementation details

The implementation details vary in literature though the methodology is commonly the same. The end of the bed is elevated between 25-45° to facilitate the venous emptying by elevating the legs above the heart level. Knees are flexed 10-35° to prevent posterior border of the tibia from compressing the popliteal vein in the knee. The hip is often externally rotated.

The cuff is inflated to a pressure that is between 35 to 80 mmHg. It is inflated from 45 seconds to 3 minutes. In some implementations, it is inflated and deflated in cycles up to five times¹⁰³. Repeating the test increases the venous capacity in subsequent tests. In healthy people the outflow will equally increase, while for those occluded with thrombi the outflow does not increase. In the commercial Medis equipment it is first inflated for 40 mmHg for one minute, followed by one minute of 60 mmHg and finally one minute of 80 mmHg for a total of three minutes before deflation. The cuff is between 15-21 cm in width in the reported values.

Venous capacity is measured as the difference in impedance from the baseline before cuff inflation to the point with lowest impedance during occlusion seen in Figure 23, where the impedance value is inverted. The outflow is typically measured from the peak value to the 3-s point after the deflation of the cuff although other values such as 2-s are also used. The derivative of the downslope is also reported in some research and additionally outflow time constant is calculated in others. The diagnosis is made based on the discriminant line presented in Figure 25. Sometimes, a grey zone is used to indicate results that are ambiguous.

The electrodes used in EIP VOP literature are generally band-type metal electrodes used together with paste to improve conductivity. The electrodes are not always reported and were considered secondary to other methodological concerns. Typically, tetrapolar measurement is used where four electrodes are applied to the calf. The current electrodes are below the knee and near the ankle, while the voltage electrodes are between these with fixed length between them.

The most important parameters regarding the device are the frequency of the current, amplitude of the current and electrodes used as well as electrical details of the circuit. The current is a sinusoidal signal. Higher amplitude has a better signal-to-noise ratio. All studies that reported their amplitude had a safe amplitude as defined by the IEC-60601-1 standard. The frequency has had a high variance with a lower limit of around

⁹⁹ Wheeler et al. Diagnostic Methods for Deep Vein Thrombosis. *Pathophysiology of Haemostasis and Thrombosis*, vol. 25, no. 1–2, pp. 6–26, Apr. 1995, <https://doi.org/10.1159/000217140>

¹⁰⁰ Goodacre et al. Measurement of the clinical and cost-effectiveness of non-invasive diagnostic testing strategies for deep vein thrombosis. *Health Technology Assessment*, vol. 10, no. 15, May 2006, <https://doi.org/10.3310/hta10150>

¹⁰¹ Wheeler et al. Occlusive impedance phlebography: A diagnostic procedure for venous thrombosis and pulmonary embolism. *Progress in Cardiovascular Diseases*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 199–205, Nov. 1974, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-0620\(74\)90044-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-0620(74)90044-9)

¹⁰² Baker W. F. Diagnosis of deep venous thrombosis and pulmonary embolism. *Medical Clinics of North America*, vol. 82, no. 3, pp. 459–476, May 1998, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-7125\(05\)70005-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-7125(05)70005-5)

¹⁰³ Hull et al. Impedance plethysmography: The relationship between venous filling and sensitivity and specificity for proximal vein thrombosis. *Circulation*, vol. 58, no. 5, pp. 898–902, Nov. 1978, <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.CIR.58.5.898>

10 kHz and upper limit of around 100 kHz. The lower limit is likely due to the effects of skin contact impedance at lower frequencies and the higher is due to implementation challenges of the circuit. The circuit injects voltage or current and measures the drop in voltage between the two voltage electrodes and transfer this to impedance value based on the injected current.

Figure 25. Discriminant line examples used for diagnosis of DVT with plethysmographic methods. It is calculated as the best fit when outflow is the function of venous capacity. Above the line are healthy values, while values below the line are those likely to have DVT occlusion. The version on the left includes a “grey zone” with unsure results. The version on the right includes patient data with recent proximal DVT to determine the discriminant line. Images from¹⁰⁷.

3.2.6. Diagnostic accuracy

A meta-analysis with 42 cohorts¹⁰⁴ reported sensitivity and specificity of 88% and 90% for proximal DVT. For distal DVT, the sensitivity was 28%. The report also noted a very high heterogeneity in the results. In another study¹⁰⁵ the sensitivity and specificity of proximal DVT were 77% and 93%. With the exclusion of certain small thrombi, the sensitivity increased to 91%. Applying a clinical model with clinical history to subgroup patients before the EIP result assessment also increased the sensitivity on the same cohort¹⁰⁵. Generally, EIP is considered unreliable in the detection of calf thrombi and also proximal DVT in the case of asymptomatic patients. Other sources share higher values for occlusive proximal DVT in the range of 94% for both sensitivity and specificity¹⁰⁶. The higher values were in the initial literature. The subsequent reporting of lower values was investigated, and it was reported to be possibly due to changes in patient referrals as well as differences in methodology¹⁰⁷. In the case of symptomatic proximal DVT, the sensitivity and accuracy are considered good, but slightly worse than compression ultrasound.

¹⁰⁴ Locker et al. Meta-analysis of plethysmography and rheography in the diagnosis of deep vein thrombosis. *Emerg Med J*, vol. 23, no. 8, pp. 630–635, Aug. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1136/emj.2005.033381>

¹⁰⁵ Wells et al. A simple clinical model for the diagnosis of deep-vein thrombosis combined with impedance plethysmography: Potential for an improvement in the diagnostic process. *Journal of Internal Medicine*, vol. 243, no. 1, pp. 15–23, 1998, <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2796.1998.00249.x>

¹⁰⁶ H. B. Wheeler & F. A. Anderson Impedance Plethysmography. in *Practical Noninvasive Vascular Diagnosis*, 2nd ed. Year Book Medical Publishers, 1987, pp. 407–437. [Online]. Available: https://archive.org/details/practicalnoninva0000unse_w8y2/

¹⁰⁷ M. A. Mansour and D. S. Sumner Overview: Plethysmographic Techniques in the Diagnosis of Venous Disease,” in *Noninvasive Vascular Diagnosis: A Practical Guide to Therapy*, A. F. AbuRahma and J. J. Bergan, Eds., London: Springer, 2007, pp. 375–384. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-84628-450-2_34

3.2.7. Challenges, errors, and limitations

Firstly, the Society for Phlebology has stated in its guidelines on diagnostics that air-cuff plethysmography is not suitable for thrombosis diagnostics¹⁰⁸. According to two decades of data, the EIP remained largely a research test while other methods for DVT detection took over¹⁰⁹. EIP equipment was generally unavailable in hospitals besides those that used it for research^{109,110}. The hospitals that used it mostly used the same devices, and those that used new equipment reported worse results. Those reports were also criticized for their selection bias and differences in methodology¹¹¹. In 2024, the availability of commercial EIP equipment for DVT detection is very limited.

There is a lack of consistency in reporting on the equipment used. Details of electrodes used as well as specifics of the methodology such as the position of the knee and hip and cuff inflation details are not always reported and vary between reports. This causes some rate of error on the true accuracy of the method. In addition, it is also clear that operator experience had some impact as the two main researcher Wheeler¹⁰¹ and Hull¹¹² consistently reported the best results in their clinics. The application of the electrodes and cuff may cause errors. Some patient groups such as pregnant women or those having respiratory difficulties may also need some special considerations with the method¹⁰⁶ causing inexperience of the operator to also lower the accuracy of the method. Wheeler considered the reported results with worse sensitivities to have significant methodological deficiencies, use of nonstandard instrumentation, small sample sizes and problems in retrospective study design⁹⁹. The methodology is simple but differences in the parameters such as the leg elevation cause errors in diagnostic accuracy.

The method is limited to certain types of DVT as well as certain types of patients. Asymptomatic patients generally have a much lower sensitivity due to lack of occlusion with a small thrombus. The outflow is also not always reduced due to, e.g., collateralization of the veins and these cause false negatives. False positives are caused by any other disorder that may cause outflow impairment such as tumor or other external compression. Certain patient groups may also reduce accuracy such as those with obesity, arterial insufficiency, Baker's cyst, calf or thigh hematoma or abscess, inguinal adenopathy, peripheral vasoconstriction and hypovolemia among others¹⁰² and should be considered when using the method.

3.2.8. Future considerations

The EIP method for DVT detection is especially useful for screening certain patient populations due to its non-invasiveness and ease of use. For wearable applications, the electrodes must be designed to be comfortable and non-intrusive to everyday life. Some modern studies exist that employ a cuff-less method by raising the

¹⁰⁸ Dörr D. Die Luftplethysmographie : und ihre Bedeutung für die Diagnostik der chronisch venösen Insuffizienz. Air plethysmography. Doctoral Thesis, 2000. <https://publikationen.ub.uni-frankfurt.de/frontdoor/index/index/year/2005/docId/3928>

¹⁰⁹ Stein *et al.* Tracking the Uptake of Evidence: Two Decades of Hospital Practice Trends for Diagnosing Deep Vein Thrombosis and Pulmonary Embolism. *Archives of Internal Medicine*, vol. 163, no. 10, pp. 1213–1219, May 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1001/archinte.163.10.1213>

¹¹⁰ Wilbur J. & Shian B. Diagnosis of Deep Venous Thrombosis and Pulmonary Embolism. *afp*, vol. 86, no. 10, pp. 913–919, Nov. 2012, Accessed: May 31, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.aafp.org/pubs/afp/issues/2012/1115/p913.html>

¹¹¹ Akers *et al.* Impedance plethysmography. It's the clinical outcome that counts. *Chest*, vol. 106, no. 5, pp. 1317–1318, Nov. 1994, <https://doi.org/10.1378/chest.106.5.1317>

¹¹² Hull *et al.* Impedance plethysmography using the occlusive cuff technique in the diagnosis of venous thrombosis. *Circulation*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 696–700, Apr. 1976, <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.CIR.53.4.696>

leg instead^{113,114}. A method before the occlusion method employed high respiratory effort using the Valsalva maneuver¹¹⁵. Both methods are untested on larger patient populations and could have possible use. Especially with modern microprocessing tools, the respiratory efforts from the impedance signal are easier to analyze, and even passive respiratory effects may be considered with signal processing tools.

Similarly, the simple discriminant line was used mostly due to ease of calculation. Machine learning may be employed for better use of parameters and patient information¹¹⁶. The signal waveform morphology is also not used in the old literature, and it may be used for further information either together with the occlusion method or without it for information about the venous and arterial system^{117,118}. Harmonic analysis, spectral analysis, and unilateral changes to wave morphology are largely unexplored possibilities. Continuous monitoring of the base impedance may also reveal especially the onset of edema relevant to DVT. The already clinically validated method can therefore be complemented with modern approaches to signal processing.

3.2.9. Commercially available VOP systems

The modular system combining VasoScreen4000 and VasoScreen5000 (medis Medizinische Messtechnik GmbH, Germany) is designed for arterial and venous vascular diagnosis (

Figure 26a). Together with “Cardiovascular Lab” software it provides 7 main parameters (based on EIP)¹¹⁹: Base impedance (Ω), Arterial inflow (%/min), Venous capacity (%), Venous outflow at 2s rate (%/min), Outflow volume at 3s (%), Outflow volume at 5s (%), Outflow time constant (s). Additionally, it provides LRR and arterial occlusion plethysmography measurement capabilities.

The AngE-System (SOT Medical Systems, Austria) is conceived as a modular solution for vascular and cardiovascular diagnostics, too (

Figure 26b). The AngE-Complete is a vascular diagnostics lab capable of performing VOP tests¹²⁰. The sensing is performed using an air cuff, and a total of 7 parameters are provided (based on APG): Venous capacity (ml/100ml), Venous outflow (ml/100ml/min), OV1 (ml/100ml) (OF 1%), OV2 (ml/100ml) (OF 2%), OV3 (ml/100ml) (OF 3%), OV4 (ml/100ml) (OF 4%), Arterial flow (ml/100ml/min).

¹¹³ Pittella et al. Combined impedance plethysmography and spectroscopy for the diagnosis of diseases of peripheral vascular system. in *2017 IEEE International Symposium on Medical Measurements and Applications (MeMeA)*, May 2017, pp. 367–372. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MeMeA.2017.7985904>

¹¹⁴ Uday et al. Design and Development of an EIP System Without an Occlusive Cuff to Detect Deep Vein Thrombosis. presented at the Second International Conference on Emerging Trends in Engineering (ICETE 2023), Atlantis Press, Nov. 2023, pp. 26–35, https://doi.org/10.2991/978-94-6463-252-1_5

¹¹⁵ Wheeler et al. Impedance Phlebography: Technique, Interpretation, and Results. *Archives of Surgery*, vol. 104, no. 2, pp. 164–169, Feb. 1972, <https://doi.org/10.1001/archsurg.1972.04180020044008>

¹¹⁶ Tumey D. M. & Randolph L. T. Apparatus and method for detecting deep vein thrombosis. 5991654A, Nov. 23, 1999 Accessed: Jun. 11, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US5991654A/en>

¹¹⁷ De Macedo et al. A novel model to simulate venous occlusion plethysmography data and to estimate arterial and venous parameters. *Res. Biomed. Eng.*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 463–473, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42600-020-00087-3>

¹¹⁸ Bejarano Monroy M. G. A novel approach to bioelectrical impedance plethysmography for the assessment of arterial and venous circulatory problems in the forearm. doctoral, City, University of London, 2019. Accessed: Jan. 25, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://openaccess.city.ac.uk/id/eprint/24064/>

¹¹⁹ VasoScreen 5000 - 4000. [Online]. Available: <https://www.medis.com/en/products/vasoscreen-5000-4000>

¹²⁰ AngETM COMPLETE. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sot-medical.com/solution/ange-complete/>

Figure 26. Commercially available VOP systems. (a) VasoScreen4000-5000 (medis GmbH, Germany), and (b) AngE-System (SOT Medical Systems, Austria).

3.2.10. Summary of knowledge gaps and potential solutions with implications for requirements

- Although plethysmographic methods have existed for decades, there is a lack of studies with large sample sizes that provide results on different types of thrombosis and use cases.
- There is a lack of consistency in reporting on the equipment and methodology used. Details of electrodes used and specifics of the methodology such as the patient’s leg position and cuff inflation details are not always reported and vary between reports. This causes differences between studies and the true diagnostic accuracy is hard to determine.
- Among the plethysmographic methods presented, EIP appears to be the most user-friendly and comfortable due to its non-invasiveness, simplicity, and ease of use. The APG method requires an air bladder, and SGP relies on mercury- or gallium-filled flexible tubes, making these methods cumbersome and less reliable compared to the EIP method. It should be noted that for continuous or frequent EIP testing, textile electrodes should be used instead of typical Ag/AgCl gel-based electrodes to ensure comfort and minimize disruption to everyday life.

3.3. Light reflection rheography (LRR) and photoplethysmography (PPG)

The search engine PubMed found 31 sources for the following query (DBQ-03-2024): (DVT OR “deep vein thrombosis”) AND (LRR OR “light reflection rheography” OR photoplethysmography). Of these, 29 sources appeared relevant to the project.

3.3.1. Background

Photoplethysmography (PPG) is a non-invasive optical technique used to measure heart rate, blood oxygen levels, and other cardiovascular parameters by detecting blood volume changes in tissue. It works on the principle that blood absorbs light. A light source (LED) emits light into the skin, and a photodetector (PD) measures the reflected or transmitted light. As the heart pumps blood, changes in capillary blood volume affect light absorption, generating a PPG signal. This signal has two main components: the alternating component (AC), which reflects pulsatile blood flow corresponding to each heartbeat, and the DC component, which represents the baseline blood volume (venous blood) and remains relatively stable over time (Figure 27).

Figure 27. PPG signal components¹²¹.

Light Reflection Rheography (LRR), sometimes referred to as Digital Photoplethysmography (D-PPG, digital vs. analog version of LRR), is a specialized mode of PPG that captures low-frequency (<0.5 Hz) variations in blood volume. It was hypothesized^{122,123} that this mode is suitable for detecting DVT as it primarily detects changes in venous blood volume using LRR sensors positioned on both lower legs. Blood flow in the peripheral venous system can be recorded quickly and easily.

3.3.2. Approach

LRR measurements are taken from a selected skin area by emitting non-visible infrared (IR, ~940 nm) light into the skin. Depending on the blood volume in that area, the light is absorbed, and the proportion of reflected light corresponds inversely to the blood volume. The light intensity of the sensors can automatically adapt to the conditions at the measurement location, making LRR measurements possible regardless of skin colour and even through targeted textiles. The measurement should be performed in a well-tempered room (20-24°C) and after a rest period of at least several minutes before the start of the examination is recommended.

LRR examination for DVT uses venous blood flow changes and observes changes in LRR signals. Several methods are used to induce venous blood flow changes: 1) passive execution of postural movements of the limbs in supine position, 2) foot pumping in sitting position, i.e., the patient performs the dorsiflexion at the ankle to push the blood in the vein of the calf back to the heart, 3) VOP technique used in venous occlusion plethysmography similar to EIP case.

3.3.3. Implementation details and extracted parameters

The LRR probe is usually placed on the calf 10 cm from the internal malleolus¹²⁴ over the long saphenous vein near the ankle. LRR signals represent DC trend variation due to three protocol phases of the examination: 1) resting baseline, 2) venous emptying manoeuvre, and 3) refilling phase. As mentioned above, there are three types of venous emptying maneuvers or tests. LRR measurement takes about 2 minutes to perform.

¹²¹ Photoplethysmography Textbook. [Online]. Available: https://peterhcharlton.github.io/post/ppg_book/

¹²² Pearce et al. Hemodynamic Assessment of Venous Problems. Surgery vol. 93,5 (1983): 715-21.

¹²³ Shepard et al. Light reflection rheography: A new non-invasive test of venous function. Bruit 1984, 8, 266–270. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0196-0644\(05\)82516-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0196-0644(05)82516-8)

¹²⁴ Antignani et al. Light-reflection rheography and acute deep vein thrombosis. Angiology vol. 44,7 (1993): 523-6. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000331979304400703>

In the “passive postural movements of the limb’s” test, the limbs are heightened individually. Figure 28 shows characteristic patterns of LRR signal.

Figure 28. Illustrations of LRR in health and pathology¹²⁴: (a) a normal subject, (b) iliofemoral thrombosis, (c) severe iliofemoral thrombosis, and (d) thrombosis of the vena cava and iliac veins.

In the “foot pumping” test, the patient should sit comfortably on a chair with the foot resting flat on the floor, and the angle between the calf and thigh should be approximately 110 degrees. This angle prevents the restriction of venous blood flow in the popliteal vein and the saphenous-popliteal junction. Visual or audio guidance is provided to the patient when the foot needs to be raised and lowered, involving movement at the ankle joint (Figure 29). This action activates the calf pump, allowing blood to be pumped out of the vein. After 8-10 beeps, the leg is kept stationary, and the device measures how long it takes for the vein to refill. Motion sensors, such as accelerometers¹²⁵, can help automatically track the voluntary movement of the foot. The study¹²⁶ proposed a robot for passive ankle movement to activate the calf pump (Figure 29).

Figure 29. Monitoring and control of the foot in foot pumping mode: by accelerometer (left and middle¹²⁵), robot-based foot movement (right¹²⁶).

There are clear differences among LRR signal patterns and venous system states as registered by foot pumping test (Figure 30).

¹²⁵ Liu et al. An Examination System to Detect Deep Vein Thrombosis of a Lower Limb Using Light Reflection Rheography. *Sensors* 21, no. 7 (2 April 2021): 2446. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21072446>

¹²⁶ Wnuk et al. Effect of passive ankle movement in the sitting position on the symptoms of chronic venous insufficiency with long-term observation. *Advances in clinical and experimental medicine: official organ Wroclaw Medical University* vol. 33,2 (2024): 135-141. <https://doi.org/10.17219/acem/166046>

Figure 30. Different LRR patterns in venous pumping test¹²⁷: (a) no occlusion, (b) partial occlusion, (c) full occlusion.

Liu et al.¹²⁵ developed foot pumping-based device and extracted 6 characteristic parameters from LRR signal: the difference between end of pumping and resting / refilling baselines VP parameters, and four slope-based parameters m representing different time intervals at 10, 40, 50, and 60s of blood refilling (Figure 31).

In venous occlusion test, a similar procedure as described in Section 3.3 is used. One of the papers describes this test in the following way: the limbs of the patient were lightly flexed and raised from the plane of the bed at a 15° angle with a pneumatic cuff at the thigh that was insufflated at various pressures (20, 40, 60 mmHg) for a period of one minute and then deflated quickly¹²⁴. However, except this relatively old paper from 1993, there are no research papers found using LRR in VOP mode.

Figure 31. Parameter extraction from LRR signal¹²⁷.

Different studies report different thresholds for diagnosis of DVT. Studies^{128,129} found similar cut-off point to discriminate DVT refilling time parameters <22s and <21s respectively as the optimal. Other studies classified degrees of calf pump insufficiency concerning to venous refilling time into 4 classes: healthy > 25s, stage I - 20-25s, stage II - 10-19s, stage III <10s. However, a longitudinal study¹³⁰ of young volunteers with healthy veins, observed over two decades, has shown an increase in refilling time in healthy subjects. The study found the following thresholds: 24 seconds in the 10-12 years age group, 29.5 seconds in the 14-16 years age group, 48.5 seconds in the 18-20 years age group, and over 45 seconds in the 29-31 years age group. Venous

¹²⁷ Liu et al Convolutional Neural Network-Based Detection of Deep Vein Thrombosis in a Low Limb with Light Reflection Rheography'. Measurement 189 (15 February 2022): 110457. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2021.110457>

¹²⁸ Sharif-Kashani et al Comparing Results of Digital Photoplethysmography in Two Groups of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease Patients with and without High Pulmonary Artery Pressure. Phlebology 23, no. 3 (2008): 125–29. <https://doi.org/10.1258/phleb.2008.007084>

¹²⁹ Tan Y. K & da Silva A. F. Digital photoplethysmography in the diagnosis of suspected lower limb DVT: is it useful?. Eur J Vasc Endovasc Surg. 1999;18(1):71-79. <https://doi.org/10.1053/ejvs.1999.0886>

¹³⁰ Stücker et al. Changes in venous refilling time from childhood to adulthood in subjects with apparently normal veins. J Vasc Surg. 2005;41(2):296-302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvs.2004.11.023>

hemodynamics appear to be influenced by growth and maturation during adolescence and should not be confused with venous insufficiency. Therefore, venous refill time determined by active dorsal extensions is unsuitable for diagnosing vein function in children and adolescents and should be replaced with the passive elevation test in these age groups.

3.3.4. Diagnostic accuracy

There are several studies that have examined the feasibility of assessing venous hemodynamic and detection of DVT by using PPG or LRR and providing accuracy values^{122,123,131,132}.

Mitrani et al.¹³² studied 72 patients using LRR and contrast venography. Of the 24 patients with DVT confirmed by venography, 23 were also detected by LRR. Among the 45 patients with no thrombus on venography, 35 had normal venous emptying on LRR. Therefore, LRR demonstrated a sensitivity of 96% and 78% specificity, comparable to other non-invasive tests.

Antignani¹³³ examined 47 subjects affected by acute phlebothrombosis of the lower limbs by means of LRR. Clinical Doppler and duplex scanner evaluations were used for reference diagnosis. The results were compared with a control group of 30 healthy subjects. The agreement with the clinical, instrumental, and echographic Doppler findings was 100%.

Thomas et al.¹³⁴ found that LRR has a sensitivity of 92% and a specificity of 84% in detecting acute thrombosis of the calf. This technique has a negative predictive value of 92% in selecting those patients with no thrombosis.

Sharif-Kashani et al.¹²⁸ investigated whether high pulmonary artery pressure (PAP) could act as a confounding factor in LRR/D-PPG testing results. They examined 45 patients with PAP and 45 without and found no statistically significant difference between the groups, concluding that PAP is not a confounder when using the LRR method for DVT detection. Studies investigating possible confounding factors are important for increasing trust in the LRR method.

Smith et al.¹³⁵ reported a five-and-a-half-year, single-centre experience on the diagnostic value of LRR for screening DVT. During the study period, 3,342 limbs were assessed with LRR in 3,105 patients referred with suspected DVT, including both inpatients and outpatients. The results showed a negative predictive value of 97.8% and a sensitivity of 96.4%, with a three-month post-test thromboembolism incidence of 0.9%. The use of LRR allowed duplex scanning to be avoided in 22.2% of referrals.

Although the studies mentioned above found satisfactory accuracy for plethysmography and the LRR technique, a meta-analysis¹³⁶ concluded that, while plethysmography and rheography techniques add diagnostic value, their diagnostic performance is inadequate for them to serve as stand-alone tests in DVT

¹³¹ Lindner et al. Long-Term Hemodynamic and Clinical Sequelae of Lower Extremity Deep Vein Thrombosis. *Journal of Vascular Surgery* 4, no. 5 (November 1986): 436–42.

¹³² Mitrani et al. Detection of Clinically Suspected Deep Vein Thrombosis Using Light Reflection Rheography. *American Journal of Surgery* 161, no. 6 (June 1991): 646–50. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9610\(91\)91248-h](https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9610(91)91248-h)

¹³³ Antignani et al. Light-Reflection Rheography and Acute Deep Vein Thrombosis. *Angiology* 44, no. 7 (July 1993): 523–26. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000331979304400703>

¹³⁴ Thomas et al. Light reflection rheography: An effective non-invasive technique for screening patients with suspected deep venous thrombosis. *Br. J. Surg.* 1991, 78, 207–209. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bjs.1800780225>

¹³⁵ Smith et al. The Diagnostic Value of Light Reflection Rheology for Suspected Deep Vein Thrombosis: A Five-and-a-Half Year Single Centre Experience. *Phlebology* 22, no. 3 (2007): 105–9. <https://doi.org/10.1258/026835507780807239>

¹³⁶ Locker et al. Meta-analysis of plethysmography and rheography in the diagnosis of deep vein thrombosis. *Emergency medicine journal: EMJ* vol. 23,8 (2006): 630-5. <https://doi.org/10.1136/emj.2005.033381>

diagnosis. Evaluation of their role in combination with other tests or standardized clinical assessments is required.

3.3.5. Challenges, errors, and limitations

The biggest difference between LRR and EIP approaches is sensitivity to different volumes of tissue. LRR is a local method. Studies have shown that NIR radiation can penetrate up to 4 mm into the skin¹³⁷. Therefore, it should be considered as indirectly reflecting the dynamics of deep venous flow. Liu et al.¹²⁵ noticed phase inversion of the signal due to inappropriate positioning of the sensor. Therefore, the physician must look for an appropriate position for placing the LRR sensor to obtain a reliable signal. The LRR sensor should not be placed directly on a varicose vein. The LRR signal profile depends on the location of the thrombus; therefore, interpreting the signal profile can be challenging. In addition, venous refilling time varies with the patient's age and has a broad distribution of normal values. Consequently, the diagnostic thresholds for abnormality are quite individual.

Repeatability of LRR measurements is important. The repeatability of venous function test (VFT) measurements, expressed as the intraclass coefficient (ICC) after three measurements, showed that the LRR method had fair to good repeatability¹³⁸. However, the pump test presents significant variability in the rhythm and speed of the foot dorsal flexions and cannot be performed on unconscious subjects and those with reduced mobility.

3.3.6. Future considerations

One way to improve LRR signal quality is by integrating an array of sensors and appropriate signal processing algorithms to obtain higher-quality LRR signals. Subsequently, rules for determining the quality of the LRR signals should be established.

Functional electrical or mechanical stimulation of the calf muscle can be used to generate rhythmic and reproducible muscle contractions. Studies have shown¹³⁹ that peroneal nerve stimulation can be as efficient as foot pumping when the stimulation current reaches 40 mA and 5 Hz. However, patient discomfort was rated at 4 (moderate) out of 5 (severe). Patient discomfort could be reduced by optimizing the parameters of the stimulator or by switching to a mechanical stimulator.

3.3.7. Commercially available LRR systems

Market Research Intellect Inc. expects rapid growth in the clinical photoplethysmographs market in the coming years, as detailed in its report, "Photoplethysmographs Market 2023"¹⁴⁰. A few examples of commercial devices are listed below:

¹³⁷ Jian-Chiun L. & Zhen-Yu Y. (2021). Integrated infrared image system within accurate detection. 2021 IEEE International Conference on Consumer Electronics-Taiwan (ICCE-TW), 1-2. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCE-TW52618.2021.9603040>

¹³⁸ Varaki et al. Arterial and venous peripheral vascular assessment using wearable electro-resistive morphic sensors." Scientific reports vol. 14,1 1327. 15 Jan. 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-50534-1>

¹³⁹ Tucker et al. Augmentation of Venous, Arterial and Microvascular Blood Supply in the Leg by Isometric Neuromuscular Stimulation via the Peroneal Nerve. The International Journal of Angiology: Official Publication of the International College of Angiology, Inc 19, no. 1 (Spring 2010): e31-37. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0031-1278361>

¹⁴⁰ Global Photoplethysmographs Market Overview. [Online]. Available: <https://www.marketresearchintellect.com/product/global-photoplethysmographs-market-size-and-forecast/>

- medis Medizinische Messtechnik GmbH (Germany) markets the devices¹⁴¹ VasoScreen 5000, VenoSreen, and VenoSreen plus, which include LRR measurement. There are research publications using these devices¹⁴².
- ELCAT GmbH (Germany) markets vasolab[®] 320 system¹⁴³. It is a modular device comprising D-PPG/LRR, strain gauge-based VOP, and Doppler ultrasound. There are 44 research publications related to venous thrombosis, and using this device¹⁴⁴.
- Huntleigh Diagnostics Ltd. (Cardiff, U.K.) produces Rheo Dopplex[®] II. This device has been investigated and found effective in screening patients for the absence of a DVT in the lower limb¹⁴⁵. The device was used in venous flow research studies related to general elderly¹⁴⁶ and sports professionals¹⁴⁷ populations.
- Hemodynamics Inc. (Boca Raton, Florida) produces an A-V 1000 system. There are 31 research publications related to venous thrombosis, and using this device¹⁴⁸.

3.3.8. Summary of knowledge gaps and potential solutions with implications for requirements

- To increase the accuracy of DVT detection, the PPG/LRR sensor must discriminate between venous, arterial, and capillary blood. An integrated multi-wavelength PPG/LRR sensor, combining infrared (940 nm), red (660 nm), green (530 nm), and blue (460 nm) LEDs, is a promising technology for registering both deep and shallow fluctuations in blood volume, potentially allowing this discrimination. Integrated packages, including electronic front-end and optical components, are available from the industry, facilitating the integration of the sensor into a wearable ThrombUS+ device. A reliable monitoring of arterial and venous blood volume fluctuations requires at least a 100Hz sampling rate.
- The implementation of LRR/PPG-based DVT detection protocols requires knowledge of limb position and orientation. Sensor fusion of LRR/PPG with inertial measurement units (IMUs) enables real-time monitoring of all limb segments (thigh, calf, foot) for both static orientations and dynamic movements. Miniaturized integrated IMU packages, including an accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer, and sensor fusion algorithms, are available from the industry. A reliable monitoring of dynamic movements requires a 50Hz movement data acquisition rate.
- PPG/LRR signals are susceptible to movement artifacts, breathing, and Traube–Hering–Mayer waves. A distributed multisensory configuration and array processing may potentially help mitigate these confounding factors in DVT detection. Therefore, it is recommended to use an integrated PPG/LRR/IMU sensor for each segment (thigh, calf, foot) of the leg.

¹⁴¹ Light-Reflection-Rheography (LRR) [Online]. Available: <https://www.medis.company/en/methods/light-reflection-rheography>

¹⁴² Varaki et al. Arterial and venous peripheral vascular assessment using wearable electro-resistive morphic sensors. Scientific reports vol. 14,1 1327. 15 Jan. 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-50534-1>

¹⁴³ Vasolab 320. [Online]. Available: <https://www.elcat.de/produkte-gefaessdiagnostik/plethysmograph/vasolab-320-gefaessdiagnostik-center/>

¹⁴⁴ Google Scholar. [Online]. Available: https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=%22ELCAT+GmbH%22++AND+thrombosis&btnG=

¹⁴⁵ Tan et al. Digital Photoplethysmography in the Diagnosis of Suspected Lower Limb DVT: Is It Useful?. Eur J Vasc Endovasc Surg, 1999.

¹⁴⁶ Skomudek et al. Analysis of the dynamics of venous blood flow in the context of lower limb temperature distribution and tissue composition in the elderly. Clinical interventions in aging vol. 12 1371-1378. 28 Aug. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.2147/CIA.S137707>

¹⁴⁷ Sophromadze et al. Lower extremity vein digital photoplethysmography in highly qualified football players and wrestlers. Georgian medical news, 133 (2006): 72-4.

¹⁴⁸ Google Scholar. [Online]. Available: https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=%22A-V+1000%22+AND+%22venous+thrombosis%22&btnG=

- The integrated PPG/LRR/IMU DVT monitoring subsystem requires signal processing and analysis algorithms, including: 1) a signal quality estimation algorithm, 2) signal processing to minimize confounding factors, 3) signal feature extraction (feature engineering), 4) feature selection, and 5) training a machine learning model for classification using data acquired from synthesized thrombus and data obtained from pilot preclinical studies.
- Investigational studies and data collection are necessary to define the optimal patient and sensor positioning during various tests for DVT detection: 1) passive postural movements of the limbs with the help of a medic, 2) foot pumping, and 3) the VOP technique used in venous occlusion plethysmography. Additionally, a passive, operator-independent DVT monitoring method using venous blood flow modulation at the calf through either mechanical or electrical stimulation could be investigated.

3.4. Other promising DVT diagnostic methods and technologies

3.4.1. Muscle stiffness assessment

The clinical presentation of acute lower extremity DVT is influenced by the anatomic distribution, extent, and degree of occlusion of the thrombus. Symptoms may vary from absence to massive swelling and cyanosis with venous gangrene. Three types of thrombosis are commonly recognized: isolated calf vein (distal), femoropopliteal, and iliofemoral thrombosis, and symptoms tend to be more severe as thrombosis extends more proximally. However, up to 50% of patients with acute DVT may not have specific signs or symptoms. Postoperative patients are more likely to possess small, asymptomatic, distal, non-occlusive thrombi. Signs and symptoms of acute lower extremity DVT may include pain, edema/swelling, erythema, tenderness, fever, prominent superficial veins, pain with passive dorsiflexion of the foot, and peripheral cyanosis¹⁴⁹. Obtaining the diagnosis of DVT only based on clinical signs and symptoms is highly inaccurate. The signs and symptoms of DVT are usually not specific. They may be associated with other lower extremity disorders. However, the most common presenting symptoms lacking sensitivity and specificity are calf pain and swelling. The former index has a sensitivity of 75% to 91% and a specificity of 3% to 87%, and the latter might have a sensitivity of up to 97% and a specificity of up to 88%¹⁵⁰. No one of the signs or symptoms is sufficiently sensitive or specific, either alone or in combination, to accurately diagnose or eliminate thrombosis.

Venous stasis in the affected limb due to DVT could cause a change in muscle stiffness¹⁵¹. Methods for assessing muscle stiffness will be discussed here as a possible additional source of information for DVT monitoring. There are several muscle stiffness assessments methods described in the research literature. MRI elastography is used to evaluate tissue stiffness in diverse organs such as liver, breast, muscle, kidney, and spleen. It has been proven to be highly sensitive (but most expensive) for various clinical applications, particularly in the detection of liver fibrosis¹⁵². MRI elastography was tried to identify acute, sub-acute and

¹⁴⁹ Mazzolai et al. Diagnosis and management of acute deep vein thrombosis: a joint consensus document from the European Society of Cardiology working groups of aorta and peripheral vascular diseases and pulmonary circulation and right ventricular function, *European Heart Journal*, Volume 39, Issue 47, 14 December 2018, Pages 4208–4218, <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehx003>

¹⁵⁰ Min et al. Diagnosis and Treatment of Lower Extremity Deep Vein Thrombosis: Korean Practice Guidelines. *Vasc Specialist Int*. 2016 Sep;32(3):77-104. <https://doi.org/10.5758/vsi.2016.32.3.77>

¹⁵¹ Kang et al. Classification of deep vein thrombosis stages using convolutional neural network of electromyogram with vibrotactile stimulation toward developing an early diagnostic tool: A preliminary study on a pig model. *PLoS ONE*18(2): e0281219. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0281219>

¹⁵² Akkaya et al. Magnetic resonance elastography: basic principles, technique, and clinical applications in the liver. *Diagn Interv Radiol*. 2018 Nov;24(6):328-335. <https://doi.org/10.5152/dir.2018.18186>

chronic thrombi using endogenous contrast agents and to provide objective standardisation of the diagnostic process¹⁵³.

Figure 32. Ultrasound elastography techniques ¹⁵⁴.

Ultrasound (US) elastography provides complementary information to conventional US by adding stiffness as another measurable property to current US imaging techniques¹⁵⁴. The are two main physical principles used in US elastography: strain imaging and shear wave imaging (Figure 32). US elastography is tried to be used for age assessment of deep vein thrombosis¹⁵⁵ and demonstrated an increase in thrombus stiffness according to DVT age. Strain elastography uses deformation induced by manually compressing the transducer against the tissue of interest and measuring the displacement (Figure 33). Tissue stiffness can be visually represented using measurements of this relative displacements. This technique has several major limitations, including that it requires fine control of the stress applied to the tissue and cannot easily provide quantitative data. Moreover, the stress applied is entirely operator-dependent, leading to low reproducibility. Shear wave elastography does not require compression of tissues, but specialized transducers are required for shear wave generation.

Evoked response of the muscle to the mechanical impulse or vibration (myotonometry) can be measured by accelerometer^{156,157}. The device used in this study is developed by Myoton AS, Estonia¹⁵⁸ and is widely used in superficial muscle and soft tissues condition assessment studies in medicine and sports (Figure 34).

¹⁵³ Dharmarajah et al. Aging techniques for deep vein thrombosis: a systematic review. *Phlebology*. 2015;30(2):77-84. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0268355514528691>

¹⁵⁴ Sigrist et al. Ultrasound Elastography: Review of Techniques and Clinical Applications. *Theranostics*. 2017 Mar 7;7(5):1303-1329. <https://doi.org/10.7150/thno.18650>

¹⁵⁵ Santini et al. Ultrasound Elastography to Assess Age of Deep Vein Thrombosis: A Systematic Review. *Diagnostics* 2023, 13, 2075. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics13122075>

¹⁵⁶ Viir et al Trapezius muscle tone and viscoelastic properties in sitting and supine positions. *Scandinavian Journal of Work, Environment & Health*. 2007; 33(3):76.

¹⁵⁷ M. Veldi et al. Myotonometry demonstrates changes in lingual musculature in obstructive sleep apnoea *Eur. Arch. Otorhinolaryngol.*, 259 (2002), pp. 108-112. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s004050100411>

¹⁵⁸ Digital Palpation. [Online]. Available: <https://www.myoton.com/>

Figure 33. Color-coded elastogram, with stiff tissue areas coloured red, intermediate tissue areas coloured green, and soft tissue areas coloured blue¹⁵⁹

Figure 34. Myoton digital palpation device for soft tissue assessment^{160,161}

The Evoked response of the muscle to the mechanical impulse or vibration can be measured as well by electromyography (EMG)^{162,163}. Kang JW et al used this method to classify DVT stages using CNN of EMG with vibrotactile stimulation on a pig model (Figure 35). They achieved the total average classification accuracy before and after DVT stages of $72.0 \pm 11.9\%$.

¹⁵⁹ Mumoli et al. Ultrasound elastography is useful to distinguish acute and chronic deep vein thrombosis.” Journal of thrombosis and haemostasis: JTH vol. 16,12 (2018): 2482-2491. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jth.14297>

¹⁶⁰ Agoriwo, Mary W et al. “Feasibility and reliability of measuring muscle stiffness in Parkinson's Disease using MyotonPRO device in a clinical setting in Ghana.” Ghana medical journal vol. 56,2 (2022): 78-85. doi:10.4314/gmj.v56i2.4

¹⁶¹ Myoton digital palpation device <https://www.myoton.com/>

¹⁶² Ritzmann et al. EMG activity during whole body vibration: motion artifacts or stretch reflexes? European journal of applied physiology. 2010; 110(1):143–51. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-010-1483-x>

¹⁶³ Barnes W. S. & Williams J. H. Effects of ischemia on myo-electrical signal characteristics during rest and recovery from static work. Am J Phys Med. 1987; 66(5):249–63. PMID: 3434627

Figure 35. The EMG sensor and vibration motor on a pig model of DVT¹⁶⁴

Finally, in Tensiomyography¹⁶⁵, the evoked response to the electrical stimulation of the muscle is measured by displacement sensor (Figure 36).

Figure 36. Tensiomyography principle^{166,167}

Mechanomyography (MMG) is a technique, enabling registration of the radial displacement of a muscle during a contraction¹⁶⁸. Using alone or with neuromuscular electrical stimulation (NMES), MMG is used as an alternative to EMG signal for the monitoring of muscle function, in terms of fatigue, muscle force, and its derivative (torque) as well as for prosthesis control and the detection of myopathies. Sensors used for MMG

¹⁶⁴ Kang et al. Classification of deep vein thrombosis stages using convolutional neural network of electromyogram with vibrotactile stimulation toward developing an early diagnostic tool: A preliminary study on a pig model. PLoS ONE 18(2). 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0281219>

¹⁶⁵ Tensiomyography. Quantifying muscle function. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tensiomyography.net/>

¹⁶⁶ <https://www.tensiomyography.net/>

¹⁶⁷ Wilson, Hannah V et al. "Repeated stimulation, inter-stimulus interval and inter-electrode distance alters muscle contractile properties as measured by Tensiomyography." PloS one vol. 13,2 e0191965. 16 Feb. 2018, doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0191965

¹⁶⁸ Uwamahoro et al. Assessment of muscle activity using electrical stimulation and mechanomyography: a systematic review. BioMed Eng OnLine 20, 1 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12938-020-00840-w>

signal acquisitions are based on piezoelectrics, microphones, accelerometers or capacitive displacements sensors¹⁶⁹ (Figure 37).

Figure 37. Surface MMG sensors and their signals compared to EMG^{170,171}

3.4.2. Summary of Knowledge Gaps and Potential Solutions with Implications for Requirements

- The most common symptoms of DVT, though lacking sensitivity and specificity, are calf pain and swelling. While these symptoms are nonspecific, they are associated with changes in muscle stiffness, which may provide additional information for monitoring DVT.
- Tissue stiffness can be assessed actively (with external stimulation causing muscle movement or compression) or passively. Feasible methods within the scope of the project include ultrasonography or analyzing mechanical muscle response through EMG or mechanical sensors.
- Ultrasound, a commonly used technology for DVT assessment, offers two elastography methods: (a) strain elastography, which analyses tissue displacement in response to compression provided by the operator, and (b) shear wave elastography, which uses specialized transducers. Both methods require further development: operator-independent solutions for strain elastography and specialized transducers for shear wave elastography.
- Recording the evoked mechanical response after stimulation, which causes muscle movement, measures muscle properties as a purely mechanical system. This is highly correlated with an individual's body composition. These methods are related to the PPG/LRR/IMU applications (analysis of responses from these modalities to stimuli for DVT detection) and can be further explored for adding additional data to DVT monitoring.

4. Actuators for tissue compression and US transducer positioning

Tissue compression actuator (TCA) will serve three purposes: (1) it will aid in the detection of thrombus via automatic, operator-independent compression ultrasonography (CUS), (2) it will be used in the venous

¹⁶⁹ Scarborough et al. Quantifying muscle contraction with a conductive electroactive polymer sensor: introduction to a novel surface mechanomyography device. *International Biomechanics*, 10(1), 37–46. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23335432.2024.2319068>

¹⁷⁰ Scarborough, D. M. et al. 'Quantifying muscle contraction with a conductive electroactive polymer sensor: introduction to a novel surface mechanomyography device', *International Biomechanics*, 10(1), pp. 37–46, (2023). doi: 10.1080/23335432.2024.2319068.

¹⁷¹ <https://www.figur8tech.com>

occlusion plethysmography (VOP) method, as described in Chapters 3.2 and 3.3., and (3) it will be capable of automatically steering the US transducer along the vein during prolonged clinical monitoring.

4.1. Background

In 1982, technologist Steve Talbot discovered that it was possible to distinguish between normal veins and those containing clots by using a combination of pulsed Doppler and real-time B-mode ultrasonography¹⁷². He found that an obstructed vein would not change in diameter during respiration (Valsalva maneuver) or when light pressure was applied to the skin. Today, CUS is the primary imaging technique for diagnosing DVT in routine clinical practice. The standard CUS procedure utilizes a 5- to 10-MHz linear probe, and the examination is performed using compression, interpreted according to established methods¹⁷³. Venous duplex ultrasound (VDUS), incorporating B-mode compression maneuvers and Doppler evaluation, has been shown to provide additional diagnostic value^{174, 175, 176}. Colour-flow Doppler helps detect residual flow within a thrombosed venous segment (i.e., non-occlusive DVT) and in confirming the patency of venous segments that cannot be accessed by compression maneuvers (e.g., the ilio caval veins). Along with assessing respirophasicity, distal augmentation maneuvers, such as calf compression, are performed during spectral Doppler evaluation to further confirm venous patency. A sharp "spike" of augmented antero grade venous flow should be observed during the distal augmentation maneuver. Blunted or absent flow augmentation suggests venous obstruction distal to the site being assessed¹⁷⁴. Another method requiring venous compression (the VOP method) is already analysed in Section 3.2.

4.2. Approaches

No operator-independent compression ultrasonography TCAs have been described in the literature yet. Most of the literature focuses on compression cuffs used for therapeutic purposes to facilitate venous blood return by utilizing arrays of bladders that transmit pressure to tissues. For effective treatment, pressures between 15 and 50 mmHg are required. However, a study by Hedigalla et al.¹⁷⁷ (Figure 38) concludes that compression sleeves designed with miniaturized air bladders should be supplied with over 250% of the targeted pressure due to propagated pressure loss through the skin, fat, and muscle layers. Golgouneh et al.¹⁷⁸ reviewed soft actuators (pneumatic-based, electrothermal, electrical) and sensors (pneumatic-based, piezoresistive, capacitive, piezoelectric) that could potentially be used in on-body compression applications (Figure 38). The challenges in actuation include dynamics modelling, material properties, inter- and intra-personal variabilities, biocompatibility and safety concerns, and a lack of methods for in-vivo validation. Sensing challenges, such as response drift, hysteresis, nonlinearity, sensitivity to curvature, sensor multiplexing, and manufacturing, are also discussed. The authors concluded that that future developments in soft systems may benefit from more precise pressure sensing, better predictability of applied pressure levels, and smarter closed-loop control strategies. The only limitation of pneumatic-based components is discomfort caused by ventilation issues with air-tight bladders.

¹⁷² Martens et al. The History of Diagnosing Venous Thromboembolism. *Semin Thromb Hemost.* 2024;50(5):739-750. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0044-1779484>

¹⁷³ Lensing et al. Detection of deep-vein thrombosis by real-time B-mode ultrasonography. *N Engl J Med* 1989;320(06):342–345. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM198902093200602>

¹⁷⁴ Gornik H. L. & Sharma A. M. Duplex ultrasound in the diagnosis of lower-extremity deep venous thrombosis. *Circulation.* 2014;129(8):917-921. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.113.002966>

¹⁷⁵ Adam et al. Duplex ultrasound for evaluation of deep venous blood flow in fractured lower extremities. *Polish journal of radiology*, 83, e47–e53. 2018. <https://doi.org/10.5114/pjr.2018.73291>

¹⁷⁶ Necas M. (2010). Duplex ultrasound in the assessment of lower extremity venous insufficiency. *Australasian journal of ultrasound in medicine*, 13(4), 37–45. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2205-0140.2010.tb00178.x>

Figure 38. Compression therapy device with array of mini-bladders¹⁷⁷ (left), array of cuffs for controllable compression¹⁷⁸ on tissues (right).

In VOP method, the objective is to occlude the vein lumen. The bladders are implemented to act as vein-occluding actuators¹⁷⁹ (Figure 39). Bioimpedance-based VOP measuring systems provide leg-overall (integral arterial and venous) features of blood flow. Here, the air cuff on the lower thigh is stepwise inflated to 40-60-80 mmHg to softly close venous outflow from the lower leg. The cuff was also used in a more sophisticated system for basic research¹⁸⁰ (Figure 39) on peripheral blood flow, where only foot-skin blood flow is measured with a laser while the cuff is applied to the calf. The study aimed to gain insights into the origins of blood flow surges in the skin during intermittent pneumatic compression (IPC) therapy.

Figure 39. Impedance venous occlusion plethysmography¹⁷⁹ (left) and a skin blood flow measuring laser system with IPC¹⁸⁰ (right). Here, the cuffs are used to exert occlusion on all venous vessels in the thigh or calf.

Several requirements can be deduced from the literature mentioned above. The TCA must be capable of applying a precise, adjustable pressure range (e.g., 0-200 mmHg) to ensure proper vein compression without causing patient discomfort. Compression should be applied uniformly across the targeted tissue area to avoid uneven imaging results, and the actuator should allow for quick release and re-application of pressure to facilitate various diagnostic maneuvers. In addition, a feedback mechanism should be incorporated to monitor tissue deformation in real time, ensuring consistent and accurate compression, such as a predefined reduction in vein lumen by 50% or 75%. Fail-safe mechanisms are essential to prevent excessive pressure that could damage tissue, including a dedicated safety valve designed to handle pressures of 300-350 mmHg.

¹⁷⁷ Hedigalla et al. Numerical Study to Investigate the Pressure Propagation Patterns by a Compression Sleeve with Miniaturised Air-Bladders. *2022 Moratuwa Engineering Research Conference (MERCon)*, Moratuwa, Sri Lanka, 2022, pp. 1-5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MERCon55799.2022.9906258>

¹⁷⁸ Golgouneh A. & Dunne L. E. A Review in On-Body Compression Using Soft Actuators and Sensors: Applications, Mechanisms, and Challenges. in *IEEE Reviews in Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 17, pp. 166-179, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1109/RBME.2022.3220505>

¹⁷⁹ Heinrich et al. Bridging vascular physiology to vascular medicine: an integrative laboratory class. *Advances in physiology education*, 47(1), 97–116, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1152/advan.00170.2022>

¹⁸⁰ Wang et al. Multiple blood flow surges during intermittent pneumatic compression: The origins and their implications, *Journal of Biomechanics*, Volume 143, 2022, 111264, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2022.111264>

Furthermore, emergency release features must be in place to quickly relieve pressure in case of patient discomfort or equipment failure. The TCA must be integrated with the ultrasound imaging system to synchronize compression with image capture, ensuring accurate data input for AI-based diagnostic support. Lastly, the system should support automation, enabling the TCA to adjust pressure dynamically based on imaging feedback. Additionally, the operation of the actuator should not cause noise discomfort for the patient during prolonged monitoring.

Steering the ultrasound transducer is another task of the same TCA. It must be designed to adjust the roll angle of the ultrasound transducer to optimize the imaging plane. This adjustment is critical for locating veins and improving diagnostic accuracy for DVT. In addition, the TCA plays a crucial role in Doppler ultrasound imaging by enabling precise assessments of blood flow dynamics, making it an essential tool for the accurate and efficient diagnosis of DVT. Hailu¹⁸¹ described modelling and experiments with fabricated prototypes of micro electrostatic actuators (Figure 40). Theoretical modelling showed that the midpoint of the moving plate could be raised by 22 micrometers with 145V. The actuator prototype was fabricated as a micromechanical system with a multi-layered structure. The actuator measured 5 mm in length and 3 mm in width. With a driving voltage of 150V, the hybrid actuator achieved a measured displacement of 6.48 μm in the vertical direction. However, this small displacement is insufficient in the practical context of imaging human tissues.

Figure 40. A micro electrostatic hybrid actuator¹⁸¹.

Hao¹⁸² focused on a simple soft gripper, a four-fingered pneumatic elastomeric robot mimicking a biological finger with infinite degrees of freedom. The robot operates by deflating the soft actuators to open the gripper and approach objects, then inflating to grip them. The soft fingers were made from silicone elastomer using a multi-step molding process with 3D-printed molds. Tests were conducted on finger lengths ranging from 30 mm to 100 mm. Under air pressures of -40 kPa, 0 kPa, and +40 kPa, the fingertip moved from -70 mm to +30 mm, and a maximum pull force of 13.5N was observed (Figure 41). The gripper safely handled soft objects like cacti and milk bags.

¹⁸¹ Hailu et al. Hybrid micro electrostatic actuator. *Microsyst Technol* 22, 319–327. 2016.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00542-015-2424-8>

Figure 41. Kinematics of single soft finger for soft gripper in pneumatic robot¹⁸².

The hand-held venipuncture robotic device developed by Leipheimer et al.¹⁸³ combines ultrasonic imaging with miniaturized robotics for vein cannulation in the forearm. Currently, the operator uses ultrasonic guidance to manually align the needle trajectory with the vein, while the robotic system handles needle interaction with tissues and measures the required force (up to 2 N). The device has demonstrated results comparable to clinical standards, achieving an 87% success rate among 31 participants, with an average procedure time of 93 ± 30 seconds. In trials, manual needle placement accuracy was measured at 0.23 ± 0.17 mm ($n = 25$). However, the current design does not ensure the needle remains centred with the ultrasound-imaged vessel during user or patient movement. Future developments will include a third degree of freedom (DOF) to automatically align the needle trajectory with the underlying vessel as detected by US imaging.

Figure 42. A robotic device for intravenous interventions¹⁸³.

¹⁸² Hao et al. Universal soft pneumatic robotic gripper with variable effective length. 2016 35th Chinese Control Conference (CCC), Chengdu, China, 2016, pp. 6109-6114, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ChiCC.2016.7554316>

¹⁸³ Leipheimer et al. First-in-human evaluation of a hand-held automated venipuncture device for rapid venous blood draws. TECHNOLOGY. 7. 1-10. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S2339547819500067>

Schimmoeller's¹⁸⁴ force sensing device measures the interaction between an imaging transducer and soft tissue while orienting the transducer during freehand imaging (Figure 43). The system includes a 6-axis load cell, an inertial measurement unit, and an optional camera-based motion capture sensor. Tested with a standard ultrasound system, it effectively characterizes the indentation forces applied by the ultrasound probe. In in-vivo testing on the upper leg, the maximum indentation force reached 11 N, resulting in 18% tissue compression. The 6-axis load cell fully characterizes the mechanical interaction with an uncertainty of less than 1 N, allowing for precise quantification of unusual loads and ensuring repeatability and accuracy in measurements. In addition, the specialized hydrogel clip provides a dry interface free of residue, enabling high-quality ultrasound imaging without liquid gels on the patient's skin, using an Aquaflex ultrasound gel pad, which is flexible and disposable.

Figure 43. Ultrasonic imaging probe encased with force sensors (6-axis load cell)¹⁸⁴.

Figure 44. Overhead Origami-based Collapsible Mount (Over-COM)¹⁸⁵ and¹⁸⁶ with inner shell's have 4 DOFs in translational and rotational motion (the 5th DOF).

¹⁸⁴ Schimmoeller et al. Instrumentation of off-the-shelf ultrasound system for measurement of probe forces during freehand imaging, *Journal of Biomechanics*, Vol. 83, 2019, pp. 117-124, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2018.11.032>

¹⁸⁵ Li et al. An Overhead Collapsible Origami-Based Mount for Medical Applications. *Robotics*. 2023; 12(1):21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/robotics12010021>

¹⁸⁶ Lailu et al. Review on Wearable System for Positioning Ultrasound Scanner. *Machines*. 11. 325. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.3390/machines11030325>

The actuation prototype with the highest degree of freedom (a total of five DOF) was researched by Li et al.¹⁸⁵ (Figure 43). The actuator is proposed for overhead human mounting, designed as a compact, lightweight, and portable supplement to automate ultrasonic imaging. It serves as a mount or holder for a transcranial Doppler ultrasonic sensor, intended to meet the requirements of ambulatory monitoring without the need for a skilled operator. The ultrasonic sensor, with the prototype actuator, is angled to acquire the maximum signal from the Doppler ultrasound. Currently, this non-automated procedure relies heavily on the physician's intuition and requires significant practice to master.

The overhead collapsible origami-based mount (Over-COM) features a lightweight, portable, and compact design achieved through its origami structure. It collapses from 10 cm to 2 cm (an 80% reduction), enhancing portability while ensuring sufficient contact force between the medical sensor and the patient's skin. In Li's 2023 tests, the Over-COM prototype moved the medical sensor at a velocity of up to 3.14 cm/s over a scan area of 7 cm², adequately locating the region of interest on the human body. Additionally, the ultrasound wave direction could be adjusted to form a normal angle with the skin surface within a range of 0° to 45°, optimizing Doppler signal tracking. The prototype's complexity arises from its actuation control, utilizing eight motor-actuated strings to achieve 5 degrees of freedom (DOF) within the origami structure.

A very interesting solution for controlling the contact pressure of wrist-worn PPG sensors was proposed by Jai et al.¹⁸⁷ (Figure 45). They researched a thermo-pneumatic regulator designed to maintain consistent contact force between the PPG probe and the measurement site. A watch-type PPG platform was fabricated with an overall size of 35 mm × 19 mm. In PPG measurements on the radial artery at the wrist, while the wrist posture was changed to extension, neutral, or flexion, the regulation of contact force ensured consistent PPG readings, minimizing variations in the PPG amplitude (PPGA). A thermo-pneumatic actuator, which converts thermal energy into mechanical energy through fluid expansion, was selected as the force regulator.

Figure 45. Human wrist wearing the force-regulator integrated¹⁸⁷ PPG sensor.

This actuator has the advantage of generating a force of up to 2 N and can be easily integrated into the portable PPG platform. The total size of the current PPG platform is 35 mm in diameter and 19 mm in thickness. The contact force regulation provided a constant force of 0.6 N between the PPG module and the skin. Jai and colleagues¹⁸⁷ concluded that by using contact force regulation based on a feedback algorithm, the proposed PPG platform significantly improved PPG measurements, reducing variations in the PPGA from 43.2% to 7.2%, despite changes in wrist posture.

The TSA must meet several key requirements to ensure optimal performance in vein imaging. It should enable precise roll angle adjustments with a resolution of at least 0.1 degrees and support a roll range sufficient to cover all necessary angles for complete vein imaging. Real-time adjustments should be possible, either automatically based on imaging feedback or manually controlled by the clinician. Once the optimal angle is found, the TSA must stabilize the transducer to maintain consistent imaging during compression and other

¹⁸⁷ Jai et al. A contact-force regulated photoplethysmography (PPG) platform. *AIP Advances* 1 April 2018; 8 (4): 045210. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5020914>

diagnostic maneuvers. Additionally, the TSA should be integrated with the TCA, ensuring that transducer adjustments are synchronized with tissue compression for optimal imaging results. Safety and precision are paramount, requiring the incorporation of sensors to monitor and correct any drift or unintended movement of the transducer. Furthermore, all movements should be smooth and precise to avoid disrupting the imaging process or causing patient discomfort.

A main component of the TCA and TSA is a pump. The ultrasonic piezo disc pump is a relatively recent innovation¹⁸⁸ in precision gas pumping for medical applications. Because it operates in the ultrasonic region (>20 kHz), it doesn't produce noise and therefore could increase usability of the DVT monitoring device.

There are various available commercial devices available on the market^{189,190,191,192}. The Pump¹⁸⁹ (Figure 46) can achieve a flow rate of up to 2 L/min and is lightweight, weighing only 11 g. The ThrombUS+ project will determine whether such a small piezo pump is capable of providing enough air pressure, with sufficient speed characteristics, to drive TCA and TSA for CDUS and VOP in DVT monitoring methods.

Figure 46. Ultrasonic piezo disc pump with an electronic driver¹⁸⁹.

4.3. Summary of knowledge gaps and potential solutions with implications for requirements

- Several approaches, characteristics, and parameters were analysed for the realization of a precise tissue compression actuator (TCA) to be used in compression duplex ultrasound (CDUS) and venous occlusion plethysmography (VOP) methods for DVT monitoring.
- The analysed actuators are based on different operating principles. Industrial developments, in particular, offer a wide range of enabling possibilities. Pneumatic actuation is the preferred method for biomedical applications, especially for in vivo use. Mechanical robotic principles are still not sufficiently advanced for implementation in on-body-mounted applications.
- Imaging transducer interactions with soft tissues are currently monitored using load cells, which aim to characterize the subtle and subjective maneuvers performed by sonographers with the US imaging

¹⁸⁸ Li et al. "A review of recent studies on valve-less piezoelectric pumps." *The Review of scientific instruments* vol. 94,3 (2023): 031502. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0135700>

¹⁸⁹ Smart pump module. [Online]. Available: <https://www.theleeco.com/product/smart-pump-module/#>

¹⁹⁰ Piezoelectric Micro Pump Testing Kit. [Online]. Available: <https://www.auroraprosci.com/custom-oem-fluidics/oem-miniature-pump/piezoelectric-micro-pump-testing-kit-for-liquid-or-gas-maximum-flow-rate-25-ml-min-@-60-hz-or-120-hz>

¹⁹¹ MPM5 piezo pump. [Online]. Available: https://www.maxcleversz.com/html_products/MPM5-piezo-pump-120.html

¹⁹² muRata. [Online]. Available: <https://www.murata.com/products/mechatronics/fluid>

probe. An alternative solution in obtaining a feedback control signal to TCA about the degree of vein occlusion could be developed by investigating the relationships between parameters calculated from ultrasonic images (e.g., strain, elasticity, or stiffness) and simultaneous data on tissue pressure.

- Long-duration ultrasonic imaging requires sustained acoustic coupling between the imaging transducer and the skin. In cases where standard ultrasound gel is insufficient, hydrogel disposable pads may be a viable alternative.
- Combining TCA and TSA for CDUS and VOP-based DVT monitoring into a single wearable device would increase usability and universality, as there would be no need to swap between CDUS and VOP monitoring devices.

5. Wearable limb activity and orientation monitoring

5.1. Background

The absence of physical activity is one of the main reasons for DVT. Muscle contractions and position changes during exercise cause stagnant blood to exit the veins due to the calf-pump phenomenon, increased heart rate, and gravity. As previously mentioned, the study²⁸ found that ~4-minute foot-only exercise enhanced the blood flow in the femoral vein, with mean flow volume, mean flow velocity, and peak systolic velocity increasing by around 50% above baseline, while the vein cross-section area increased by ~10%. Moreover, the effects of the exercise did not disappear momentarily - the increase in blood flow faded out gradually. 15 minutes after the exercise, the vein cross-section returned to the baseline, while the remaining blood flow parameters had decreased to ~20% above baseline.

Leg positions that restrict blood flow, such as crossed legs, are known to increase the risk of thrombus formation. While there are no studies directly linking prolonged leg crossing to DVT, as performing such experiments would be highly unethical, there's ample research supporting the general consensus that impeded blood circulation increases the risk of DVT¹⁹³. Indirect evidence includes studies on patients confined to bed rest and people on long-haul flights. It is suspected that a prolonged prone position, which is often used to remedy pulmonary insufficiency (e.g., COVID-19) and is necessary after some ophthalmological¹⁹⁴ surgeries, is also a risk factor for DVT. Meanwhile, elevated legs position is known to prompt the blood to exit the vessels thus increasing the blood flow¹⁹⁵.

These observations suggest that monitoring limb activity and position could help alert the patient or medical specialists to the need for physical activity or adjustments in limb position. How this is achieved, relevant examples, and supporting literature are discussed below.

5.2. Use cases of wearable activity monitoring

Inactivity detection is an easily implementable yet highly useful application of an activity monitoring system. The system can detect periods of inactivity and suggest taking a walk, exercising, or engaging in a serious game. Collected activity data can be analysed to improve both personal treatment plans and overall system

¹⁹³ McLendon et al. Deep Venous Thrombosis Risk Factors. Available: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470215/>

¹⁹⁴ Wang et al. Prone Position Increases the Risk of Postoperative Deep Vein Thrombosis in Cervical Spine Surgery by Limiting Venous Return in the Lower Limbs. *Spine (Phila Pa 1976)*. 2024 Aug 15;49(16):1154-1161. <https://doi.org/10.1097/BRS.0000000000004929>

¹⁹⁵ Nicholson et al. Prevention of Venous Thromboembolism in 2020 and Beyond. *J Clin Med*. 2020 Aug 1;9(8):2467. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm9082467>

performance. In addition, exercise guidance through serious games could greatly benefit from biofeedback provided by limb segment orientation sensors, enabling automatic monitoring of exercise accuracy.

5.3. Approaches

Limb activity monitoring can be conducted using either inertial measurement units (IMUs) in the form of on-chip microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) or marker-based optical tracking. Optical tracking, which requires markers and cameras, is less suitable for clinical applications and bed-bound patients. Some IMUs provide up to 9 degrees of freedom (DOF) by integrating a triaxial accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer into a single package. Limb segment orientation—expressed in quaternions, radians, or degrees—can be derived by processing IMU data with various fusion algorithms. Certain sensors are capable of running fusion algorithms on the chip itself, a technique known as edge computing. This method reduces the computational load on the main processor, especially in systems with multiple IMUs. However, the downside of computing IMU orientation at the edge is that the algorithms are pre-designed by the manufacturer and cannot be modified or improved. A potential compromise is to use a small processor dedicated to the IMU chip. This allows full customization of the algorithms while freeing up the main system for other tasks.

5.4. Calibration of IMU-based systems

The magnetometer is the most calibration-dependent sensor among the three components of a 9-DOF IMU. It requires offset, gain, and temperature calibration, referred to as intrinsic or hardware calibration, as well as calibration for ambient effects. Intrinsic calibration, also known as factory calibration, is intended to be long-term. However, experience from the project partner KTU has shown that magnetic sensors, particularly in the presence of stronger magnetic fields, tend to lose their offset very quickly. Calibration for ambient effects is categorized into soft iron and hard iron calibrations. Soft iron calibration corrects for magnetic disturbances caused by nearby ferromagnetic materials, such as structural beams in the walls and furniture. Hard iron calibration compensates for constant magnetic fields in the environment, which may arise from the Earth's magnetic field, nearby magnets or other sources of electromagnetic radiation. In this application, hard iron calibration is unnecessary, as the ambient magnetic field is useful for orientation tracking.

Magnetometer calibration is typically performed by executing specific movements with the sensor so that the measurement of the ambient magnetic field (primarily the Earth's magnetic field, 20–65 μT) is recorded by all sensor axes. The resulting “cloud” of values is then centered by introducing bias compensation (addition), and, if necessary, adjusted to form a perfect sphere through gain compensation (multiplication). Gyroscope calibration involves rotating the gyroscope at a constant rate and measuring its output. The bias is calculated by averaging the measured output over a certain period of time and subtracting the expected value. Accelerometer calibration is conducted by placing the accelerometer in a known position and orientation (e.g., flat on a surface) to measure its output. Offset values are then calculated by subtracting the measured output from the expected value (usually 0 when the accelerometer is at rest) to determine the offset. MEMS sensors typically have dedicated registers where calibration offset (bias) values can be entered. However, it is impractical to expect users to recalibrate the sensor frequently. Ideally, a proposed wearable system should be robust enough to perform adequately without requiring user calibration.

5.5. Accuracy, reliability and limitations

Limited work has been done to determine the reliability of IMU-based systems. Variations in IMU manufacturers, the lack of transparency from commercial device manufacturers regarding the components used, different fusion algorithms, and the absence of universal testing standards or protocols result in

inadequate comparisons between different systems. Taylor et al.¹⁹⁶ performed a robust static and dynamic validation of a single commercial IMU-based system (Opal version 2, APDM Inc., Portland, Oregon), which demonstrated static sensor orientation estimation accuracy within 0.6° and precision within 0.1°. Accuracy was better for smaller rather than larger displacements. The representation of angular velocity provided by the IMUs showed accuracy within 4.4° per second and precision within 0.2° per second. However, it should be noted that the researchers recalibrated the sensors before every measurement, and there was no assessment of cumulative errors. The project partners' (KTU, ATHENA) experience indicates that IMU-based systems are prone to accumulating errors over time and with repeated motions.

5.6. Implementation details and output parameters

The implementation of IMU-based limb activity and orientation monitoring can be achieved either by acquiring a commercial system or by developing a custom system. A minimum of 3–4 separate sensors should be used—one for each segment of the limb and one for the torso: 1) foot, 2) calf, 3) thigh, and 4) torso.

A study¹⁹⁷ has been conducted to determine the optimal locations for IMU sensor pairs. However, the study did not conclude the optimal arrangement for a 4-sensor system. Additionally, the optimal location of the calf sensor for the best estimation of the calf-thigh joint angle does not align with the optimal location for the best estimation of the calf-foot joint angle. Furthermore, the differences in estimation accuracy may be insignificant compared to deviations caused by other prominent factors, such as unintended sensor movement or changes in sensor orientation due to underlying muscle contractions.

The optimal data acquisition rate is 50 Hz, though this is not a mandatory criterion as long as the system performs adequately. Orientation data should be output in quaternions, degrees, or radians. Additionally, raw sensor data may need to be output as well. This can be expressed in m/s² for acceleration, rad/s or deg/s (dps) for the gyroscope, and μ T for the magnetometer. It is also acceptable to output the data in digital counts if performing the conversion during data processing benefits the system design.

5.7. Commercially available IMU systems

There are many commercially available IMU-based motion-capture systems that include sensors and data processing algorithms. Notable examples include 3D Motion Capture (Noraxon, USA), Xsens (Movella, USA), and X-IMU3 (x-IO, UK). The latter offers open-source code for controlling their hardware on various development platforms, which can be highly beneficial for developing a custom solution for the project.

5.8. Summary of knowledge gaps and potential solutions with implications for requirements

- The magnetometer is the most calibration-dependent sensor among the three components of a 9-DOF IMU. However, many 6-DOF IMUs and fusion algorithms exclude compass data, relying only on the accelerometer and gyroscope. This decision largely depends on the application. In use cases such as gaming and indoor applications, orientation is often estimated without magnetic data, as it can cause more harm than good. However, the absence of a global orientation reference may lead to cumulative orientation errors, which could be detrimental to the intended application.

¹⁹⁶ Taylor et al. Static and dynamic validation of inertial measurement units. *Gait & posture* vol. 57 (2017): 80-84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2017.05.026>

¹⁹⁷ Niswander et al. Optimization of IMU Sensor Placement for the Measurement of Lower Limb Joint Kinematics. *Sensors*. 2020; 20(21):5993. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20215993>

- Gyroscope drift is a well-known issue that affects activity monitoring systems, including commercial ones. An additional reference method or algorithmic solution could be implemented for offset clearance or position verification.
- The mechanical attachment of sensors requires careful consideration. A small rotation of an IMU can result from fabric sliding on the leg or changes in leg shape due to muscle contraction. Even a slight rotation of a tiny sensor can lead to significant errors in limb motion visualization. Therefore, the visualization algorithm should be designed to correct itself, either when the limb returns to a known position or by using reference or redundant sensors.
- It can be difficult to identify when a fusion algorithm produces data discrepancies due to errors or sensor saturation. The use of additional sensors may help mitigate this problem.

AI-based orientation estimation could offer a solution to performance issues commonly encountered in wearable IMU applications. However, it may require more than the minimal number of sensors per limb segment. Training artificial intelligence models using IMU output may also require more than one IMU sensor per limb segment, as additional data may be necessary to introduce corrections.